

Safety Platform for Emergency vaccines

AESI Case Definition Companion Guide Guillain Barré and Miller Fisher Syndromes

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CEPI Project Manager	Thomas Cole		
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Dissemination Level	Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/>			

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Description of the deliverable	<p>This deliverable updates the first Companion Guide for GBS (SO2 D2.5.2.1, Feb 2021) as follows: SNOMED-CT codes added; separate tables for ICD-9/10-CM and SNOMED-CT codes versus MedDRA codes; MedDRA table of codes includes Preferred and Lower Level Terms; updated Background Rates and Risk Factor Appendices based on scoping literature review; data abstraction and interpretation form along with algorithms for assessing level of diagnostic certainty amended to harmonize with those available online as part of digital transformation including a glossary of terms; order of appendices aligned with that used for all companion guides developed since 2022. This guide can be used by stakeholders to assess the occurrence of GBS in several settings including as an adverse event following immunization.</p>
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Key words Guillain Barré Syndrome, GBS, Miller Fisher Syndrome, Brighton case definition, risk factors, background rates, ICD-9-CM, ICD-10-CM, MedDRA, case definition level of certainty.

DOCUMENT HISTORY

NAME OF DOCUMENT	DATE	VERSION	CONTRIBUTOR(S)	DESCRIPTION
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Transform Tier 1 AESI Tools	18 January 2021	V0.1	Barbara Law, Marta Rojo Villaescusa	First draft
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Transform Tier 1 AESI Tools	29 January 2021	V0.1	Corry Dekker	Review
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Transform Tier 1 AESI Tools	31 January 2021	V0.1	Miriam Sturkenboom	Review
SO2-D2.5.2.1 Transform Tier 1 AESI Tools	09 February 2021	V1.0	Barbara Law	Final version
SPEAC 2.0 D2.4.2	23 Feb 2026	V2.0	Barbara Law Hammad Ali Ariel Zadok Dale Nordenberg Wan-Ting Huang Marta V Rojo	<p>Change order of appendices as follows: 1 = Code terms (was 4) 2 = Background incidence (was 2) 3 = Risk factors (was 1) 4 = Caveats and guidance for real time investigation (was 3) 5 = Data abstraction form and algorithms for levels of certainty (was 5, 6 and 7)</p> <p>Renumber references to match the new order of appendices</p> <p>Add SNOMED-CT codes. Separate table for MedDRA codes, including Preferred and Lower Level terms (PT and LLT), versus ICD-9/10-CM and SNOMED-CT codes</p> <p>Updated Background Rates Appendix</p> <p>Updated and expanded Risk Factor Appendix</p> <p>Updated case report forms and algorithms to the latest versions developed as part of digital transformation</p>

DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS

ADEM	Acute Disseminated Encephalomyelitis
AESI	Adverse Events of Special Interest
AFP	Acute flaccid paralysis
AIDP	Acute inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy
AIV3	Adjuvanted Trivalent inactivated influenza vaccine
AMAN	Acute motor axonal neuropathy
AMSAN	Acute motor and sensory axonal neuropathy
BC	Brighton Collaboration
CAR	Chimeric antigen receptor
CCIV4	Cell based Quadrivalent inactivated influenza vaccine
CD	Case Definition
CEPI	Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness and Innovation
CHIKV	Chikungunya virus
CI	Confidence interval
CIDP	Chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy
CM	Clinical Modification (relates to numbered versions of ICD codes)
CMV	Cytomegalovirus
CSF	Cerebrospinal Fluid
CT	Computed Tomography
CUI	Concept Unique Identifier
DTaP	Diphtheria, tetanus, acellular pertussis vaccine
DTP	Diphtheria, tetanus, whole cell pertussis vaccine
DTR	Deep tendon reflex
EBV	Epstein Barr Virus
ED	Emergency department
EEG	Electroencephalogram
EMG	Electromyogram
FAERS	FDA adverse event reporting system
GBS	Guillain Barré Syndrome
HAV	Hepatitis A vaccine
HBV	Hepatitis B vaccine
HD-IIV3	High-Dose Trivalent inactivated influenza vaccine

HEV	Hepatitis E virus
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HPV	Human papillomavirus
HPV2	Human papillomavirus bivalent vaccine
HPV4	Human papillomavirus quadrivalent vaccine
HPV9	Human papillomavirus nonavalent vaccine
HR	Hazards ratio
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
ICI	Immune checkpoint inhibitor
IIV	Inactivate influenza vaccine
IIV3	Trivalent inactivated influenza vaccine
IIV4	Quadrivalent inactivated influenza vaccine
IIV-HD	High-Dose inactivated influenza vaccine
JE-L	Live attenuated Japanese encephalitis vaccine
IL	Interleuken
IPV	Inactivated polio vaccine
IVIG	Intravenous immune globulin
LAIV3	Trivalent live attenuated influenza. vaccine
LAIV4	Quadrivalent live attenuated influenza. Vaccine
LOC	Level of diagnostic certainty
LP	Lumbar Puncture
MedDRA	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities
MenACWY-D	Quadrivalent Meningococcal Polysaccharide Diphtheria Toxoid Conjugate Vaccine
MFS	Miller Fisher Syndrome
MIV	Monovalent Inactivated Influenza Vaccine
MMR	Measles mumps rubella vaccine
MMRV	Measles mumps rubella varicella vaccine
MR	Measles rubella vaccine
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NCS	Nerve Conduction Studies
NINCDS	National Institute of Neurological and Communicative Disorders and Stroke
NPV	Negative predictive value
OPD	Outpatient department
OR	Odds ratio
PCV13	13 valent pneumococcal conjugate vaccine
PCV20	20 valent pneumococcal conjugate vaccine
PPV	Positive predictive value
PPSV23	23 valent pneumococcal polysaccharide vaccine
RBC	Red Blood Cell
RIV3	Recombinant Trivalent influenza vaccine
RIV4	Recombinant Quadrivalent influenza vaccine

RR	Relative risk
RSVPreF/PSVPreF3	Respiratory syncytial virus prefusion F
RZV	Recombinant zoster vaccine
SCCS	Self-controlled case series
SCRI	Self-Controlled Risk Interval
SD-IIV3	Standard-dose Trivalent inactivated influenza vaccine
SIV	Swine Influenza Virus
SLE	Systemic lupus erythematosus
SPEAC	Safety Platform for Emergency Vaccines
Tdap	Tetanus, diphtheria(reduced content), acellular pertussis vaccine
TIV	Trivalent influenza vaccine
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
TSH	Thyroid stimulating hormone
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System
VAAP	Vaccine Associated Paralytic Poliomyelitis
WBC	White Blood Cell
ZIKV	Zika virus
ZVL	Zoster Vaccine Live

1. Background

CEPI has contracted with the Brighton Collaboration, through the Task Force for Global Health, to harmonize the safety assessment of CEPI-funded vaccines via its Safety Platform for Emergency vaccines (SPEAC) Project.

A key aspect of this harmonization has been creation of lists of priority potential adverse events of special interest (AESI) that are relevant to vaccines targeting CEPI target diseases. Having identified relevant AESI, SPEAC then works to ensure tools and resources are available to facilitate a standard approach to global vaccine safety research and pharmacovigilance activities.

SPEAC Work Package 2 creates resources and tools for the AESI including:

1. Tabular summaries of risk factors and background rates for each AESI.
2. Guidance on AESI real-time investigation, data collection, analysis and presentation.
3. Spreadsheet summaries of ICD9/10 and MedDRA codes for each AESI.
4. Tools to facilitate capturing the specific clinical data needed to meet BC AESI case definitions across a variety of settings applicable to clinical trials, epidemiologic studies and individual case causality assessment. These include:
 - a. Data abstraction and interpretation forms to facilitate capturing data from medical charts and applying it to determine a given AESI case definition level of certainty.
 - b. Rules for creating new variables relevant to the case definition criteria, if needed.
 - c. Tabular formulae for determining Brighton Level of Diagnostic Certainty (LOC) based on the final value of each case definition criterion (YES, NO, UNKNOWN).
 - d. Pictorial algorithm showing the path to each LOC (1-5) based on criterion values. This contains all the information needed to determine LOC and thus can be used as a stand-alone tool.
 - e. Glossary of terms relevant to anaphylaxis and the neurologic AESI.

Initially these resources and tools were developed as separate documents but starting in 2020 they were pulled together into a single 'Companion Guide' for each published Brighton Collaboration Case Definition. The first Guide for GBS (V1.0) was finalized Feb 9, 2021 [5]. In November 2022, SPEAC 2.0 started. A new key feature was to embark on Digital Transformation of tools and resources developed as part of the original SPEAC project from 2019 through October 2022. The original data abstraction forms, tabular checklist and level of certainty algorithms published in V1.0 of the Companion Guides have been revised as part of the digital transformation process.

Another initiative of SPEAC 2.0 was to extend and update the original background rate and risk factor sections in the guide, based on a more thorough literature review than was done for the first versions of several companion guides including GBS.

2. Objective of this deliverable

To update the Companion guide for GBS: to incorporate changes made to harmonize across all guides: language, order of appendices and provision of SNOMEDCT codes (in addition to MedDRA, ICD-9-CM and ICD-10-CM); to update the data abstraction forms and algorithms so they match what are being used for Digital Transformation including the Automated Brighton Classification (ABC Tool) and other digital data collection tools; to provide newly published data for GBS background incidence and risk factors; and to expand the section on vaccines as a risk factor for GBS 3.

3. Methods

The methods for developing each of the tools are briefly described in Appendix 6 of this Guide along with links to source documents which have more detailed methodology. More detail regarding the literature review done to capture newly published evidence on GBS background incidence and risk factors as well as a new section related to all published evidence on vaccine – GBS associations is presented below.

A scoping literature review was done using two different search strategies: 1) the incidence and risk factors for the outcome, 2) vaccine association with GBS.

Four searches were conducted for: 1. background incidence, 2. risk factors, 3. vaccine association with GBS, 4. Case reports of GBS after vaccination.

1. Literature search to identify BACKGROUND INCIDENCE

("Guillain-Barre Syndrome/epidemiology"[Mesh:noexp]

OR

("Guillain-Barre Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Guillain Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barré"[tiab] OR "GBS"[tiab] OR "Miller Fisher Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Miller Fisher"[tiab] OR "Miller-Fisher"[tiab] OR "Fisher Syndrome"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyradiculoneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Autoimmune Neuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Autoimmune Neuropathies"[tiab] OR "Bickerstaff Brainstem Encephalitis"[tiab])

AND ("Incidence"[Mesh:noexp] OR "Epidemiology"[Mesh:noexp] OR "incidence"[tiab] OR "epidemiology"[tiab]))

AND English[lang]

AND ("Observational Study"[Publication Type] OR "Review"[Publication Type] OR "Systematic Review"[Publication Type] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type])

AND ("2009/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT])

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2. Literature search to identify RISK FACTORS

("Guillain-Barre Syndrome/epidemiology"[Mesh:noexp]
 OR
 ("Guillain-Barre Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Guillain Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barré"[tiab] OR
 "GBS"[tiab] OR "Miller Fisher Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Miller Fisher"[tiab] OR "Miller-Fisher"[tiab] OR "Fisher
 Syndrome"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyneuropathies"[tiab]
 OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating
 Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory
 Polyradiculoneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute
 Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Autoimmune Neuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute
 Autoimmune Neuropathies"[tiab] OR "Bickerstaff Brainstem Encephalitis"[tiab])
 AND ("Risk Factors"[Mesh] OR "risk factor"[tiab] OR "risk factors"[tiab] OR "risk score"[tiab] OR "risk scores"[tiab]
 OR "health correlate"[tiab] OR "health correlates"[tiab] OR "population at risk"[tiab] OR "populations at risk"[tiab]))
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 AND ("Review"[Publication Type] OR "Systematic Review"[Publication Type] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type])
 AND ("2009/01/01"[PDAT]: "3000/12/31"[PDAT])
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 19033158[pmid] OR 24624471[pmid] OR 23770307[pmid] OR 32278359[pmid] OR 22835735[pmid])
 NOT ("Incidence"[Mesh:noexp] OR "Epidemiology"[Mesh:noexp] OR "incidence"[tiab] OR "epidemiology"[tiab])

3. Literature search to identify: vaccine association with GBS

("Guillain-Barre Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Guillain Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barré"[tiab] OR
 "GBS"[tiab] OR "Miller Fisher Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Miller Fisher"[tiab] OR "Miller-Fisher"[tiab] OR "Fisher
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 OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating
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 Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Autoimmune Neuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute
 Autoimmune Neuropathies"[tiab] OR "Bickerstaff Brainstem Encephalitis"[tiab])

AND ("Vaccines"[Mesh] OR "vaccine"[tiab] OR "vaccines"[tiab] OR "Vaccination"[Mesh] OR "vaccination"[tiab] OR "vaccinations"[tiab] OR "vaccinate"[tiab] OR "vaccinated"[tiab] OR "immunization"[mesh] OR "immunization"[tiab] OR "immunizations"[tiab] OR "immunisation"[tiab] OR "immunisations"[tiab] OR "immunize"[tiab] OR "immunized"[tiab] OR "immunise"[tiab] OR "immunised"[tiab])

AND English[lang]

AND ("Observational Study"[Publication Type] OR "Clinical Trial"[Publication Type] OR "Review"[Publication Type] OR "Systematic Review"[Publication Type] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type] OR "Clinical Trial Protocol"[Publication Type])

AND ("2009/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT])

NOT ("animals"[Mesh] NOT "humans"[Mesh])

NOT (20600491[pmid] OR 28657162[pmid] OR 11604736[pmid] OR 13982385[pmid] OR 10082069[pmid] OR 18834494[pmid] OR 3472424[pmid] OR 8825272[pmid] OR 4051833[pmid] OR 8301426[pmid] OR 18443311[pmid] OR 3982649[pmid] OR 12792145[pmid] OR 1789689[pmid] OR 8189671[pmid] OR 2789453[pmid] OR 28477675[pmid] OR 18973064[pmid] OR 17595235[pmid] OR 7918815[pmid] OR 8988116[pmid] OR 27022152[pmid] OR 12131933[pmid] OR 21428966[pmid] OR 15122430[pmid] OR 27477441[pmid] OR 11402102[pmid] OR 14696900[pmid] OR 28722564[pmid] OR 7998771[pmid] OR 20102270[pmid] OR 24102733[pmid] OR 11954865[pmid] OR 15749412[pmid] OR 8612191[pmid] OR 26088600[pmid] OR 7943604[pmid] OR 11895024[pmid] OR 2631660[pmid] OR 3574191[pmid] OR 18662736[pmid] OR 17683586[pmid] OR 16521871[pmid] OR 9796754[pmid] OR 3969208[pmid] OR 3262981[pmid] OR 2290923[pmid] OR 9436731[pmid] OR 7086793[pmid] OR 8406059[pmid] OR 16801513[pmid] OR 10733998[pmid] OR 8301426[pmid] OR 9440401[pmid] OR 18042139[pmid] OR 1517173[pmid] OR 1729571[pmid] OR 14607309[pmid] OR 9703176[pmid] OR 15242417[pmid] OR 12682322[pmid] OR 8933229[pmid] OR 1922642[pmid] OR 2718810[pmid] OR 10680793[pmid] OR 8042448[pmid] OR 11528157[pmid] OR 15221623[pmid] OR 9153599[pmid] OR 10809910[pmid] OR 9062775[pmid] OR 7785420[pmid] OR 33462778[pmid] OR 27666816[pmid] OR 26948435[pmid] OR 22694000[pmid] OR 19088488[pmid] OR 19388722[pmid] OR 19033158[pmid] OR 24624471[pmid] OR 23770307[pmid] OR 32278359[pmid] OR 22835735[pmid])

4. Literature search to identify: CASE REPORTS of GBS after vaccination

("Guillain-Barre Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Guillain Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barre"[tiab] OR "Guillain-Barré"[tiab] OR "GBS"[tiab] OR "Miller Fisher Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Miller Fisher"[tiab] OR "Miller-Fisher"[tiab] OR "Fisher Syndrome"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Polyradiculoneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyradiculoneuropathies"[tiab] OR "Acute Autoimmune Neuropathy"[tiab] OR "Acute Autoimmune Neuropathies"[tiab] OR "Bickerstaff Brainstem Encephalitis"[tiab])

AND ("Vaccines"[Mesh] OR "vaccine"[tiab] OR "vaccines"[tiab] OR "Vaccination"[Mesh] OR "vaccination"[tiab] OR "vaccinations"[tiab] OR "vaccinate"[tiab] OR "vaccinated"[tiab] OR "immunization"[mesh] OR "immunization"[tiab] OR "immunizations"[tiab] OR "immunisation"[tiab] OR "immunisations"[tiab] OR "immunize"[tiab] OR "immunized"[tiab] OR "immunise"[tiab] OR "immunised"[tiab])

AND English[lang]

AND ("Case Reports"[Publication Type])

AND ("2009/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT])

NOT ("animals"[Mesh] NOT "humans"[Mesh])

NOT (20600491[pmid] OR 28657162[pmid] OR 11604736[pmid] OR 13982385[pmid] OR 10082069[pmid] OR 18834494[pmid] OR 3472424[pmid] OR 8825272[pmid] OR 4051833[pmid] OR 8301426[pmid] OR 18443311[pmid])

OR 3982649[pmid] OR 12792145[pmid] OR 1789689[pmid] OR 8189671[pmid] OR 2789453[pmid] OR 28477675[pmid] OR 18973064[pmid] OR 17595235[pmid] OR 7918815[pmid] OR 8988116[pmid] OR 27022152[pmid] OR 12131933[pmid] OR 21428966[pmid] OR 15122430[pmid] OR 27477441[pmid] OR 11402102[pmid] OR 14696900[pmid] OR 28722564[pmid] OR 7998771[pmid] OR 20102270[pmid] OR 24102733[pmid] OR 11954865[pmid] OR 15749412[pmid] OR 8612191[pmid] OR 26088600[pmid] OR 7943604[pmid] OR 11895024[pmid] OR 2631660[pmid] OR 3574191[pmid] OR 18662736[pmid] OR 17683586[pmid] OR 16521871[pmid] OR 9796754[pmid] OR 3969208[pmid] OR 3262981[pmid] OR 2290923[pmid] OR 9436731[pmid] OR 7086793[pmid] OR 8406059[pmid] OR 16801513[pmid] OR 10733998[pmid] OR 8301426[pmid] OR 9440401[pmid] OR 18042139[pmid] OR 1517173[pmid] OR 1729571[pmid] OR 14607309[pmid] OR 9703176[pmid] OR 15242417[pmid] OR 12682322[pmid] OR 8933229[pmid] OR 1922642[pmid] OR 2718810[pmid] OR 10680793[pmid] OR 8042448[pmid] OR 11528157[pmid] OR 15221623[pmid] OR 9153599[pmid] OR 10809910[pmid] OR 9062775[pmid] OR 7785420[pmid] OR 33462778[pmid] OR 27666816[pmid] OR 26948435[pmid] OR 22694000[pmid] OR 19088488[pmid] OR 19388722[pmid] OR 19033158[pmid] OR 24624471[pmid] OR 23770307[pmid] OR 32278359[pmid] OR 22835735[pmid])

The results of all 4 searches were uploaded into a combined COVIDENCE file. All titles/abstract and full texts were screened by HA or BL. All articles related to background incidence were further screened by MRV to identify articles that had original incidence rate data in the general population. A standard excel spreadsheet was used to extract the incidence data. Subsequently, the excel file was reviewed by a different investigator (BL) before updating the background incidence table.

Data extraction for all articles related to general risk factors (not including vaccine as a risk factor) was done by two investigators (HA & BL) using a word document to capture key findings. For both searches, additional articles were found via hand search of the included articles' citation lists. Citations included in all reviews and meta-analyses were obtained to ensure only original data would be captured.

Data extraction for all articles related to possible or proven vaccine-associations was done by EpiCare Consulting LLC. All data were extracted into an Excel template and summarized in Table 3.

4. Results

PRISMA flow diagram for the literature review was prepared.

The outputs are provided as separate Appendices to simplify printing as needed. These are provided as shown below.

1. GBS Diagnosis Codes: ICD-9CM, ICD-10CM, MedDRA and SNOMEDCT
2. GBS Background Rates
3. GBS Risk Factors
4. GBS Case Definition key caveats for diagnosis, data analysis and presentation
5. GBS Data Abstraction and Interpretation Form, Algorithms to determine the level of certainty and glossary of terms.
6. Summary of methods. Also provides links, as appropriate, to the original deliverable documents with more detailed methodology.

5. Recommendations & discussion

This guide brings together resources and tools related to the AESI of GBS including risk factors, background rates, guidance for real time investigation, ICD-9/10-CM, MedDRA and SNOMED codes for data entry or database searching and provides tools for collecting and interpreting clinical data to determine level of diagnostic certainty for the Brighton GBS or Miller Fisher case definitions.

APPENDIX 1.

GBS and Miller Fisher Diagnostic Codes: ICD-9-CM, ICD-10-CM, SNOMEDCT and MedDRA

Table 1.1 Guillain Barre Syndrome (GBS) and Miller Fisher Syndrome (MFS) Diagnostic Codes: ICD-9/10-CM and SNOMEDCT. Search terms for GBS and MFS in electronic healthcare databases.

UMLS		Medical Diagnostic Terms and Codes			
CUI	Name	Term	ICD-9-CM	ICD-10-CM	SNOMEDCT
C0018378	Guillain-Barre Syndrome	Guillain-Barre syndrome		G61.0	
C3542501	Acute infective polyneuritis	Guillain-Barré syndrome			40956001
		Guillain-Barre syndrome			155082001
		Guillain-Barre syndrome			267707000
		Acute infective polyneuritis	357.0		129131007
					193173004
		Acute infective polyneuritis NOS			193176007
C0032541	Polyneuritis	Polyneuritis			76886005
		Inflammatory polyneuropathy		G61	300951006
		Other inflammatory polyneuropathies		G61.8	
C0032587	Polyradiculoneuropathy			128078004	
C4551910	Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy			26261000119109	
C38909441	Acute Motor Axonal Neuropathy			715770009	
C3900111	Acute motor sensory axonal neuropathy			71622005	
C0393907	Axonal sensorimotor neuropathy			230657007	
C0270921	Axonal neuropathy			60703000	
C1263857	Peripheral axonal neuropathy			128208007	
C5190783	Pharyngeal-cervical-brachial variant of Guillain-Barre syndrome			783010003	
C4707803	Paraparetic variant of Guillain-Barre syndrome			766722008	
C5567526	Facial diplegia with paresthesia			1172701002	
C0393799	Miller Fisher Syndrome	Miller Fisher Syndrome		G61.0	
		Fisher's syndrome	357.0		1767005
		Miller-Fisher variant of Guillain-Barre syndrome			193175006
C5190881	Acute pure sensory neuropathy			230548007	
C4707661	Acute sensory ataxic neuropathy			783244002	
C0270886	Polyneuritis cranialis	Polyneuritis cranialis			766049000
		Disorders of multiple cranial nerves		G52.7	56795008

No broader concepts identified.

Table 1.2 Guillain Barre (GBS) and Miller Fisher Syndrome (MFS) Diagnosis Codes: MedDRA Codes. Search and/or coding terms for GBS and MFS in pharmacovigilance data. Preferred Terms (PT) and Lower Level Terms (LLT) were obtained using MedDRA V 28.1.

inUMLS		MedDRA Terms and Codes		
CUI	Name	Preferred Term (PT)	Lower Level Terms (LLT)	Code
C0018378	Guillain-Barre Syndrome	Guillain-Barre syndrome	Guillain-Barre syndrome	10018767
			Guillain Barre syndrome	10018766
			Syndrome Guillain-Barre	10042812
		Zika virus associated Guillain Barre syndrome	Zika virus associated Guillain Barre syndrome Zika virus associated Guillain Barre-like syndrome	10081046 10081055
C0018378	Guillain-Barre Syndrome	Ascending flaccid paralysis	Ascending flaccid paralysis	10087798
C3542501	Acute Infective Polyneuritis	Guillain-Barre syndrome	Acute infective polyneuritis	10000813
		Ascending flaccid paralysis	Paralysis ascending	10033803
C0032541	Polyneuritis	Polyneuropathy	Polyneuritis	10036104
C0032587	Polyradiculoneuropathy	Polyradiculoneuropathy	Polyradiculoneuropathy	10087869
C4551910	Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy	Guillain-Barre syndrome	Acute inflammatory demyelinating polyradiculopathy	10067604
			Acute inflammatory demyelinating polyradiculoneuropathy	10067898
			AIDP	10087910
C38909441	Acute Motor Axonal Neuropathy	Acute motor axonal neuropathy	Acute motor axonal neuropathy	10076658
C3900111	Acute motor sensory axonal neuropathy	Acute motor-sensory axonal neuropathy	Acute motor-sensory axonal neuropathy	10076657
C0270921	Axonal neuropathy	Axonal neuropathy	Axonal neuropathy	10003882
C0393799	Miller Fisher syndrome	Miller Fisher syndrome	Miller Fisher syndrome	10049567
			Fisher syndrome	10076684
C0154733	Multiple cranial nerve palsy	Cranial nerve palsies multiple	Cranial nerve palsies multiple	10011314
			Multiple cranial nerve palsies	10028186
C0152025	Polyneuropathy	Polyneuropathy	Polyneuropathy	10036105
			Polyneuropathy NOS	10036118

APPENDIX 2.

GBS Background Rates

2.1 GBS Background Rates

TABLE 2.1. GBS BACKGROUND RATES BY GEOGRAPHIC REGION: STUDIES OF ALL AGES OR ADULTS ONLY

Country	Study years	Population (age in years)	Incidence per 100,000 person years [95% confidence interval] (total cases)		
			All	Males	Females
AFRICA					
Libya [6]	1983-1985	0-9	0.3 (2)	-- (0)	0.7 (2)
		10-19	1.8 (6)	2.3 (4)	1.2 (2)
		20-29	3.1 (6)	4.0 (4)	2.1 (2)
		30-39	5.9 (9)	3.9 (3)	8.1 (6)
		40-49	1.7 (2)	1.6 (1)	1.8 (1)
		50-59	1.5 (1)	-- (0)	3.1 (1)
		≥ 60	1.1 (1)	2.1 (1)	-- (0)
		All ages	1.73 (27)	1.62 (13)	1.85 (14)
Tanzania [7]	1984-1992	12-29	0.7 (25)		
		30-49	1.3 (28)		
		≥ 50	0.5 (6)		
		All ages	0.83 (59)		
AMERICAS					
Canada [8] (Ontario) <i>Note: incidence data were provided by year for 2015 through 2020. Only 2018 is presented here as the most recent data before COVID-19. All year data are available in the excel spreadsheet and the online dashboard.</i>	2018	0-4	0.83 [0.31–1.82]	0.81 [0.17–2.38]	0.86 [0.18–2.50]
		5-11	0.46 [0.15–1.08]	0.91 [0.30–2.13]	0.00 [0.00–0.00]
		12-15	0.64 [0.18–1.65]	0.63 [0.08–2.28]	0.66 [0.08–2.37]
		16-19	1.14 [0.49–2.25]	1.66 [0.61–3.61]	0.59 [0.07–2.13]
		20-24	0.79 [0.34–1.56]	1.14 [0.42–2.48]	0.42 [0.05–1.50]
		25-29	1.29 [0.68–2.20]	0.96 [0.31–2.25]	1.63 [0.70–3.21]
		30-39	1.73 [1.19–2.43]	2.75 [1.79–4.02]	0.73 [0.29–1.50]
		40-49	1.35 [0.87–1.99]	1.44 [0.76–2.46]	1.26 [0.65–2.21]
		50-59	2.08 [1.50–2.80]	2.24 [1.42–3.36]	1.92 [1.17–2.96]
		60-69	3.53 [2.69–4.55]	4.09 [2.82–5.75]	3.00 [1.96–4.40]
		70-79	3.84 [2.75–5.24]	5.15 [3.34–7.61]	2.70 [1.51–4.45]
		≥80	4.00 [2.59–5.91]	6.43 [3.68–10.4]	2.39 [1.09–4.55]
All ages	1.88 [1.66–2.12]	2.31 [1.97–2.69]	1.46 [1.20–1.77]		
Canada [9] (Quebec)	1989-2014	<25		Not included	1.49 [1.17-1.89] (68)
		25-34			1.44 [1.22-1.69] (144)
		≥35			1.06 [0.65-1.73] (16)
		All ages			1.42 [1.24-1.61] (228)
Canada [10]	2000-2002	1-4	2.1 [1.2-3.6]		
		5-22	0.6 [0.3-0.9]		
		0.2-22	0.8 [0.56-1.14] (33)		
Canada [11] (Alberta)	1994-2004	1-110	1.6 (496)		
Canada [12] i. Quebec	1983-1989	All ages	i. 1.51 (1302)		

Ontario			1.78 (1031)		
USA[13] (National) <i>Note: Incidence data calculated separately for each database. See Table 2.3 for details on the database populations</i>	2019 BHI	18-25	1.56 [1.11–2.15]	3.85 [3.38–4.37]	2.53 [2.19–2.90]
		26-35	2.66 [2.04–3.41]		
		36-45	2.86 [2.25–3.57]		
		46-55	3.16 [2.57–3.83]		
		56-64	4.63 [3.95–5.39]		
		All ages	3.11 [2.83–3.42]		
	2019 CVS Health	18-25	1.25 [0.75–1.95]	2.51 [2.06–3.04]	1.95 [1.56–2.39]
		26-35	1.46 [0.94–2.18]		
		36-45	2.10 [1.50–2.88]		
		46-55	2.98 [2.28–3.84]		
56-64		3.01 [2.27–3.91]			
All ages	2.23 [1.93–2.56]				
2019 Health Core	18-25	1.65 [1.13–2.32]	2.64 [2.23–3.10]	2.01 [1.66–2.42]	
	26-35	2.06 [1.47–2.81]			
	36-45	2.01 [1.48–2.67]			
	46-55	2.86 [2.26–3.59]			
	56-64	2.80 [2.17–3.56]			
	All ages	2.33 [2.05–2.62]			
2019 Market Scan	18-25	1.13 [0.72–1.68]	2.83 [2.41–3.29]	1.71 [1.40–2.06]	
	26-35	1.81 [1.28–2.50]			
	36-45	2.34 [1.79–3.02]			
	46-55	2.57 [2.03–3.22]			
	56-64	2.99 [2.37–3.71]			
	All ages	2.24 [1.99–2.52]			
2019 Optum	18-25	2.01 [1.27–3.02]	2.34 [1.91–2.84]	3.71 [3.12–4.38]	
	26-35	2.70 [1.94–3.64]			
	36-45	3.21 [2.44–4.15]			
	46-55	2.85 [2.15–3.70]			
	56-64	3.78 [2.90–4.84]			
	All ages	2.97 [2.61–3.37]			
2019 Medicare	≥65	4.63 [4.36–4.90]			
USA [14] (National)	2009-2015	0-17	0.4 (288)	1.2 (1932)	0.9 (1554)
		18-34	0.7 (539)		
		35-44	1.0 (518)		
		45-54	1.3 (691)		
		55-64	2.0 (954)		
		≥65	2.0 (496)		
		All ages			
USA[15]	2004-2015	10-55 Pregnancy plus 42 days postpartum			0.24 [0.04–0.78]

		10-55 Pregnancy only			0.28 [0.05–0.93]
USA[16] (Multiple-VSD)	2000- 2009	0-4 5-17 18-24 25-49 50-64 ≥65 All ages	3.13 [2.98-3.28]	0.70 [0.29-1.11] 1.13 [0.84-1.43] 1.36 [0.85-1.87] 2.52 [2.18-2.86] 5.19 [4.53-5.84] 12.84[11.47-14.20] 3.70 [2.46-3.95]	0.93 [0.44-1.42] 0.78 [0.53-1.03] 1.16 [0.70-1.61] 1.82 [1.54-2.09] 3.99 [3.45-4.54] 8.50 [7.52-9.48] 2.64 [2.45-2.84]
USA [17] (Tennessee)	2000- 2010	All ages	1.40 [1.20-1.59]		
USA [18] (California)	1998- 2004	10-17 18-25 26-62 All ages	2.4 [2.0-2.9] (121)	2.1 [0.8-4.6] (6) 0.8 [0.1-3.0] (2) 3.3 [2.5-4.2] (58)	1.8 [0.6-4.2] (5) 0.4 [0.01-2.1] (1) 2.3 [1.7-3.1] (49)
USA [19] (Military)	1999- 2007	<20 20-24 25-29 30-34 35-39 ≥40 All ages	3.48 [2.47-4.75] 2.23 [1.82-2.71] 2.21 [1.70-2.83] 1.61 [1.11-2.26] 1.73 [1.19-2.45] 3.29 [2.41-4.39] 2.28 [2.03-2.54]	2.22 [1.96-2.51]	2.59 [1.93-3.39]
USA (National data) [20]	2000 2001 2002 2003 2004	≥18	1.75 (993) 1.68 (963) 1.71 (986) 1.79 (1042) 1.65 (972)		
USA (Michigan) [21]	1992- 1999	All ages	6.3 (471)	7.4 [6.6-8.4]	5.3 [4.6-6.1]
USA (California) [22]	1980- 1986	<15	0.60 [0.48-0.73] (93)	0.64 [0.48-0.85] (51)	0.55 [0.44-0.74] (42)
USA (Kansas) [23]	1984- 1988	10-88	2.2 (43)		
USA (Vermont) [24]	1980- 1985	<25 25-44 45-64 ≥65 All ages	0.86 (11) 0.97 (9) 2.52 (14) 4.73 (17) 1.6 (51)	2.0	1.3
USA (Virginia) [25]	1967- 1987	0-9 10-19 20-29 30-39 40-49 50-59	1.3 (10) 1.8 (16) 2.2 (18) 1.7 (14) 0.9 (6) 2.2 (11)	1.3 (5) 1.5 (7) 1.4 (6) 1.9 (8) 1.2 (4) 1.6 (4)	1.3 (5) 2.0 (9) 2.9 (12) 1.4 (6) 0.6 (2) 2.8 (7)

		60-69	2.4 (11)	3.6 (8)	1.3 (3)
		≥70	1.4 (6)	1.4 (3)	1.4 (3)
		All ages	1.7 (92)	1.7 (45)	1.7 (47)
USA (Minnesota) [26]	1935-1980	≤17	0.81 (8)		
		18-39	1.34 (13)		
		40-59	2.84 (16)		
		≥60	3.25 (11)		
		All ages	1.68[1.24-2.23] (48)		
USA (Colorado) [27]	1975-1983	All ages			
		Larimer Cy	2.2		
		Weld Cy	1.8		
Aruba [28]	2003-2011	14-77	3.93 (39)		
Curaçao [29]	1987-1999	All ages	2.53 [1.87-3.35] (49)	3.28 [2.21-4.69]	1.86 [1.12-2.990]
Martinique & Guadalupe [30]	2011	All ages	1.76 (14)		
	2012		1.89 (15)		
	2013		1.65 (13)		
	2014		3.45 (27)		
	2015		1.93 (15)		
Puerto Rico [31] (National)	2012-2015	All ages	1.7 [1.3-2.1]		
Puerto Rico [32]	2013	3-82	1.7 (61)		
Honduras [33]	1989-1999	≤14	1.37 (394)		
Brazil [34] (National)	2014	All ages	0.74		
	2015		0.96		
	2016		1.02		
Brazil [35] (Salvador)	2015	12-19	1.5		
		20-39	3.9		
		40-59	7.3		
		≥60	14.7		
		All ages	5.6		
Brazil [36]	1994-2007	All ages	0.3 (149)		
Brazil [37]	1995-2002	1-83	0.4 (95)		
Brazil [38]	1990-1996	<15	0.46 (1678)		
Chile [39]	2013-2019	All ages	2.46 [0.37-2.57] (1779)		
Chile [40]	2001-2012	0-4	2.17		
		5-9	2.23		
		10-19	1.61		

		20-29	1.22		
		30-39	1.57		
		40-49	2.21		
		50-59	2.81		
		60-69	3.60		
		70-79	4.30		
		≥80	3.46		
		All ages	2.10 (4158)		
Columbia [41] (Barranquilla)	2015- 2016	0-19	1.5		
		20-39	6.1		
		40-59	13.4		
		≥60	16.2		
		All ages	7.8		
Argentina, Brazil, Chile&Columbia [42]	1990- 1994	1-4	0.86 [0.78-0.89]		
		5-14	0.52 [0.49-0.53]		
		1-14	0.62 [0.61-0.64] (2296)		
Paraguay ^[43]	1990- 1991	<4	1.7		
		10-14	0.1		
		<15	1.1 (37)		
Uruguay [44] (South)	2018- 2020	≥16	1.7 [1.25-2.25]	2.4	1.1
Latin America /Caribbean [45] i. Entire Region ii. North* iii. South * iv. Mexico v. El Salvador vi. Honduras vii. Brazil viii. Chile * North: includes Cuba, Mexico, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Panama, Columbia and Ecuador; South: includes Peru, Argentina, Brazil, Chile	2000- 2008	<15	i. 0.82 [0.72-0.90]		
			ii. 1.08 [0.96-1.28]		
			iii. 0.57 [0.49-0.67]		
			iv. 1.14		
			v. 3.86		
			vi. 1.72		
			vii. 0.40		
			viii. 1.63		
ASIA					
China [46] (National)	2016- 2019	0-4	0.201 [0.185–0.216] (657)		
		5-9	0.200 [0.184–0.216] (617)		
		10-14	0.235 [0.217–0.252] (701)		

		15-19	0.303 [0.283–0.323] (873)		
		20-24	0.314 [0.296–0.333] (1085)		
		25-29	0.386 [0.368–0.404] (1805)		
		30-34	0.432 [0.413–0.451] (1930)		
		35-39	0.475 [0.454–0.497] (1880)		
		40-44	0.527 [0.505–0.549] (2216)		
		45-49	0.692 [0.669–0.715] (3463)		
		50-54	0.927 [0.899–0.954] (4369)		
		55-59	1.165 [1.128–1.203] (3775)		
		60-64	1.445 [1.404–1.487] (4685)		
		65-69	1.677 [1.627–1.727] (4325)		
		70-74	1.806 [1.741–1.870] (2989)		
		75-79	1.799 [1.720–1.878] (1996)		
		80-84	1.546 [1.454–1.637] (1104)		
		≥85	0.866 [0.780–0.952] (391)		
		All ages	0.698 [0.691-0.705](38861)	0.824 [0.813–0.834]	0.566 [0.557–0.575]
China [47] (HongKong)	2009-2018	<18	0.62 (63)		
China [48]	2013	All ages	0.44 [0.25–0.67]		
	2014		0.58 [0.38–0.82]		
	2015		0.42 [0.28–0.58]		
	2016		0.41 [0.27–0.58]		
	2017	0–18	0.16 [0.08–0.26]		
		19–29	0.20 [0.12–0.30]		
		30–39	0.40 [0.25–0.59]		
40–49		0.45 [0.29–0.66]			
50–59		0.78 [0.51–1.12]			
60–69		1.03 [0.71–1.41]			
	≥70	1.12 [0.76–1.54]			
	All ages	0.51 [0.35–0.60]			
China [49] (Hong Kong)	1993-1998	>15	0.44 (20)		
China [50] (Nanjing, Yancheng, Xuzhou)	2008-2010	0-4	0.38 (15)		
		5-9	0.36 (11)		
		10-14	0.22 (10)		
		15-19	0.50 (29)		
		20-24	0.41 (26)		
		25-29	0.45 (29)		
		30-34	0.53 (33)		
		35-39	0.47 (29)		
		40-44	0.79 (43)		
		45-49	0.60 (31)		
		50-54	0.64 (30)		
		55-59	1.01 (43)		
60-64	0.82 (32)				

		65-69	0.94 (26)		
		70-74	1.23 (27)		
		75-79	1.13 (18)		
		≥80	0.47 (9)		
		All ages	0.59 (441)	0.72 (276)	0.45 (165)
China [51] (Harbin)	1997-1998	0-9	1.15 (10)	1.34 (6)	0.94 (4)
		10-19	0.74 (7)	0.82 (4)	0.65 (3)
		20-29	0.61 (7)	0.50 (3)	0.72 (4)
		30-39	0.40 (4)	0.79 (4)	-- (0)
		40-49	0.75 (4)	0.38 (1)	1.10 (3)
		50-59	0.44 (2)	0.89 (2)	-- (0)
		≥ 60	0.50 (2)	0.49 (1)	0.52 (1)
		All ages	0.74 [0.46-1.13] (36)	0.74 [0.46-1.13] (21)	0.57 [0.32-0.94] (15)
Japan[52] (National)	2014-2016	≤15	0.19 (87)		
Japan [53] (National) <i>Note: see Table 2.3 for description of differences between the MDV and JMDC databases</i>	2019	MDV database	0.9 (112)		
		0-11	3.3(220)		
		12-17	2.9 (259)		
		18-24	3.3 (968)		
		25-44	4.0 (1335)		
		45-64	4.8 (836)		
		65-74	5.4 (1007)		
		≥75	3.8 (4810)	4.3 (2635)	3.4 (2175)
		JMDC database	1.3 (155)		
		0-11	2.9 (197)		
12-17	2.7 (243)				
18-24	4.1 (1238)				
25-44	4.9 (1658)				
45-64	3.4 (1263)				
65-74	3.7 (4754)	5.4 (3382)	2.1 (1372)		
Japan [54] (Tokushima & Kochi Prefectures)	2006-2015	<14		0.09 [0.00-0.51] (1)	0.00 [0.00-0.36] (0)
		15-44		0.59 [0.33-0.95] (16)	0.11 [0.02-0.32] (3)
		45-64		0.47 [0.24-0.85] (11)	0.50 [0.26-0.87] (12)
		≥65		0.78 [0.44-1.28] (15)	0.46 [0.25-0.79] (13)
		All ages	0.42 (71)	0.53 [0.39-0.72] (43)	0.31 [0.21-0.45] (28)
Japan [55] (Tottori)	1988		1.13 (7)		
	1989	All ages	0.97 (6)		
	1990		1.30 (8)		
	1991		1.14 (7)		

	1992		1.14 (7)		
	All years		1.14 (32)		
S Korea [56] (National)	2009	All ages	0.78 [0.70–0.86]	0.95 [0.87–1.04]	0.61 [0.54–0.68]
	2010		1.13 [1.04–1.22]	1.22 [1.12–1.31]	1.04 [0.95–1.13]
	2011		0.96 [0.88–1.05]	0.86 [0.78–0.94]	1.07 [0.98–1.16]
	2012		1.35 [1.25–1.45]	1.64 [1.53–1.75]	1.05 [0.96–1.14]
	2013		1.31 [1.21–1.41]	1.06 [0.94–1.15]	1.56 [1.46–1.67]
	2014		1.69 [1.58–1.80]	1.91 [1.79–2.03]	1.47 [1.37–1.58]
	2015		1.40 [1.30–1.50]	0.74 [0.66–0.81]	2.06 [1.94–2.18]
	2016		2.14 [2.01–2.26]	2.05 [1.93–2.17]	2.22 [2.10–2.36]
	2017		1.89 [1.78–2.02]	2.67 [2.53–2.82]	1.12 [1.02–1.21]
	2018		2.19 [2.06–2.32]	2.96 [2.81–3.11]	1.42 [1.31–1.52]
	2019		1.21 [1.12–1.31]	1.47 [1.37–1.58]	0.95 [0.86–1.03]
S Korea [57] (National)	2016	All ages	1.60 [1.49-1.71]		
	2017		1.52 [1.41-1.62]		
	2018		1.68 [1.57-1.79]		
	2019		1.33 [1.23-1.43]		
	2020		1.10 [1.01-1.19]		
S Korea [58] (National)	<i>Note: The study presented data by age group for every year from 2002 through 2018. Only 2018 is shown here, but the spreadsheet and online dashboard presents rates for all study years.</i>	0-4	1.27		
		5-9	0.82		
		10-14	0.82		
		15-19	1.18		
		20-24	1.52		
		25-29	1.58		
		30-34	1.32		
		35-39	1.45		
		40-44	1.43		
		2018 45-49	2.01		
		50-54	1.78		
		55-59	2.63		
		60-64	2.85		
		65-69	3.66		
		70-74	4.47		
		75-79	5.32		
80-84	4.16				
≥85	1.54				
	All ages	1.68 [1.58-1.78] (1053)			
S Korea [59] (National)	2010	All ages	1.28 [1.19–1.39] (648)	1.47 [1.33–1.63]	1.09 [0.97–1.23]
	2011		1.24 [1.15–1.34] (630)	1.47 [1.33–1.62]	1.41 [1.27–1.56]
	2012		1.26 [1.16–1.36] (640)	1.56 [1.41–1.72]	0.95 [0.84–1.08]
	2013		1.45 [1.35–1.56] (741)	1.70 [1.55–1.87]	1.20 [1.07–1.34]
	2014		1.63 [1.53–1.75] (838)	1.93 [1.77–2.11]	1.34 [1.20–1.49]
	2015		1.65 [1.54–1.76] (849)	1.92 [1.76–2.09]	1.38 [1.24–1.53]
	2016		1.82 [1.71–1.94] (941)	2.14 [1.97–2.32]	1.50 [1.36–1.66]

S Korea [60] (National)	2010-2017	<18	1.25				
S Korea [61] (National)	2008-2009	<20	0.31 [0.14–0.49]	0.87 [0.46–1.27]	0.40 [0.21–0.58]		
		20-34	0.24 [0.06–0.41]				
	2009-2010	35-49	0.40 [0.16–0.64]	1.04 [0.61–1.48]	0.70 [0.34–1.07]		
		50-64	1.11 [0.44–1.78]				
		≥65	2.02 [1.15–2.90]				
		All ages	0.63 [0.37–0.89]				
		<20	0.42 [0.16–0.68]				
		20-34	0.61 [0.26–0.97]				
Taiwan [62] (National)	2000-2013	35-49	0.84 [0.26–1.42]	1.65 (5998)	1.99		
		50-64	1.27 [0.47–2.06]				
		≥65	1.92 [0.98–2.86]				
		All ages	0.87 [0.49–1.26]				
		0-9	0.76			0.88	0.63
		10-19	0.56			0.62	0.49
		20-29	0.92			1.10	0.73
		30-39	1.04			1.35	0.73
		40-49	1.36			1.71	1.01
		50-59	2.12			2.54	1.71
60-69	4.10	4.85	3.39				
70-79	6.35	7.71	4.92				
≥80	6.34	8.51	4.22				
All ages	1.65 (5998)	1.99	29				
Taiwan [64] (National)	1986-1990	≤15	0.66 (72)				
Thailand [65] (National)	2005	All ages	0.48 (225)				
	2006		0.62 (294)				
	2007		0.70 (326)				
	2008		0.74 (346)				
	2009		0.81 (387)				
	2010		0.78 (371)				
	2011		0.73 (356)				
	2012		0.75 (363)				
	2013		0.88 (427)				
	2014		0.80 (386)				
	2015		0.78 (379)				
	2016		No rate (incomplete data)				
	2017		0.93 (453)				
	AUSTRALIA/OCEANIA						
Australia [66] (New South Wales)	2017-2018	All ages	3.9 [3.5-4.4]				

Australia [67] (Victoria)	2004-2009	12 - <16		1.61 [066-2.56] (11)	Not included
Australia [68] (Victoria)	1980-1984	>15	0.9 (110)		
Australia [69] (West Aust)	1980-1985	0-9	1.13 (15)		
		10-19	0.62 (9)		
		20-29	1.61 (23)		
		30-39	1.32 (17)		
		40-49	0.68 (6)		
		50-59	2.07 (15)		
		60-69	2.60 (14)		
		70-79	1.77 (6)		
		80-90	3.30 (4)		
All ages	1.35 (109)	1.49 (61)	1.20 (48)		
New Zealand [70] (National)	1988 – 2010	All ages	2.32 (2056)		
EUROPE					
Balkans [71] (Montenegro, Serbia, Bosnia&Herzegovina)	2009-2013	≥18 crude ≥18 age- adjusted	0.87 [0.78-0.95] 0.86	1.14	0.58
Denmark [72] (National)	1987-2016	0-3	0.78 [0.60–1.01] (60)	1.10 [0.79–1.48]	0.46 [0.27–0.73]
		4-7	0.68 [0.51–0.89] (52)	0.61 [0.39–0.91]	0.75 [0.50–1.09]
		8-11	0.58 [0.42–0.77] (44)	0.67 [0.43–0.97]	0.48 [0.29–0.76]
		12-15	0.72 [0.55–0.94] (56)	0.31 [0.21–0.44]	0.63 [0.41–0.94]
		All ages	0.69 [0.60–0.79] (212)	0.80 [0.66–0.95]	0.58 [0.47–0.72]
Denmark [73] (National)	1987-2016	16-29	1.10 [0.99–1.23] (324)	1.20 [1.03–1.39]	1.00 [0.85–1.18]
		30-39	1.52 [1.36–1.69] (346)	1.80 [1.57–2.07]	1.22 [1.02–1.44]
		40-49	1.30 [1.16–1.46] (304)	1.58 [1.36–1.83]	1.02 [0.84–1.22]
		50-59	2.11 [1.91–2.31] (430)	2.46 [2.17–2.79]	1.75 [1.50–2.02]
		60-69	2.76 [2.51–3.02] (460)	3.37 [2.99–3.80]	2.18 [1.88–2.51]
		70-79	2.80 [2.50–3.13] (319)	3.54 [3.04–4.10]	2.21 [1.86–2.61]
		80-89	2.36 [1.97–2.81] (129)	3.37 [2.60–4.29]	1.80 [1.38–2.30]
		≥90	0.75 [0.30–1.54] (7)	1.26 [0.26–3.69]	0.57 [0.16–1.46]
		All ages	1.77 [1.70–1.84] (2319)	2.09 [1.98–2.21]	1.45 [1.36–1.55]
Denmark [74] (National)	2012-2015	All ages	1.59 [1.42-1.78] (299)		
Denmark [75] (National)	1980-2009	<1	0.09 [0.01–0.31]	0.00 [0.00–0.31]	0.18 [0.02–0.64]
		1-3	0.55 [0.38–0.76]	0.80 [0.53–1.17]	0.28 [0.13–0.53]
		4-9	0.60 [0.46–0.76]	0.65 [0.46–0.89]	0.55 [0.37–0.78]
		10-17	0.94 [0.76–1.14]	0.88 [0.65–1.17]	1.00 [0.75–1.30]
		All ages	0.67 [0.58–0.77]	0.71 [0.59–0.86]	0.62 [0.50–0.76]

Denmark [76] (Ringkøbing County)	1965-1982	All ages	1.14 (51)		
Denmark [77] (Copenhagen County)	1977-1984	20-90	2.0 (34)		
Finland [78] (National)	2002-2012	11-15		Not included	1.11 [0.71-1.74]
Finland [79] (National)	1980-1986	<15	0.38 [0.25-0.56] (27)		
Finland [80] (National)	1981-1986	≤18	0.58 (43)		
		19-49	0.67 (92)		
		≥50	1.35 (112)		
		All ages	0.84 (247)		
Finland [81] (Mainland)	2004-2014	0-4	0.49	0.43	0.59
		5-9	0.44	0.29	0.57
		10-15	0.84	0.60	1.06
		16-49	1.32	1.42	1.18
		50-79	2.72	4.09	2.08
		≥80	1.72	6.08	1.47
		All ages	1.70	2.46	1.44
Finland [82] (Southwest)	2004-2013	≥16	1.82 (69)		
France [83] (National)	2008-2013	All ages	2.42 [2.37-2.47] (9391)		
Germany [84] (National)	2007-2009	All ages	2.6 [2.4-2.7] (889)	3.1 [2.8-3.4] (478)	2.2 [2.0-2.4] (411)
Germany [85] (National)	2003	All ages	1.78 (1466)		
	2004		1.60 (1324)		
	2005		1.89 (1559)		
Greece [86] (Southwest)	1989-2001	1.2-83	0.99(0.81-1.19)(105)	1.2[0.93-1.53](65)	0.76[0.55-1.04](40)
Greece [87] (Northwest)	1996-2005	All ages	1.22 (46)		
Iceland [88] (National) <i>Note: the number of cases reflects what was published. The age specific numbers as shown in Table 1 of the paper, add up to 62 whereas it was noted there were 63 cases in total.</i>	1995-2014	0-9	0.7 (6)		
		10-19	0.5 (4)		
		20-29	0.7 (6)		
		30-39	1.2 (10)		
		40-49	1.0 (8)		
		50-59	1.1 (7)		
		60-69	1.8 (8)		
		70-79	2.2 (7)		
		80-89	3.9 (6)		
		90-99	0 (0)		
		All ages	1.1 (63)		

Italy [89] (National)	1994-1995	All ages	0.92 [0.75-1.09] (109)		
Italy [90] (Ferrara)	2003-2017	0-9	1.05 (4)	1.04 (2)	1.07 (2)
		10-19	0.25 (1)	–	0.53 (1)
		20-29	0.22 (1)	–	0.44 (1)
		30-39	1.18 (9)	1.30 (5)	1.06 (4)
		40-49	1.83 (16)	2.51 (11)	1.15 (5)
		50-59	1.56 (12)	1.62 (6)	1.50 (6)
		60-69	1.68 (12)	1.77 (6)	1.61 (6)
		70-79	2.31 (15)	2.43 (7)	2.21 (8)
		≥80	0.74 (3)	1.48 (2)	0.37 (1)
		All ages	1.38 [1.08-1.74] (73)	1.54 [1.09-2.11] (39)	1.23 [0.85-1.72] (34)
Italy [91] (Ferrara)	1981-2001	0-19	0.53 (3)	0.35 (1)	0.72 (2)
		20-39	0.98 (10)	1.16 (6)	0.80 (4)
		40-59	2.01 (21)	2.81 (14)	1.28 (7)
		60-79	3.24 (28)	4.62 (17)	2.21 (11)
		≥80	4.30 (7)	1.98(1)	5.34 (6)
		All ages	1.91 [1.49-2.43] (69)	2.28 [1.62-3.12] (39)	2.57 [1.06-2.24] (30)
Italy [92] (Ferrara)	1981-1993	GBS			
		0-29	0.89 (7)		
		30-59	1.61 (16)		
		≥60	3.82 (20)		
		All ages	1.87 (43)		
		Variant			
		GBS			
		0-29	0.38 (3)		
		30-59	0.30 (3)		
≥60	0.38 (2)				
All ages	0.35 (8)				
Italy [93] (Emilia-Romagna region) <i>Included GBS (87 cases) and Miller Fisher (7 cases) for incidence rates; excluded GBS variants (11 cases). See study below for overall incidence for each of the GBS types</i>	1992-1993	0-9	0.73 (4)	1.06 (3)	0.37 (1)
		10-19	0.36 (3)	0.23 (1)	0.49 (2)
		20-29	0.94 (11)	1.00 (6)	0.87 (5)
		30-39	0.83 (9)	1.10 (6)	0.56 (3)
		40-49	0.94 (10)	1.51 (8)	0.37 (2)
		50-59	1.30 (14)	2.09 (11)	0.54 (3)
		60-69	2.34 (24)	3.57 (17)	1.27 (7)
		≥70	1.85 (19)	2.50 (10)	1.43 (9)
		All ages	1.20 [0.96-1.46] (94)	1.64 [1.25-2.09] (62)	0.79 [0.54-1.11] (32)
Italy (Emilia Romagna) [94]	Classic GBS	0-9	0.73 (4)		
		10-19	0.24 (2)		
		20-29	0.86 (10)		

	1992-1993	30-39 40-49 50-59 60-69 ≥70 All ages	0.84 (9) 0/66 (7) 1.12 (12) 2.34 (24) 1.85 (19) 1.11 [0.89-1.36] (87)		
	variant GBS 1992-1993	All ages MFS Other variants	0.09 [0.04-0.18] (7) 0.14 [0.07-0.25] (11)		
Italy [95] (Ferrara)	1981-1987	0-9 10-19 20-29 30-39 40-49 50-59 60-69 70-79 All ages	0.86 (1) -- (0) -- (0) 0.58 (1) 3.25 (6) 0.50 (1) 3.98 (6) 0.72 (1) 1.08 (16)	1.39 (10)	0.81 (6)
Italy [96] (LaSpezia)	2003-2015	21-90	3 [0.9-5.37]		
Italy [97]	2010-2011	≥18	1.84 [1.72 – 1.95] (365)		
Italy [98] (Lombardy)	1996	<35 35-54 55-74 ≥75 All ages	0.79 [0.75-1.10] 1.33 [0.92-1.85] 3.22 [2.76-7.58] 4.67 [2.77-7.38] 1.55 [1.30-1.83] (138)	1.67 [1.3-2.11] (74)	1.43 [1.09-1.84] (64)
Italy [99] (Valle d’Aosta)	1995-1996	All ages	1.36 [1.13-1.63] (120)	1.78 [1.4-2.24] (74)	1.11[0.81-1.48] (46)
Italy [100] (Sardinia)	1961-1980	2-75	0.4 (120)	0.41 (62)	0.39 (58)
Netherlands [101] (National)	1996-2008	<10 10-19 20-29 30-39 40-49 50-59 60-69 ≥70 All ages	1.25 [0-2.66] (3) 0.40 [0-1.18] (1) 0.73 [0-1.73] (2) 0.59 [0-1.40] (2) 0.91 [0-1.95] (3) 1.43 [0.03-2.84] (4) 2.15 [0.04-4.25] (4) 1.99 [0.04-3.93] (4) 1.14 [0.67-1.61] (23)		
Netherlands [102] (Southwest region)	1987-1996	All ages	1.18[1.08-1.29] (476)	1.42[1.26-1.59]	0.94 [0.82-1.09]
Norway [103]	2006-7	≥16	2.98	2.56	3.40

(S Rogaland)	2007-8		4.14	4.95	3.32
Serbia [104]	2009-2018	≥18	1.07 [0.83-1.37]	1.4	0.76
Blanco-Ruiz 2024[105]	2018-2021	0-9	0.97 [0.83-1.13] (168)		
		10-19	0.85 [0.73-0.92] (167)		
		20-29	0.93 [0.79-1.70] (179)		
		30-39	1.06 [0.93-1.20] (258)		
		40-49	1.29 [1.16-1.42] (401)		
		50-59	1.93 [1.77-2.10] (542)		
		60-69	2.97 [2.74-3.21] (636)		
		70-79	3.26 [2.99-3.56] (511)		
		80-89	2.82 [2.48-3.18] (260)		
		≥90	0.61 [0.34-1.03] (14)		
		All ages	1.67 (3147)	2.18 [2.08-2.27](2012)	1.18 [1.11-1.25](1135)
Spain [106] (Provincial hospitals)	2003-2016	0-9	2.55 (6)	4.09 (5)	0.88 (1)
		10-19	0.96 (2)	1.85 (2)	0 (0)
		20-29	0.38 (1)	0 (0)	0.77 (1)
		30-39	0.58 (2)	0.55 (1)	0.62 (1)
		40-49	2.47 (8)	4.14 (7)	0.65 (1)
		50-59	1.15 (3)	2.25 (3)	0 (0)
		60-69	3.24 (6)	5.57 (5)	1.05 (1)
		70-79	5.69 (9)	8.67 (6)	3.37 (3)
		80-89	6.26 (6)	11.21 (4)	3.32 (2)
				All ages	2.07 (43)
Spain [107] (National0)	1998-1999	20-29	0.45 (8)	0.55 (5)	0.34 (3)
		30-39	0.64 (10)	1.03 (8)	0.26 (2)
		40-49	1.03 (14)	1.19 (8)	0.87 (6)
		50-59	1.72 (20)	2.26 (13)	1.19 (7)
		60-69	2.42 (25)	3.89 (19)	1.10 (6)
		70-79	2.32 (15)	4.15 (1)	1.05 (4)
		≥80	1.91 (6)	2.86 (3)	1.44 (3)
				All ages	1.25 (98)
Spain [108] (National)	1985-1990	20-29	0.50 (45)		
		30-39	0.61 (48)		
		40-49	0.67 (46)		
		50-59	1.05 (62)		
		60-69	1.66 (86)		
		70-79	1.25 (40)		
		≥80	0.65 (10)		
		All ages	0.85 (337)	1.14 (218)	0.58 (119)
Spain [109] (Cantabria)	1975-1988	0-9	0.59 (6)		
		10-19	1.57 (18)		
		20-29	0.79 (9)		
		30-39	0.64 (6)		
		40-49	1.05 (8)		

		50-59	1.41 (12)		
		60-69	1.23 (8)		
		≥70	0.32 (2)		
		All ages	0.95 (69)	1.18 (43)	0.71 (26)
Sweden [110] (National)	1978-1993	All ages	1.77 (2257)	2.01	1.54
Sweden [111] (Vastra Gotaland)	2017-2020	0-29	0.45 [0.21-0.85]		
		30-59	1.36 [0.9-1.96]		
		60-99	2.65 [1.85-3.67]		
		All ages	1.35 [1.06-1.70]		
Sweden [112] (Stockholm City)	1996	0-9	1.02 (6)	0.99 (3)	2.04 (3)
		1-19	1.21 (6)	1.18 (3)	1.24 (3)
		20-29	1.25 (8)	1.54 (5)	0.94 (3)
		30-39	1.24 (8)	1.81 (6)	0.63 (2)
		40-49	1.27 (8)	1.57 (5)	0.96 (3)
		50-59	0.94 (5)	1.49 (4)	0.38 (1)
		60-69	3.10 (12)	5.99 (11)	0.49 (1)
		70-79	4.48 (16)	3.89 (6)	4.94 (10)
		≥80	1.98 (4)	1.47 (1)	2.24 (3)
		All ages	1.63 [1.28-2.05] (73)	2.00 [1.28-2.05] (44)	1.27 [0.85-1.83] (29)
Sweden [113] (SW Stockholm)	1973-1991	All ages	1.84 (556)	2.15 (281)	1.57 (275)
Sweden [114] (SW Stockholm)	1973-1991	0-9	0.25 (2)	0.49 (2)	-- (0)
		10-19	1.07 (9)	0.70 (3)	1.45 (6)
		20-29	1.35 (12)	1.58 (7)	1.13 (5)
		30-39	1.59 (15)	1.26 (6)	1.93 (9)
		40-49	0.78 (6)	1.03 (4)	0.53 (2)
		50-59	3.38 (19)	3.17 (9)	3.59 (10)
		60-69	2.49 (11)	4.28 (9)	0.86 (2)
		70-79	2.93 (8)	2.65 (3)	3.14 (5)
		≥ 80	1.87 (2)	-- (0)	2.73 (2)
		All ages	1.56 [1.24-1.93] (84)	1.64 [1.19-2.2] (43)	1.46 [1.05-1.99] (41)
UK [115] (National)	1995-1996	All ages	3.0 [1.0-6.0]		
UK [116] (England - London)	2015-2019	All ages	1.71 [1.60-1.81] (1040)	2.03 [1.87-2.19]	1.39 [1.26-1.52]
UK [117] (England-Thames)	1993-1994	All ages	1.2 [0.9-1.4] (79)	1.1 [0.7-1.4] (35)	1.3 [0.9-1.5] (44)
UK [118] (England-Oxfordshire)	1974-1986	0-4	1.3 ()		
		5-14	0.1 (1)		
		15-24	0.7 (9)		
		25-34	1.2 (12)		
		35-44	1.0 (8)		
		45-54	1.5 (10)		
		55-64	2.0 (12)		

		65-74	1.8 (9)		
		≥ 75	1.9 (6)		
		All ages	1.1 [0.8-1.4] (72)	1.0[0.6-1.3] (32)	1.2[0.8-1.6] (40)
UK [119] (England & Wales)	1978	0-4	0.5 (1)		
		5-14	0.6 (3)		
		15-44	1.1 (16)		
		45-64	1.4 (11)		
		65-74	1.9 (6)		
		≥ 75	1.1 (2)		
		All ages	1.1 (39)	1.32 (22)	0.95 (17)
UK [120] (Scotland)	1992- 2000	0-14		0.47 [0.19-0.96] (7)	0.42 [0.15-0.92] (6)
		15-24		0.63 [0.23-1.38] (6)	1.08 [0.52-1.98] (10)
		25-34		0.87 [0.43-1.56] (11)	1.11 [0.61-1.86] (14)
		35-44		1.00 [0.52-1.75] (12)	1.29 [0.72-2.13] (15)
		45-54		1.98 [1.24-3.00] (22)	1.21 [0.64-2.06] (13)
		55-64		3.15 [2.05-4.61] (26)	2.30 [1.39-3.23] (19)
		65-74		3.86 [2.50-5.70] (25)	1.86 [1.02-3.13] (14)
		75-84		2.85 [1.37-5.25] (10)	2.54 [1.39-4.27] (14)
		85-100		2.26 [0.27-8.14] (2)	0.86 [0.10-3.11] (2)
		All ages	1.33 [1.15-1.50] (228)	1.45 [1.19-1.72] (121)	1.22 [0.98-1.46] (107)
UK [121] (Scotland)	1980- 1988	19-60	0.80 [0.46-1.15]		
		61-89	1.62 [0.80-2.43]		
		≥19	1.1 [0.81-1.40] (56)		
European ADVANCE (Accelerated Development of Vaccine benefit-risk Collaboration in Europe) Project^{WSillame 2021}					
All country data combined	2003-2014	0-1	2.86 [2.43-3.37]		
		2-4	2.71 [2.35-3.13]		
		5-14	1.79 [1.63-1.97]		
		15-24	3.10 [2.90-3.32]		
		25-44	6.99 [6.79-7.21]		
		45-64	6.31 [6.11-6.52]		
		≥65	5.34 [5.11-5.58]		
		All ages	5.25 [5.15-5.34]		
Denmark (Aarhus University Hospital and Staten Serum Institute)	2003-2014 for all	0-1	0.4 [0.17-0.82]		
		2-4	1.0 [0.68-1.48]		
		5-14	0.7 [0.51-0.85]		
		15-24	1.2 [0.99-1.41]		
		25-44	2.0 [1.83-2.23]		
		45-64	3.4 [3.12-3.66]		
		≥65	4.6 [4.19-5.00]		
		All ages	2.4 [2.27-2.49] (1711)		
Italy (Agenzia regionale di sanità)		0-1	1.0 [0.47-2.09]		
		2-4	1.7 [1.03-2.67]		
		5-14	0.9 [0.64-1.29]		
		15-24	1.5 [1.14-1.96]		
		25-44	1.7 [1.47-1.94]		

		45-64 ≥65 All ages	3.1 [2.79-3.43] 4.5 [4.14-5.00] 2.6 [2.49-2.80] (1085)		
Italy (Val Padana)		0-1 2-4 5-14 15-24 25-44 45-64 ≥65 All ages	0.0 0.0 1.1 [0.42-2.97] 1.2 [0.45-3.17] 1.8 [1.14-2.81] 2.8 [1.99-4.01] 5.7 [4.32-7.47] 2.8 [2.30-3.35] (109)		
Italy (Pedianet)		0-1 2-4 5-14 All 0-14	-- (0 cases) 1.9 [0.48-7.73] -- (0 cases) 0.5 [0.13-2.04] (24)		
Spain (Base de Datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria)		0-1 2-4 5-14 15-24 25-44 45-64 ≥65 All ages	0.4 [0.14-1.34] 0.5 [0.17-1.20] 0.5 [0.28-0.82] 0.5 [0.33-0.73] 1.0 [0.77-1.17] 1.6 [1.36-1.97] 1.8 [1.43-2.24] 1.1 [0.97-1.21] (321)		
UK (Royal College of General Practitioners Research and Surveillance Centre)		0-1 2-4 5-14 15-24 25-44 45-64 ≥65 All ages	0.8 [0.25-2.45] 1.2 [0.55-2.73] 0.5 [0.24-0.97] 1.0 [0.59-1.56] 1.4 [1.08-1.83] 2.2 [1.74-2.67] 3.4 [2.75-4.21] 1.8 [1.57-2.00] (257)		
UK (The Health Improvement Network)		0-1 2-4 5-14 15-24 25-44 45-64 ≥65 All ages	0.4 [0.19-0.93] 1.0 [0/67-1.60] 0.6 [0.48-0.87] 1.0 [0.76-1.25] 1.3 [1.15-1.50] 2.3 [2.12-2.60] 3.2 [2.86-3.57] 1.8 [1.67-1.89] (1021)		
European ACCESS Project [122]					
Italy, Spain,UK	2017–2020	All ages GP only	1.25 [0.27–2.23]		
Netherlands	2014–2020	All ages	2.09 [0.46–3.74]		

		INPATIENT only			
Italy	2017 – 2020	All ages INPATIENT & EMR	3.39 [2.16–4.63]		
Spain, Netherlands	2017–2020	All ages GP & IN- OUTPATIENT	3.21 [1.00–4.42]		
Denmark, France	2010–2013 (Denmark) + 2017–2020 (France)	All ages IN- OUTPATIENT	3.33 [2.48–4.17]		
MIDDLE EAST					
Iran [123] (National)	2008-2013	<15	1.72 (1884)		
Iran [124] (National)	2002 2003 2004	5-14	0.68 (121) 0.76 (135) 0.65 (114)		
Iran [125] (Southwest)	2006-2015	<5 5-9 10-14 All ages	2.21 (96) 1.34 (51) 0.92 (37) 1.51[1.29-1.73](184)	1.59 (99)	1.43 (85)
Iran [126] (N Guilan Province)	2009-2018	All ages	0.69		
Iran [127] (Northwest)	2001 2002 2003 2004 2005 2006 All years	0-15	1.49 ([0.8-2.4] 1.95 [1.2-2.9] 3.44 [2.4-4.7] 2.14 [1.3-3.2] 2.04 [1.2-3.1] 2.57 [1.7-3.7] 2.27 [1.9-2.6] (143)		
Iran [128] (Northwest)	2003	< 15 ≥ 15 All ages	2.28 2.06 2.11 (76)	2.5 (45)	1.73 (31)
Iraq [129] (National)	1997-2011	<15	1.33 [0.97-1.68]		
Kuwait [130] (National)	1992-1997	0-4 0-12	1.15 (10) 0.95 (19)		

Table 2.2 Methodology used for incidence studies in Table 2.1 (listed in same order as in Table 2.1)

1 st Author and Locale	Methodology
AFRICA	
Radhakrishnan 1987[6]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Benghazi (Libya) residents; screening done in polyclinics, university hospitals, rehabilitation centers, medical board for patients seeking disability benefits and medical care abroad and the sole neurology center in the region.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not used</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see Table 3.3)</p> <p>Validation: not described</p> <p>Note: 13 GBS cases identified; all with elevated CSF protein and normal CSF WBC count; 4 needed ventilatory support; 2 deaths. EMG/NCS not noted.</p>
Howlett 1996[7]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Neurologic admissions to Kilimanjaro Christian Medical Center in N Tanzania (only regional hospital with neurological and rehabilitation services).</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital Register / ICD 9 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (see Table 3.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review</p> <p>Note: 89 cases diagnosed as GBS of which 59 met the study CD (66.3%); of the 59 that met the CD, 11 were HIV seropositive. Mean (range) in days from onset to peak illness: 6.0 (1-28); weakness involving legs in 93.2% and arms in 49.2%; Reflexes reduced or absent in 94.9% legs and 54.2% arms; most cases had CSF tested (specific number not given); mean CSF protein 204.1 mg/100ml (range 10-1200; lab normal range of 15-50); CSF WBC mean 3.7/mm. No mention of electrophysiologic tests.</p>
AMERICAS	
Nasreen 2022 [8]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalizations and Emergency room visits for GBS in Canadian province of Ontario.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Canadian Institute for Health Information Discharge Abstract Database & National Ambulatory Care reporting System / ICD-10-CA G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD-10 code for GBS</p> <p>Validation: not validated</p>

<p>Auger 2018[9]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Population-based cohort of women in Quebec (Canada) who delivered a baby between 1989 and 2013. Excluded any with prior history of GBS. Followed to end of 2014 to identify hospitalization for GBS. Database/Codes: Quebec hospital discharge database / ICD-9 code 357.0 and ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: ICD 9/10 code. Validation: Determined % of cohort who were intubated or admitted to ICU (28.1% of study cohort; expected 20-30% for GBS). Note: <i>Besides calculating overall incidence of GBS, key focus was to examine impact of autoimmune comorbidities on incidence of GBS in parous women. See Risk Factor Appendix 3, Table 3.1 Pregnancy and Comorbidity</i></p>
<p>Deceuninck 2008[10]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Quebec(Canada), admitted to acute care hospital Database/Codes: Med-Echo registry / ICD-9 code 357.0 Case Definition: Hughes and Cornblath classification plus Brighton GBS working group criteria as of Sept 2007. Confirmed case: typical clinical features, electrophysiologic findings consistent with GBS; CSF elevated protein and WBC count $<50/\text{mm}^3$; no alternative diagnosis. Probable case: typical clinical features and no alternative diagnosis; Possible case: incomplete but compatible clinical presentation and no alternative diagnosis, Validation: Medical record review by pediatric neurologist. Note: <i>CSF obtained in 32 of 33 cases – cytoalbuminic dissociation in 20 (63%); EMG for 25/33 – 22 (88%) had pattern consistent with GBS.</i></p>
<p>Hauck 2008[11]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Alberta (Canada) Database/Codes: Alberta Ministry of Health administrative database / ICD-9 code 357.0; ICD-10 code G61.0. Case Definition: ICD codes Validation: not done</p>
<p>McLean 1994[12]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Acute care hospital admissions in Quebec and Ontario (Canada) Database/Codes: Hospital Medical Records Institute (Ontario) and Med-Echo (Quebec) / GBS: ICD-9 code 357.0 (acute polyinflammatory polyneuropathy); Not GBS(possible false negative cases): 357.8 (inflammatory and toxic polyneuropathy), 357.9 (inflammatory and toxic polyneuropathy, unspecified) , 375.0 (dacryoadenitis – selected to assess false negative rate – because 357 code could be transcribed in error to 375)</p>

	<p>Case Definition: Definite case - progressive weakness of legs and arms AND areflexia or marked hyporeflexia in legs and arms AND deficit relatively symmetric AND [CSF protein elevated during or after 1st week or illness OR EMG or other electrophysiologic test consistent with demyelinating polyneuropathy] AND CSF mononuclear cells <10/ml AND absence of fever at onset of neurologic symptoms AND no alternative cause; Probable case – clinical findings as in definite case except progressive weakness of arms not needed AND CSF and EMG results normal or not done; Possible case: clinical findings compatible with GBS except DTRs not recorded</p> <p>Validation: Chart review of a sample of cases by two neurologists.</p> <p>Code Validity: For code 357.0 false positive rate of 26.2% for Ontario cases and 21% for Quebec cases); Of 141 charts coded as 357.8 (43), 357.9 (81) or 375.0 (17), none were found to represent GBS (0% false-negatives)</p>
<p>Moll 2023[13]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Multiple USA health care settings including inpatient facilities, emergency departments, other outpatient facilities, individual healthcare providers.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Multiple US administrative claims databases (see notes for list and description of each) / ICD-10-CM G61.0 (GBS).</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD-10 code</p> <p>Validation: not done.</p> <p>Note: <i>Incidence data presented separately for each different administrative claims database, including:</i></p> <p>For individuals aged <65 years including children:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BHI: <i>Blue Health intelligence included a study cohort of all enrollees who received a biologic product, were pregnant, or were born after Oct 1, 2015. Total cohort of 34 million individuals and about 350,000 pregnancy outcomes annually</i> • CVS Health: <i>CVS Health Clinical Trial Services captures demographic and medical and drug claims data for individuals enrolled from January 2018 forward in Aetna commercial and Medicare Advantage health plans; contains > 37 million people</i> • Health Core: <i>Health Core Integrated Research Database includes medical and pharmacy claims and laboratory results for 76 million individuals; includes physician office, outpatient and ER visits, hospital stays, outpatient surgeries, ambulance transportation, skilled nursing facility episodes and durable medical equipment; over 23 million members in 2020</i> • Market Scan: <i>IBM Market Scan Commercial Database has >25 million annual enrollees for active employees and early retirees and dependents ensured by employer-sponsored plans. Captures individual-level clinical utilization,</i>

	<p><i>expenditures and enrollment across inpatient, outpatient and prescription drugs from a selection of large employers, health plans, government and public organizations.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optum: includes enrollment, prescription drug and pre-adjudicated hospital and physician health insurance claims <p>For individuals aged ≥65 years:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medicare: Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) contains enrollment, demographic and claims information for all individuals enrolled in parts A/B (since 1991), Part C (since 2012) and Part D (since 2006). About 34 million current beneficiaries annually on average.
Leung 2020[14]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: USA insured healthcare visits – inpatient and outpatient. Database/Codes: Truven Health MarketScan Commercial Claims & Encounters Database (employer-sponsored insurance healthcare claims from all US states / ICD-9-CM code 357.0; ICD-10-CM code G61.0 Case Definition: one of the ICD codes and at least 1 inpatient claim for: LP or EMG or NCS within 45 days of GBS onset date. Validation: no validation</p>
Myers 2019[15]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: USA hospital cases involving pregnant women that occurred during pregnancy or up to 42 days post partum. Database/Codes: Vaccine safety administrative health care data from seven integrated health care systems (not specified) / ICD-9 357.0 Case Definition: Brighton Collaboration [1] : Included Levels 1, 2 and 3 of diagnostic certainty for incidence calculations Validation: medical records reviewed by trained data abstractors; data reviewed by two trained personnel independently to determining Brighton LOC. Note: only identified 2 confirmed cases of GBS during pregnancy – none post-partum; both LOC 2. Code Validity: PPV only 10% - however two main reasons – Of 35 potential cases: 23 had a history of GBS rather than incident case; 8 were patients with Group B Streptococcal infection but were miscoded as GBS; 1 other was miscoded (not explained); 1 found not to be GBS at follow-up.</p>
Shui 2012[16]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: USA hospital inpatient or emergency department (ED) or outpatient (OPD) care. Database/Codes: Vaccine safety datalink (VSD) including data from seven managed care organizations (Seattle, Boston, Minneapolis-St Paul, Denver, Oakland, Portland, Pasadena) / ICD-9 357.0 Case Definition: Brighton Collaboration [1]</p>

	<p>Validation: medical record review for a convenience sample of 109 visits with GBS code that occurred within 42 days after seasonal influenza vaccine. Data abstracted based on Brighton case definition and final review/adjudication done by neurologist with GBS expertise.</p> <p>Note: Code Validity: <i>PPV of the ICD-9 code determined based on validation results: Level of certainty (LOC) 1 for 6 cases, 2 for 16 cases, 3 for 6 cases. An additional 9 that were LOC4 (insufficient information to reach LOC 1, 2 or 3) were classified as probable cases. PPV for confirmed or probable cases varied by the source setting for cases: Inpatient or ED: 55%; OPD 20%. PPV for confirmed cases only: ED/inpatient 47%; all 3 settings 28%.</i></p>
Lee 2012[17]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Tennessee State hospital inpatients. Used Social Security Numbers to create an optimized database which excluded duplicates, non-Tennessee residents and any GBS cases diagnosed in a prior year.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Tennessee hospital discharge databases / ICD-9 code 357.0 with no evidence of a prior GBS diagnosis</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD-9 code</p> <p>Validation: For Oct 1, 2009 through Mar 31, 2010 used 36 acute GBS cases found by CDC active surveillance program as the gold standard for comparison to the 29 cases in the optimized database to calculate</p> <p>Code Validity: sensitivity (81%) and PPV (45%).</p>
Klein 2010[18]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: New onset GBS seen in outpatient, emergency department or admitted to hospital in North California, USA</p> <p>Database/Codes: North California Kaiser Permanente / ICD-9 code 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: Clearly stated diagnosis by a neurologist.</p> <p>Validation: medical record review by trained medical record analysts. Verified 78.1% of 121 identified cases.</p>
Nelson 2009[19]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Visits to a USA military treatment facility coded as GBS.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Defense Medical Surveillance System (DMSS) that has all medical encounters at military treatment facilities for all active duty US military, 1998 to 2009 (when study published) / ICD9-CM code 357.0.</p> <p>Case Definition: Code plus ≥ 2 separate GBS-associated medical encounters within 1 year of initial diagnosis.</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
Alskehlee 2008[20]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p>

	<p>Case Sources: Hospital admissions from a database covering about 1000 US hospitals representing a 20% stratified sample of US community hospitals.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Nationwide Inpatient Sample (NIS) / ICD-9-CM code 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD-9 code</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
ChurchPotter 2003[21]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: GBS cases reported to Michigan Department of Community Health (USA)</p> <p>Database/Codes: Michigan reportable disease database and GBS registry / not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: not provided</p> <p>Validation: not described</p>
Rantala 1994[22]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Children admitted to Los Angeles and Orange counties with diagnosis of any neuropathy (USA)</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases</p> <p>Case Definition: Criteria proposed by GBS Study Group: required for diagnosis – progressive motor weakness of >1 limb; areflexia or marked hyporeflexia; CSF monocytes ≤ 50 or 2 PMNs; supportive of diagnosis: progression for days to a few weeks, relative symmetry, mild sensory signs or symptoms, cranial nerve involvement, onset of recovery 2-4 weeks after halt of progression, autonomic dysfunction, initial absence of fever, elevated CSF protein after 1 week of symptoms, abnormal electrodiagnostics. Excluded cases with history or evidence of polio, diphtheria, botulism, hexacarbon abuse, porphyria, lead intoxication, toxic neuropathy, exposure to organophosphates or tick paralysis.</p> <p>Validation: Case histories reviewed by child neurologist.</p>
Hoppock 1994[23]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospital cases from Sedgwick County, Kansas (USA)</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge data / ICD-9 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: Subacute progressive weakness of at least the lower extremities and decreased deep tendon reflexes.</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review. 43 of 45 possible cases met the case definition. Two that didn't had exaggerated rather than decreased reflexes</p>
Koobatian 1991[24]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalized patients in Virginia (USA).</p> <p>Database/Codes: Uniform Hospital Discharge Data Set for discharges from all 17 Virginia hospitals / ICD-9 code 357.0</p>

	<p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1981 (see Table 3.3)</p> <p>Validation: Used written discharge summaries from hospital medical charts for each possible case. Of 72 identified cases, 45 (63%) confirmed, 6 (8%) probable, 14 (19%) noncases – of which 7 were clearly miscoded, and 7 (10%) indeterminate.</p>
Riggs 1989[25]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Admissions to West Virginia University Health Sciences Center (USA)</p> <p>Database/Codes: Medical Discharge records / acute neuropathies – no codes provided</p> <p>Case Definition: Asbury 1981 – see Table 3.3</p> <p>Validation: not provided</p>
Beghi 1985[26]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Olmsted County, Minnesota (USA) residents seen at Mayo Clinic for polyradiculitis, peripheral neuritis or neuronitis.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Mayo Clinic record linkage system / not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review by clinical neurologist with confirmation of diagnosis by two consultant neurologists.</p> <p>Note: CSF obtained for 42 of 48 cases; elevated CSF protein in 38/42; CSF leukocyte count ≤ 10 in 40/42; 2 had counts >10 but not known if <50; 26/30 cases with EMG had findings consistent with GBS.</p>
Kaplan 1985[27]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Larimer and Weld Counties, Colorado (USA); Hospital admission for GBS or on the basis of interviews with all practicing neurologists in the counties.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital medical records / ICD-8 354 (polyneuritis and polyradiculitis) or ICD-9 code 357.0 (acute infectious polyneuritis)</p> <p>Case Definition: Progressive muscle weakness and loss of DTRs, diagnosed by a neurologist as GBS.</p> <p>Validation: Chart review to see if case definition met.</p>
Suryapranata 2016[28]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Aruba</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge database / ICD-9 code 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (see Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review</p>

Van Kiningsveld 2001[29]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in the only neurologic ward in Curacao Database/Codes: Hospital discharge database / ICD-9 code 357.0 Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (See table 2.3) Validation: Medical chart review by senior neurologist</p>
[1]Balavoine 2017[30]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Martinique and Guadalupe Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases / not provided Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (See table 2.3) Validation: not described <i>Note: Detailed chart review done for 13 cases of GBS that were considered to be chikungunya related. These had to meet the case definition.</i></p>
Dirlikov 2017[31]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalized cases of suspected GBS at 9 reference hospitals in Puerto Rico (USA Territory in Caribbean). Database/Codes: Hospital database / not described Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1] Validation: not described</p>
Salinas 2017[32]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Cases identified by the Puerto Rico Health Study which includes island-wide medical insurance claims for medical encounters for about 90% of Puerto Rican residents (USA Territory in Caribbean). Database/Codes: Health insurance claims data / ICD-9 code 357.0 and ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: Brighton case definition[1] clinical criteria as required for LOC3 Validation: Of 149 cases found in nine selected referral hospitals, Brighton CD LOC distribution: 67 (45%) met the Brighton case definition (17 LOC1, 34 LOC2, 16 LOC3). This proportion was applied to the crude GBS incidence calculated from all claims data with a GBS code. A total of 25 cases (17%) were LOC4 and 57 cases (38%) were LOC5, all of which were excluded from the incidence calculation.</p>
Molinero 2003[33]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study Case Sources: hospitalised AFP cases at Hospital Escuela Materno-Infantil in Tegucigalpa, Honduras. Database/Codes: Poliomyelitis Eradication Surveillance System (PESS) database / not provided</p>

	<p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (See table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: All identified cases examined and diagnosed by one of the authors.</p> <p>Note: Total of 394 GBS cases; CSF exam done for 317 (80%) – CSF protein elevated in 164 (52%)</p>
Wachira 2021[34]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised patients in Brazil.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital Admissions Information System / ICD-10 G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: Not provided</p> <p>Validation: Not done</p>
Styczynski 2018[35]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Salvador metropolitan area of Brazil – cases reported by physicians and hospitals.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Center for Information and Epidemiologic Surveillance (CIEVS) database</p> <p>Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1] Confirmed GBS if LOC 1, 2 or 3.</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review</p> <p>Note: found 50 GBS cases;</p> <p>Electrophysiology testing / CSF sampling and results: 44 (88%) had cytoalbuminologic dissociation; time from onset of symptoms to maximal severity mean of 6 days (range 4-9 days); 9(18%) had electrophysiologic testing (5 AMAN; 4 AIDP).</p>
Dourado 2012[36]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Patient population from Brazil state of Rio Grande do Norte. Not clearly described but seem to be patients followed by the authors.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not used</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1981 and 1990 (See table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: All cases examined by same neurologist (first author of study) who also performed nerve conduction studies on all.</p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: of 149 GBS cases, 122 (81.9%) had AIDP and 27 (18.1%) axonal variants (22 AMAN, 5 AMSAN).</p>
Guimaraes Rocha 2004[37]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases at single hospital in Sao Paulo, Brazil.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital Discharges</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (See table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Neurological evaluation</p> <p>Electrophysiology testing / CSF sampling and results: all suspect cases had CSF examination and electrodiagnostic studies.</p>

<p>Dias-Tosta 2002[38]</p>	<p>Study type: AFP (acute flaccid paralysis) surveillance study Case Sources: GBS cases identified as part of Brazilian national AFP surveillance. Database/Codes: Fundacao nacional de Saude of Brazilian Ministry of Health database / not provided Case Definition: presence of roughly symmetrical motor weakness over a period ranging from days to 4 weeks plus decrease or disappearance of DTRs. Validation: not described</p>
<p>Idiaquez 2025[39]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Patients hospitalised for GBS for ≥ 7 days in government-funded and private tertiary hospitals in Chile. Database/Codes: Chilean hospital discharge database (Departamento de Estadisticas e Informacion de Salud – DEIS) / ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: ICD-10 code in principal diagnosis field plus hospital stay for ≥ 7 days Validation: not done</p>
<p>Rivera-Lillo 2016[40]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospital discharges and emergency visits for all of Chile. Database/Codes: Department of Statistics and Health Information (DEIS) of Chilean Ministry of Health database / ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done</p>
<p>Salinas 2017[41]</p>	<p>Study type: Surveillance study Case Sources: all clinical encounters in Barranquilla, Columbia. Database/Codes: Secretaria de Salud de Barranquilla / ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1] LOCs 1-3 Validation: Medical chart review, applying Brighton case definition Brighton CD LOC distribution: Study done during a local Zika virus outbreak. Of 74 cases with GBS code living in Barranquilla, 47 included for incidence determination (2 LOC1, 11 LOC2, 34 LOC3; excluded 9 LOC4 and 18 LOC5). 40 of 47 included in a case control study to examine association with Zika virus – 21 (53%) of cases with GBS had lab evidence of a recent Zika virus or flavivirus infection.</p>
<p>Silveira 1997[42]</p>	<p>Study type: Surveillance study</p>

	<p>Case Sources: GBS cases identified as part of the South American AFP surveillance system. Countries included Argentina, Brazil, Chile and Columbia.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Poliomyelitis Eradication Surveillance System (PESS) database / not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 and 1990 (See table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: not described</p> <p>Note: AFP noted to be a reportable condition in Latin America for <15 yr olds. Most cases examined by a neurologist and have electrodiagnostic tests and CSF analysis.</p>
<p>Hart 1994[43]</p>	<p>Study type: AFP (acute flaccid paralysis) surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: National Paraguay AFP surveillance program</p> <p>Database/Codes: Paraguayan Ministry of Health / not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 and 1990 (see Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Independent medical chart review by two neurologists</p> <p>Electrophysiology testing / CSF sampling and results: of 37 identified cases, nerve conduction testing done in 31 and was abnormal in 90%; 14 had CSF examination with elevated protein in 9.</p>
<p>Chiesa 2021[44]</p>	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Montevideo and Canelones departments or Uruguay (population 1,412,751 aged >16 years). Cases ascertained via multiple sources of information from specialties involved in GBS diagnosis (neurology, neurophysiology, internal, emergency and intensive care medicine. Reached via monthly phone surveys done through communication networks of Uruguayan Society of Neurology.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Not used</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (see table 3.2) and applied the Brighton criteria to determine level of diagnostic certainty. Miller Fisher Syndrome defined as presence of ataxia, ophthalmoplegia and areflexia in the absence of relevant limb weakness or other signs suggesting CNS involvement.</p> <p>Validation: Study team neurologists followed up and examined all reported patients at the reporting clinical center.</p> <p>Brighton CD LOC distribution: 51 GBS cases included: 21 (41%) LOC1, 19 (37%) LOC2, 3 (6%) LOC3, 5 (10%) Miller Fisher – LOC 1 or 2, 3 (6%) other diagnosis: CIDP, critical illness neuropathy, multiple mononeuropathy;</p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: electrophysiologic testing done in 34 of whom 23 (68%) had AIDP, 5 (15%) had AMAN/AMSAN and 6 (17%) were normal.</p> <p>Electrophysiology testing / CSF sampling and results: CSF examination done in 40 cases with cytoalbuminologic dissociation in</p>

	77%; Ganglioside antibodies found in 18 (60%) of 30 tested. Incidence based on classical GBS (42 cases = 82% of all cases) or Miller Fisher (found in 5 = 10% of all cases). Did not include 3 bilateral facial nerve palsies or 1 case of GBS-Miller Fisher overlap. Electrophysiologic test done for 147 cases of whom 100 (68%) had AMAN pattern.
Landaverde 2010[45]	<p>Study type: AFP (acute flaccid paralysis) surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: Cases of GBS found via the AFP surveillance program for children <15 years old in Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Peru, Bahamas, Guyana, Jamaica, St Vincent and the Grenadines, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Polio Eradication Surveillance System (PESS) that includes Latin America and Caribbean country data since 1980's / Code not described.</p> <p>Case Definition: PAHO Polio Eradication Field Guide criteria: acute, symmetrical and distal flaccid paralysis with absence of DTRs; time from onset to maximal severity ranging from hours to 10 days; low involvement of the high cranial nerves; autonomic dysfunction; CSF elevated protein with relatively few WBCs; abnormal nerve conduction velocity at 3 weeks plus demyelination; symmetrical atrophy of peroneal muscle that tends to resolve within 60 days; cramps, tingling and reduced sensation on palms and soles.</p> <p>Validation: Neurologist case review; if diagnosis not established reviewed by classification committee to eliminate possibility of polio and define final diagnosis.</p>
ASIA	
Zheng 2022[46]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in China.</p> <p>Database/Codes: National Hospital Quality Monitoring System (has inpatient medical records from all public tertiary hospitals in China) / ICD-10 G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS (year not specified; see table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review</p>
Chiu 2022[47]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospital admission to any of 11 pediatric units of public hospitals in Hong Kong.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital databases / ICD-10 code G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1]</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review by a pediatric neurologist</p> <p>Brighton CD LOC distribution:</p>

	of 63 GBS cases, 59 met the Brighton case definition: 40 LOC1, 17 LOC2, 2 LOC3. 8 cases were classic Miller Fisher, and 8 Miller Fisher/GBS overlap
Xu 2024[48]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospital cases and other health encounters included in the insurance database for Urban China.</p> <p>Database/Codes: National Urban Medical Insurance database (covers >95% of entire urban Chinese population) / ICD-10 G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: not described</p> <p>Validation: Independent review of medical charts by two. Neurologists and any disagreement resolved by including another senior neurologist</p>
Hui 2005[49]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases - single hospital in Hong Kong</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital record database / ICD-9 code 357, 356.4, 356.8, 356.9</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review</p> <p>Note: 20 cases; all with EMG – 19 AIDP pattern, one Miller Fisher variant; Weeks from onset to maximum severity: 0-1 for 9, 1-2 for 7 and 2-3 for 4.</p>
Chen 2014[50]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: hospitalised cases in the Jiangsu province cities of Nanjing, Yancheng and Xuzhou</p> <p>Database/Codes: Searched hospital records for: Guillain-Barre syndrome, GBS, acute inflammatory demyelinating polyradiculopathy, AIDP, chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyradiculopathy, CIDP, acute motor-axonal neuropathy, AMAN, acute motor-sensory axonal neuropathy, AMSAN, Miller-Fisher syndrome and MFS.</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 and 1990 (see Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Neurologist review of medical records.</p>
Cheng 2002[51]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Harbin (China) city hospitals and clinics with notification of cases by physicians</p> <p>Database/Codes: not used</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Neurologists follow up all notifications, examining each patient within two days of notification</p>
Fujii 2023[52]	Study type: Retrospective cohort study

	<p>Case Sources: Questionnaire sent to all child neurologists in Japan to find cases of GBS, Miller Fisher Syndrome (MFS) and Bickerstaff’s brainstem encephalitis (BBE). Only 50.4% of neurologists responded so incidence could be underestimated.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not used</p> <p>Case Definition: GBS-NINCDS 1978 and 1990 (see Table 2.3); MFS: clinical triad of ophthalmoplegia, ataxia and areflexia, with relatively acute onset without muscle weakness; Atypical MFS: two of three clinical triad features plus anti-GQ1b IgG antibodies in serum; BBE: acute onset of disturbance in consciousness, external ophthalmoplegia and ataxia; included cases with 2 of 3 findings if anti-GQ1b antibodies in serum</p> <p>Validation: based on child neurologist diagnosis and met the NINCDS criteria</p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: GBS phenotypes based on electrophysiologic testing: 31 (35.6%) AIDP; 18 (20.7%) AMAN; 9 (10.3%) AMSAN; 29 (33%) unclassified; anti-ganglioside IgG antibodies found in 46 of 69 tested (66.7%). Of 69 GBS cases tested, 94.4% of 18 AMAN; 51.7% of 29 AIDP; 88.9% of 9 AMSAN; 50% of 12 unclassified. Among 9 MFS cases, 88.9% had antibodies detected; All four tested cases of BBE had IgG anti-ganglioside antibodies.</p>
<p>Sobue 2021[53]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised and outpatient cases in Japan.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Japan Medical Data Center (JMDC) and Medical Data Vision Co. Ltd (MDV) / ICD-10 code G61.0</p> <p>Rates calculated separately for each database:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JMDC has inpatient and outpatient claims data for 7.3 million persons, mainly workers aged <65 years employed by mid- to large-sized companies and their dependents, and excludes those aged ≥75 years. • MDV has health insurance claims for inpatients and outpatients primarily from Diagnosis Procedure Combination (DPC) hospitals. The proportion of hospitals providing increased from 8% in 2015 to 20% in 2019. <p>Case Definition: ICD code</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
<p>Matsui 2018[54]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Tokushima and Kochi Prefectures, Japan</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge records / not specified</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (see Table 2.3); Miller Fisher syndrome: presence of clinical triad (ophthalmoplegia, ataxia, areflexia) without major limb weakness or signs suggesting CNS involvement. Excluded Bickerstaff encephalitis.</p> <p>Validation: Verification by two neurologists managing the cases in hospital.</p>

	Note: identified 71 GBS and 37 Miller Fisher cases													
Kusumi 1995[55]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Tottori, Japan Database/Codes: Hospital records / not specified Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (See Table 2.3) Validation: Medical record review</p>													
Jeong 2024[56]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in South Korea Database/Codes: National Health Insurance Service (NHIS) / ICD-10 G61.0 Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done</p>													
Choi 2023[57]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in South Korea Database/Codes: Health Insurance Review and Assessment Service database / ICD-10 codes G61.0 Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done</p>													
Yi 2022[58]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in South Korea Database/Codes: National Health Insurance Service (NHIS) / ICD-10 codes for GBS (G61.0), serum neuropathy (G61.1), other inflammatory polyneuropathies (G61.8) and inflammatory polyneuropathy, unspecified (G61.9). Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see Table 2.3) / Operational CD based on the validation results: hospitalised cases with ICD-10 code G61.0 treated in a specific department (neurology, pediatrics or rehabilitation medicine). Validation: evaluated accuracy of diagnostic codes, nerve conduction studies, hospitalization and treatment departments. Case ascertainment validation: Of 146 patients identified by codes selected for study, 44 identified as GBS; 102 had other diseases: 47 cervical disc disorder with myelopathy; 14 CIDP, 10 G61.9; 10 malingering; 9 diplopia; 4 multifocal motor neuropathy (G61.82), 4 hereditary motor and sensory neuropathy (G60.0); 4 polyneuropathy unspecified (G62.9). Assessed accuracy of several operational definitions for GBS – Table copied from the article supplementary table 1:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Operational definition</th> <th>Sensitivity</th> <th>Specificity</th> <th>PPV</th> <th>NPV</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>ICD-10 code for GBS (G61.0) only</td> <td>100%</td> <td>22%</td> <td>35%</td> <td>100%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Operational definition	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	ICD-10 code for GBS (G61.0) only	100%	22%	35%	100%
Operational definition	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV										
ICD-10 code for GBS (G61.0) only	100%	22%	35%	100%										

	ICD-10 GBS code + Nerve conduction study	77%	61%	46%	86%
	ICD-10 GBS code + hospitalisation	100%	86%	75%	100%
	ICD-10 GBS code + [neurology, pediatrics or rehabilitation medicine] department	100%	45%	44%	100%
	ICD-10 GBS code + specific department (as above) + hospitalisation	100%	92%	85%	100%
Kim 2021[59]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in South Korea Database/Codes: National Health Insurance Service (NHIS) / ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: Typical GBS - ICD code G61.0. Excluded possible atypical forms of GBS: ICD-10 codes: G61.8 (other inflammatory polyneuropathies); G61.9 (inflammatory neuropathy, unspecified); G62.8 (other specified polyneuropathies); G62.9 (polyneuropathy, unspecified) Validation: not done</p>				
Yoon 2021[60]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in South Korea Database/Codes: Korean National Health Insurance (NHI) database (public system covering >98% of the population) / ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done</p>				
Kim 2015[61]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in a nationally representative sample of S. Korean hospitals. Database/Codes: Health Insurance Review & Services (HIRA) / ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1] Validation: Medical record review by trained physicians and then reviewed by a research committee of neurologists, pediatric neurologists and epidemiologists to assign Brighton level of diagnostic certainty. Brighton CD LOC distribution: Of 695 incident cases, 370 (53.2%) met Level 1, 2 or 3 of the Brighton case definition.</p>				
Liou 2016[62]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Taiwan Database/Codes: National Health Insurance research Database (NHIRD) – single payer compulsory health insurance program covering >99.5% of Taiwanese population / ICD-9 code 357.0</p>				

	<p>Case Definition: ICD code of 357.0; excluded any with ICD-9 code for CIDP (357.81); critical illness polyneuropathy (357.82); polyneuropathy because of other diseases (e.g. porphyria and diphtheria; 357.4); acute poliomyelitis (045, 045.1); myasthenia gravis, other myasthenic syndrome (358.0, 358.01, 358.1, 358.8), acute transverse myelitis (323); acute alcohol intoxication (303.0); poisoning by drug and biologic substances (960, 979).</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
Huang 2015[63]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Taiwan</p> <p>Database/Codes: National Health Insurance Research Database (NHIRD) / ICD-9 code 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD 9 code</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
Hung 1994[64]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Taiwan</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital medical records / not used</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 and 1990 (See Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review by pediatric neurologists</p>
Kasemsap 2021 [65]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Thailand</p> <p>Database/Codes: National Health Security Office database (national health coverage) / ICD-10 code G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD code</p> <p>Validation: not done</p> <p>Electrophysiology testing / CSF sampling and results: of 4521 GBS cases identified, LP done in 68.5%; electrophysiologic study in 18.3%</p>
AUSTRALIA – OCEANIA	
Pillsbury 2023[66]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in New South Wales, Australia.</p> <p>Database/Codes: New South Wales Admitted Patient Data Collection (APDC) / ICD-10 codes – see Case Definition</p> <p>Case Definition: Narrow CD: G61.0 only; Broad CD: G61.0, G61.1 (serum neuropathy), G61.8 (other inflammatory polyneuropathies), G61.9 (Inflammatory polyneuropathy, unspecified)</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>

	<p>Note: The incidence table 2.1 presents the rate for the narrow case definition based on the specific ICD-10 code for GBS (G61.0). The broad definition included all the other codes listed above in addition to G61.0 and gave a rate of 10.3 (95% CI 9.6-11.0) for all ages. Clearly this includes many entities other than GBS and thus was not included in the incidence table.</p>
Clothier 2013[67]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases involving adolescent boys aged 12 to <16 years resident in Victoria, Australia. Database/Codes: Victorian Admitted Episodes Dataset; Victorian Emergency Minimum Dataset / ICD-10-AM code G61.0 Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done Note: The study included adolescent boys only to determine background rates ahead of the introduction of HPV vaccines for boys in Australia.</p>
Storey 1989[68]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Cases admitted to hospitals in Victoria, Australia. Database/Codes: Computerised medical record systems in Victorian teaching hospitals (total of 8) / not provided Case Definition: Cases reviewed by a neurologist who indicated that the patient met classical clinical criteria for GBS or had a related variant. Validation: Neurologist diagnosis</p>
Hankey 1987[69]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Cases admitted to one of 4 Perth (Australia) teaching hospitals. Database/Codes: Hospital Morbidity Data System / polyneuritis, polyneuropathy, Guillain-Barre syndrome Case Definition: NINCDS 1981 (see Table 2.3) Validation: Medical record review. Note: 109 cases identified; 99 presented with muscle weakness, 72 with paraesthesiae, 28 with myalgia; DTR's absent or reduced in all but 2 cases; cranial nerve palsies present in 70 cases; 5 cases of Miller-Fisher variant; autonomic dysfunction in 22; 31 required mechanical ventilation; Electrophysiology testing / CSF sampling and results: CSF examined in 103 cases and 92 had elevated CSF protein; nerve conduction studies and EMG exam done in 52, all with findings consistent with polyradiculopathy.</p>
Baker 2012[70]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in New Zealand, nationwide with a principal or additional diagnosis of GBS.</p>

	<p>Database/Codes: National Hospital Discharge database / ICD-9 code 357.0; ICD-10 code G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD codes</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
EUROPE	
Peric 2014[71]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in 3 Balkan countries (Serbia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Montenegro)</p> <p>Database/Codes: Medical records from all tertiary care centers / no code(s) provided</p> <p>Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1]</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review</p> <p>Brighton CD LOC distribution: Specifics of Brighton Levels of Certainty not presented but noted that almost 90% of cases met Level 1 or 2. Incidence based on Levels 1, 2, 3 and 4</p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: 327 GBS cases; 65% AIDP, 7% AMAN, 5% AMSAN, 3% Miller Fisher, 0.6% pharyngeal-cervical-brachial variant; 19% not specified.</p> <p>Electrophysiology testing / CSF sampling and results: LP done in 241 (74%) of which 88% had elevated CSF protein of >0.55g/l; only 2 (0.8%) had CSF WBC >50. Electrophysiology done in 262 (80%).</p>
Levison 2020[72]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases at any Danish pediatric hospital department</p> <p>Database/Codes: Danish National Patient Registry / ICD-8 code 354.00 – polyradiculitis acuta (from 1977-1983); ICD-10 code G61.0</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (See Table 3.3) and Brighton case definition [1] to classify level of diagnostic certainty</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review of 145 possible cases. Unable to locate the medical record for 67 additional cases. Record reviewed by one physician and if needed, by a neurologist.</p> <p>Case ascertainment validation (Sens (sensitivity), Spec (specificity), NPV (Negative predictive value), PPV (Positive predictive value): 125 cases confirmed for PPV of GBS codes of 86% (95% CI 80-91%).</p> <p>Brighton CD LOC distribution:</p>

	<p>18 (14%) Level 1; 88 (70%) Level 2; 19 (15%) level 3 and 0 Level 4. Failure to reach Level 1 was due to no Nerve Conduction Study (79%) or CSF protein not elevated (20%). 98% of cases had LP done. Those with normal CSF protein were obtained earlier in the disease course: 23 cases, median time from onset to LP of 2 days (Interquartile range 104 days); Of 100 with elevated CSF protein median time to LP was 5 days (interquartile range 2-9 days). Of 20 nonconfirmed cases 6 had medullary lesions, 3 were diagnosed as functional condition, 7 had other conditions and 4 were CIDP.</p>
<p>Levison 2019[73]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospital cases with a primary GBS diagnosis at any Danish department of neurology. Database/Codes: Danish National Patient Registry / ICD-8 code 354.00 – polyradiculitis acuta (from 1977-1983); ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: NINDS (year not specified but see Table 3.3 as all years very similar) and classified according to Brighton case definition Validation: Selected a validation cohort of 573 adult cases (total cases found 2,319). Retrieved 425 medical record which were reviewed by one physician and for uncertain cases, verified by a senior neurologist. Brighton CD LOC distribution: Confirmed GBS in 356 of 425 cases (83.8%). Brighton level 1 44.9%; Level 2 43.5%; Level 3 10.4%; Level 4 1.1%. Miller Fisher variant 1.6%; no other variants found. Case ascertainment validation (Sens (sensitivity), Spec (specificity), NPV (Negative predictive value), PPV (Positive predictive value): by NINDS criteria = 83.8% (95% CI 80.0-87.0); by Brighton criterion = 82.8% (79.0-86.1) Main reason for not reaching Brighton level 1 was normal or missing information of the protein concentration in CSF (36.0%) and normal or missing information of the Nerve Conduction Study (30.3%)</p>
<p>Al Hakem 2019[74]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: All Denmark population-based study including cases of GBS seen in hospital, emergency rooms or outpatients. Database/Codes: Danish National Patient Registry (DNPR) / ICD-10 code G61.0 (GBS), G61.1 (serum neuropathy), G61.8 (other inflammatory neuropathy), G61.9 (inflammatory neuropathy, unspecified) Case Definition: NINDS 1990 diagnostic criteria for GBS; Wakerly 2014 definitions for Miller Fisher and Pharyngocervicobrachial (PCB) variants and overlap syndromes (See Table 3.3). Brighton CD[1] used to classify cases (LOC 1, 2, 3 or 4) after medical record review. For Incidence Rate only included only cases meeting Brighton CD LOC 1, 2 or 3. Validation: Medical record review for all ascertained cases.</p>

	<p>Brighton CD LOC distribution: 299 of 1078 cases retrieved using the ICD-10 codes met the NINDS or Wakerly criteria depending on GBS type; A total of 279 (93%) cases met the Brighton CD at Level 1 (155; 52%), Level 2 (118; 39%) or Level 3 (6; 2%). Twenty cases (7%) were assigned Level 4; missing data among these 20 cases were: no hyporeflexia (4 cases); course of disease not monophasic (4 cases); failed to reach nadir within 28 days after onset (12 cases).</p>
Rasmussen 2012[75]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: national birth cohort of infants delivered in Denmark between Jan 1, 1980 and Dec 31, 2009 and admitted to hospital for the first time for one of several selected events, including GBS. Database/Codes: Danish National Hospital Registry / ICD-8 34400 and ICD-10 G61.0 code for acute infectious and post-infectious polyneuritis (GBS) Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done for this study</p>
Bak 1985[76]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospital cases in Ringkøbing County, Denmark Database/Codes: not used Case Definition: Senior neurologist diagnosis Validation: Based on neurologist diagnosis – all cases in the Ringkøbing county known to the neurology team</p>
Halls 1988[77]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Copenhagen County, Denmark Database/Codes: not stated Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 / 1981 – see Table 2.3 Validation: medical record review <i>Note: point out that the NINCDS criterion may miss cases because of absolute requirement for areflexia to meet case definition</i></p>
Skufca 2017[78]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Finland Database/Codes: National Hospital Discharge Register (HILMO) / ICD10 code G61.0 (GBS) Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done <i>Note: study was done to determine background rates prior to introduction of HPV vaccination program for adolescent girls so only included 11-15 yr girls</i></p>

<p>Rantala 1991</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Finland. Database/Codes: Finnish National Board of Health hospital discharge database / any discharge diagnosis of polyneuropathy – no codes provided Case Definition: Essential for diagnosis - progressive motor weakness in >1 limb; areflexia or appreciable hyporeflexia; ≤50 monocytes or ≤2 PMN per mm³ of CSF. Strongly supportive of diagnosis – progression over some days to a few weeks; cranial-nerve involvement; onset of recovery 2-4 weeks after halt in progression; raised CSF protein after one week of symptoms; abnormal electrodiagnostics with slowed conduction or prolonged F waves. Validation: Case history review by a pediatric neurologist.</p>
<p>Kinnunen 1998[80]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Finland. Database/Codes: Finnish national wide Hospital Discharge Register / ICD code for polyradiculitis (version and code not provided). Case Definition: NINCDS 1981 (see Table 2.3) Validation: Medical chart review; primary screening by one of the authors (2 years training in neurology) and confirmed by experienced neurologist.</p>
<p>Sipila 2017[81]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in mainland Finland. Database/Codes: Finnish Care Register for Health Care / ICD-10 G61.0 for GBS; excluded ICD-10 code Z50.X (rehabilitation diagnosis) to ensure capturing new cases. Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done</p>
<p>Sipila 2015[82]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Southwest Finland. Database/Codes: Turku University Hospital Patient Discharge Register / ICD-10 G61.0 (GBS) Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done</p>
<p>Delannoy 2016[83]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in France.</p>

	<p>Database/Codes: French hospital discharge database PMSI (Programme de Medicalisation des Systemes d'Information) / ICD-10 G61.0 (GBS)</p> <p>Case Definition: main CD was first hospitalization for GBS based on ICD-10 G61.0 as principal diagnosis; 3 alternative case definitions: 1. excluded codes that could indicate neurologic disorders likely to be misclassified as GBS (diabetes, HIV, cancer, alcoholic disease, renal insufficiency); 2. Excluded cases that had 2 or more additional hospital admissions for GBS in the year following the first GBS hospitalization; 3. Excluded cases that did not receive immunoglobulin or plasma Exchange during first hospital stay as well as cases that were managed in hospital for <6 days.</p> <p>Validation: not done</p> <p>Note: Crude incidence rate / 100,000 person years based on method used to ascertain cases: main 2.42 (2.37-2.47); alternative 1 1.80 (1.75-1.84); alternative 2 1.76 (1.71-1.80); alternative 3 1.23 (1.19-1.26).</p>
Hense 2014[84]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: inpatient and outpatient cases including data on diagnostic and therapeutic procedures and outpatient drug prescriptions in Germany.</p> <p>Database/Codes: German Pharmacoepidemiological Research Database (GePaRD) / ICD10 GBS code G61.0;</p> <p>Case Definition: 2 code-based definitions: 1. GBS ICD10 code only; 2. GBS ICD10 code plus an Operations and procedures code of either LP, neurography or myography during the same hospital stay.</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
Lehmann 2007[85]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Germany.</p> <p>Database/Codes: German hospitals (80-87% of all hospitals in Germany) admissions administrative database. / ICD10 GBS code (G61.0)</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD code</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
Chroni 2004[86]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in 2 Patras (Greece) hospitals – University Hospital and Karamandanio Children Hospital.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not stated / included patients with diagnoses of GBS, polyradiculitis, idiopathic polyneuropathy, neuritis caranialis or acute paraparesis. Excluded any with polyradiculoneuropathy associated with collagen and neoplastic diseases, hepatitis, HIV and any with >50WBC/mm³ of CSF.</p> <p>Case Definition: NINDS 1990 (see Table 2.3)</p>

	<p>Validation: Medical chart review</p>
Markoula 2007[87]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in a single neurology inpatient service in Northwest Greece. Database/Codes: not used Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (see Table 2.3). Excluded cases with: >5 mononuclear WBC/mm³ of CSF; neuropathies associated with exogenous toxic agents, metals or drugs; porphyria; hereditary demyelinating neuropathy; presence of a sensory level or sphincter dysfunction. Validation: Medical chart review</p>
Hafsteinsdottir 2018[88]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Iceland. Database/Codes: Landspítali University Hospital and Akureyri Hospital medical records / codes not provided Case Definition: Brighton GBS case definition Validation: medical record review; Brighton CD LOC distribution: of 63 cases meeting the Brighton CD, 36 (57%) were Level 1, 20 (32%) Level 2 and 7 (11%) Level 3. Nerve conduction studies done for 47 (75%) of cases with 87% showing AIDP, 4% AMAN and 9% were normal.</p>
Beghi 1996[89]	<p>Study type: GBS Registry surveillance study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Lombardy (Italian province) hospitals with neurology and child neurology departments. Database/Codes: not used Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (See Table 2.3); minimal required criteria: muscle weakness in >1 limb; absence or severe reduction of tendon reflexes; absence of sensory levels; <10 WBC or 2 PMNs / mm³ in CSF; absence of diphtheria, botulism, poliomyelitis, porphyria or exposure to organic solvents, organophosphorous esters or lead. Also included Atypical GBS defined by Ropper classification (see Table 2.3). Validation: Case report form completed by local investigator at each study site. Note: Study designed to create a GBS registry covering the entire Lombardy region (population 8,891,652 based on 1981 census). Included 109 cases of whom 95 (87.2%) were typical GBS, 7 (6.4%) were atypical, including 5 Fisher syndrome, 1 paraparetic variant and 1 pure pandysautonomia; 7(6.4%) didn't fit into any of the typical or atypical case definitions.</p>
Granieri 2019[90]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Ferrara city, Italy.</p>

	<p>Database/Codes: Ferrara Health System Administrative database / ICD-9 GBS code 357.0 Case Definition: NINDS 1990 (See Table 2.3) Validation: Medical record review</p>
Govoni 2003[91]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospital cases prospectively enrolled while on neurological Ward of Ferrara University Hospital (Italian city) and retrospective search of hospital medical records and clinical neurophysiology services Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases / ICD-9 codes 357 (inflammatory and toxic neuropathy), 356.4 (progressive idiopathic neuropathy), 356.8 (others), 356.9 (unspecified) Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see Table 2.3) Validation: Neurologic examination as part of patient care.</p>
Govoni 1999[92]	<p>Study type: Population-based surveillance study with prospective case ascertainment and retrospective chart review. Case Sources: Hospital cases prospectively enrolled while on neurological Ward of Ferrara University Hospital (Italian city) and retrospective search of hospital medical records and clinical neurophysiology services Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases / ICD-9 codes 357 (inflammatory and toxic neuropathy), 356.4 (progressive idiopathic neuropathy), 356.8 (others), 356.9 (unspecified) Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see Table 2.3) Validation: Medical record review. <i>Note: Calculated incidence separately for GBS meeting NINCDS criteria (43 cases) and those not meeting criteria but considered to be clinical variants of GBS (8 cases including 3 Miller Fisher syndrome, four polyneuritis cranialis and 1 sensory form).</i></p>
Emilia-Romagna Study Group on Clinical and Epidemiological Problems in Neurology 1997[93] and 1998[94]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study Case Sources: Cases seen in neurologic units (Departments, Services, University Clinics) of the Public Health System of Emilia Romagna which includes 8 Italian provinces (Bologna, Ferrara, Forli-Cesena, Modena, Parma, Piacenza, Ravenna, Reggio Emilia; total 3,090,512 population.) Study investigators asked neurologists to refer cases but also checked completeness of case ascertainment by searching for GBS in discharge databases. Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases / ICD-9 code 357.xx (any peripheral neuropathy) Case Definition: NINCDS 1978, 1981 and 1990 criteria for GBS (see Table 2.3); Miller Fisher syndrome (MFS; required triad of ataxia, ophthalmoplegia and areflexia in the absence of peripheral limb weakness; GBS variants had acute monophasic peripheral nervous system diseases with albumino-cytologic dissociation but not fulfilling criteria for GBS or MFS.</p>

	<p>Validation: All cases reviewed by neurologists involved in the study. Required consensus on diagnosis for the GBS variants other than MFS.</p> <p>Note: <i>all included cases reviewed by study group and a standard data collection form used to capture: date of onset; infections during month prior to onset and other relevant associated diseases; date of observation or admission; standard neurologic exam; presence or absence of fever at onset; presence or absence of autonomic symptoms or signs; date of CSF collection and results; electrophysiologic study results. Patients followed up daily for first 10 days, twice weekly from days 11-30, once weekly during the second month after onset and then once monthly for next four months or until recovery.</i></p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: Of 105 total cases, 87(82.8%) were classic GBS, 7 (6.7%) Miller Fisher and 11 (10.5%) GBS variants other than Miller Fisher Syndrome.</p>
Paolino 1991[95]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Multiple sources including hospitalised cases, clinic attendees, interview of all practising neurologists in Ferrara, Italy</p> <p>Database/Codes: Looked for diagnoses of: GBS, polyradiculitis, polyneuritis, polyradiculoneuritis, polyneuropathy, poliomyelitis, Landry’s ascending paralysis, bilateral Bell’s palsy, meningoradiculitis, neuritis, peripheral neuropathy.</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 and 1981 (see Table 2.3).</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review</p>
Benedetti 2019[96]	<p>Study type: Mixed retrospective and prospective study cohort</p> <p>Case Sources: Patients with Guillain-Barré syndrome admitted to the Neurology Unit of Sant’Andrea Hospital in the La Spezia area (Liguria region, north-western Italy). Study population originated from four local sub-regions: Golfo dei Poeti, Val di Magra, Val di Vara, and Riviera Spezzina.</p> <p>Database/Codes: La Spezia hospital Neurological unit discharge database / ICD-9 GBS code 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: NINDS 1990 and Wakerly 2014 (see table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review</p> <p>Electrophysiology testing / CSF results: Of 92 cases identified, 75 (87%) had electrophysiologic testing and 65 (71%) had CSF examined. Protein was elevated in 58(89%) and normal in the rest (11%).</p>
Benedetti 2015[97]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Adult (≥18 yrs) cases identified by the Italian Network for the study of GBS (ITANG) active surveillance; also searched hospital discharge data to ensure completeness of case ascertainment.</p>

	<p>Database/Codes: Italian National Institute of Health database / ICD-9 code 357.0 (GBS)</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990; Brighton case definition [1]</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review and follow up every 3 months for 1 year post discharge via telephone survey.</p> <p>Brighton CD LOC distribution: Among 265 cases - 45.5% Level 1 GBS, 20% Level 2 GBS, 2.5% Level 3 GBS, 7.9% Level 4 GBS, 16.2% Level 5 GBS; 0.8% Level 1 Miller Fisher, 2.2% Level 2 Miller Fisher; 0 Level 3; 4.9% Level 4 Miller Fisher</p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: 237 AIDP (64.9%); 57 AMAN/AMSAN (15.7%); 29 Miller Fisher (7.9%); 14 facial diplegia (3.8%); 5 pure sensory neuropathy (1.4%); 3 pharyngeal-cervical-brachial form (0.8%); 19 other form (5.2%); 1 unclassified (0.3%).</p>
Bogliun 2004[98]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Study based on the pilot project by Beghi 1996 in the same region (Lombardy, Italy).</p> <p>Database/Codes: not used</p> <p>Case Definition: same as Beghi 1996 described above</p> <p>Validation: same as Beghi 1996, described above</p> <p>Note: Total of 138 cases enrolled with 10 (7.2%) atypical variants including 4 Miller Fisher, 3 cranial polyneuritis (facial diplegia), 2 pure motor signs and one sensory loss and areflexia.</p>
Chio 2003[99]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Prospective enrolment of cases from all 28 departments of neurology in Piemonte and Valle d'Aosta (Italy); supplemented by search of all discharges from public and private hospitals in Piedmont region as well as search of data collected by Flaccid Palsy Surveillance Network among children aged ≤ 14 years old.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases / ICD-9 codes 357.0 (acute infective polyneuritis), 357.8 (other polyneuritis), 357.9 (unspecified polyneuritis).</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978; excluded cases with marked, persistent asymmetry of neurologic signs; >5 mononuclear leukocytes in CSF; diabetic or alcoholic neuropathy; neuropathies associated with exogenous toxic agents, metal or drugs; poliomyelitis; porphyria. Classified cases as: classic GBS (NINCDS criteria) or Miller-Fisher syndrome (triad of ataxia, ophthalmoplegia and areflexia in absence of relevant limb weakness). Excluded other GBS variants.</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review with three members of scientific committee for the study verifying blindly, the local physician diagnosis.</p>
Congia 1989[100]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Sardinia, Italy.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not described</p>

	<p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1981; required cytoalbuminogic dissociation in CSF to include a case.</p> <p>Validation: medical record review</p>
<p>Van der Maas 2011[101]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: All sources of medical information including hospital admission and outpatient visits throughout the Netherlands.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Integrated Primary Care Information database (GP research database) / GBS, AIDP, CIDP, Miller-Fisher sndrome, (poly)neuropathy, (poly)radiculopathy, AMAN, AMSAN</p> <p>Case Definition: Brighton case definition[1]</p> <p>Validation: Electronic database included a statement that GBS was confirmed by a neurologist (true case) or GP or neurologist included GBS in the differential diagnosis (possible case) For all ‘true’ and ‘possible’ cases, questionnaire sent to GP along with a request to provide copies of specialist letters. Neurologist assigned the final classification based on the additional information.</p> <p>Case ascertainment validation (Sens (sensitivity), Spec (specificity), NPV (Negative predictive value), PPV (Positive predictive value): Of 47 cases with additional information, 23 were confirmed as GBS (21) or Miller Fisher (2) for a PPV of 49% (35-63%)</p>
<p>Van Koningsveld 2000[102]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in southwestern Netherlands</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases / ICD-9 code 357.0</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 (See table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review by senior neurologist. Of 615 coded cases, 494 (80.3%) met the NINCDS criterio. Among 116 excluded cases 24 had CIDP, 18 failed to meet the criterio, 13 files not found and 18 were from outside the study area.</p>
<p>Farbu 2015[103]</p>	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised GBS cases enrolled by study team which was responsible for neurological care of all people in Norway’s South Rogaland region.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not used</p> <p>Case Definition: NINDS 1990 (See Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Clinical evaluaton</p>
<p>Stojanov 2020[104]</p>	<p>Study type: Mixed retrospective and prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Serbia.</p>

	<p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases from all 5 tertiary healthcare centers in Serbia / not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1]</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review</p> <p>Note: 640 GBS cases; Did not provide Brighton levels of certainty breakdown; onset to nadir mean 10.2days (SD 8.3days; median 8, range 1-28 days).</p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: Electrophysiology performed on 389 at the Clinical center of Serbia: 64.3% AIDP, 8.2% AMAN, 4.9% AMSAN, 3.1% Miller Fisher, 0.3% Pharyngo-cervico-brachial variant; 19% undetermined.</p>
<p>Blanco-Ruiz 2024[105]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Spain covered by the National Epidemiological Surveillance Network (47 million people)</p> <p>Database/Codes: Spanish Minimum Basic Hospital Discharge Dataset / ICD-10 code G61.0 (GBS)</p> <p>Case Definition: Medical code</p> <p>Validation: Not validated</p>
<p>Aragones 2021[106]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Incident hospitalised GBS patients living in the district of Osona (Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain), identified through a neurological disease registry, serving a catchment population of 151,907.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Neurologic disease registry at Hospital Universitari de Vic which included GBS cases contributed to by all hospital neurologists</p> <p>Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1]</p> <p>Validation: Medical record review.</p> <p>Brighton CD LOC distribution: 43 new cases of GBS identified: 58.2% Level 1, 30.2% Level 2, 2.3% Level 3, 9.3% Level 4.</p> <p>GBS subtype distribution: EMG done in 86% of cases; of these 73.7% had demyelinating pattern and 26.3% axonal pattern. 72.1% AIDP, 16.3% AMAN, 4.7% AMSAN, 4.7% Miller-Fisher.</p>
<p>Cuadrado 2004[107]</p>	<p>Study type: Prospective GBS surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Spain</p> <p>Database/Codes: not described</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1981 (See Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Clinical records reviewed by neurologists</p>

<p>Cuadrado 2001[108]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases, out-patient visits, neurophysiological laboratory lists across Spain. Database/Codes: not described Case Definition: NINCDS 1981 (see Table 2.3) Validation: Clinical records reviewed by a neurologist.</p>
<p>Sedano 1993[109]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in University Hospital Marques de Valdecilla - neurologic referral center for Cantabria, Spain. Database/Codes: Hospital discharge database / ICD code 354 (inflammatory polyneuropathy) Case Definition: NINCDS 1981/1990 (see Table 2.3) Validation: Medical chart review GBS subtype distribution: of 69 identified cases, 60 (86.9%) were typical GBS, 2 had Fisher’s syndrome; other noted to have incomplete follow-up so not clear if able to classify.</p>
<p>Jiang 1997[110]</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Sweden. Database/Codes: Hospital Inpatient Register / ICD-9 Swedish version code 357A (GBS) Case Definition: ICD code Validation: not done Case ascertainment validation (Sens (sensitivity), Spec (specificity), NPV (Negative predictive value), PPV (Positive predictive value): note that a previous study showed 83% PPV and 100% NPV for GBS code as used in southwest Stockholm and considered reasonable that similar rates would apply throughout Sweden. (see details in Jiang 1997[110] below)</p>
<p>Hafsteinsdottir 2023[111]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Vastra Gotaland, Sweden (population 1,682,625). Database/Codes: Diagnosis databases for four regional hospitals / ICD-10 code G61.0 Case Definition: Brighton case definition [1] Levels 1-3. Validation: Medical chart review. Case ascertainment validation Sens (sensitivity), Spec (specificity), NPV (Negative predictive value), PPV (Positive predictive value):</p>

	93 of 126 cases with GBS code confirmed (68.4%); 35 (27.8%) coded incorrectly or had an alternate diagnosis; 7 (5.6%) thought to have GBS but didn't meet Brighton criteria for levels 1, 2 or 3.
Cheng 2000[112]	<p>Study type: Prospective GBS surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: Cases referred by a multicentre network of 18 Swedish neurologists covering a population of 4.48 million in Stockholm. Also searched hospital databases for GBS to ensure complete ascertainment.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital databases / ICD-9 357</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (see Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: Clinical follow up by neurologist of notified cases and neurologist medical record review for any non-notified cases.</p>
Jiang 1997[113]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Southwest Stockholm.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Stockholm County Hospital In-patient Register (HIR) / ICD-8 code 354.01 (1973-1986 for Guillain-Barre polyradiculitis) and ICD-9 code 357A (1987-1992 for acute inflammatory polyneuropathy / Guillain-Barre syndrome).</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 (See Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: medical record review by a senior neurologist.</p> <p>Note: <i>in addition to determining GBS incidence, study objectives including assessing the quality of information on GBS diagnosis recorded in a population-based register and to examine sources of errors when using hospital discharges as a source for incident GBS cases.</i></p> <p>Case ascertainment validation Sens (sensitivity), Spec (specificity), NPV (Negative predictive value), PPV (Positive predictive value) :</p> <p>PPV (probability of coded GBS cases to fulfil NINCDS criteria): 102 coded cases but charts available for only 83 cases of which 69 (83.1%) met the NINCDS criteria. PPV for code positioned as first time registered GBS diagnosis was 84.0% (63/75) and when coded as secondary diagnosis was 75% (6/8). The 14 false positives included 3 CIDP, 3 myelitis, 2 diabetic polyneuropathy, 1 HSV radiculitis, 1 Vitamin B12 deficiency and 4 neuropathy of unknown origin.</p> <p>NPV defined as probability of not being coded as GBS when NINCDS criteria not fulfilled. For NPV used a surrogate population sample that included 40 patients discharged with diagnosis of unspecific polyneuropathy (code 354.09); all 40 case medical records were reviewed by a neurologist who applied the GBS NINCDS criteria, and if not fulfilled, assigned a diagnosis based on clinical judgment. None of the 40 cases met the NINCDS criteria, giving an NPV of 100%.</p>
Jiang 1995[114]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Southwest Stockholm.</p>

	<p>Database/Codes: Stockholm County Hospital In-patient Register (HIR) / ICD-8 code 354.01 (1973-1986 for Guillain-Barre polyradiculitis) and ICD-9 code 357A (1987-1992 for acute inflammatory polyneuropathy / Guillain-Barre syndrome).</p> <p>Case Definition: ICD codes</p> <p>Validation: not done – but noted prior validation in same región showed code PPV of 83% and NPV of 100% (see Jiang 1997[113])</p>
MacDonald 2000[115]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Prospective community-based search for neurologic disorders in 13 general practices in the London, England area linked to the national Hospital for Neurology and neurosurgery. Multiple case-findings methods used, but nothing specified for GBS in particular.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not described</p> <p>Case Definition: not described</p> <p>Validation: not described</p>
Carey 2021[116]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases and clinic records for London City, England.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) / READ codes F3700 (GBS), F3701 (postinfectious polyneuritis), F3702 (Miller-Fisher síndrome), F370z (acute infective polyneuritis NOS)</p> <p>Case Definition: GBS codes</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
Rees 1998[117]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Multiple methods used to ascertain GBS cases in Southeast England: voluntary reporting scheme by consultant neurologists and neurophysiologists; hospital discharges; subjects enrolled in a study of <i>C jejuni</i> as a cause of GBS; death certificates.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharges databases / ICD-9 code 357.0 (GBS)</p> <p>Case Definition: case diagnosed as GBS by one of two neurologists or met criteria of NINCDS 1990;</p> <p>Validation: neurologist assessment or medical chart review</p>
Winner 1990[118]	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Oxfordshire, England.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Oxford Region hospital discharge databases / ICD-8 code 354 (polyneuritis and polyradiculitis including GBS) and ICD-9 code 357.0 (GBS) and 357.9 (unspecified toxic and inflammatory neuropathy)</p>

	<p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 /1981; and patients with Miller-Fisher triad (ophthalmoplegia, ataxia, areflexia) without limb weakness; see Table 2.3</p> <p>Validation: hospital record review</p>
Haberman 1982[119]	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Southeast England.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge databases / ICD-8 code 354.9 (polyneuritis or polyradiculitis)</p> <p>Case Definition: cases presenting with acute or subacute onset of progressive muscular weakness with areflexia accompanied by mild sensory disturbances AND diagnosed as acute polyneuritis of the GBS type by the consultant physician or neurologist.</p> <p>Validation: medical chart review</p> <p>Note: of 83 cases with code 354.9, 44 excluded because: correctly coded but not GBS (25); incorrectly coded (4); duplicate due to readmission (3); resident outside the population region (7); onset date not in study Interval (5).</p>
Hughes 2006[120]	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Scotland.</p> <p>Database/Codes: General Practice Research Database (GPRD) / codes for GBS or infective polyneuritis (not provided)</p> <p>Case Definition: code for GBS</p> <p>Validation: not done</p>
Sridharan 1993[121] UK Scotland	<p>Study type: Prospective GBS surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: admitted to one of Aberdeen teaching hospitals (serve Aberdeen and Regional Referral service for hospitals in Grampian, Orkney and Shetland; total population 543,213 with 103,166 over age of 60 years.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Scottish Morbidity Record System 1 / ICD 8 code (354) and ICD 9 (357.0; 357.9) for GBS</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 and 1981 (see Table 2.3)</p> <p>Validation: case review by consultant neurologist</p>
Willame 2021[131] ADVANCE project	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Cases identified in country electronic health records: Denmark – Aarhus University Hospital and Staten Serum Institute; Italy – Agenzia Regionale di Sanita, Val Padana and Pedianet; Spain – BIFAPO [Base de Datos para la iverstigacion Frmacoepidemiologica en Atencion Primaria]; United Kingdom: Royal College of General Practitioners Research and Surveillance Centre and The Health Improvement Network (THIN).</p> <p>Database/Codes: Multiple European country electronic databases – see Case Sources / medical codes for GBS</p> <p>Case Definition: Medical codes</p>

	<p>Validation: not validated</p> <p>Note: <i>Incidence data presented for all countries as well as individually by country</i></p>
<p>Willame 2023[122] ACCESS Project</p>	<p>Study type: Administrative data study</p> <p>Case Sources: Varies by country-specific databases: Spain – SIDIAP, FISABIO, BIFAPO, includes GP visits, in- and out-patients; Italy (ARS – GP, inpatients and emergency visits); Netherlands (PHARMO – inpatients, out-patients and GP visits); Denmark (national Danish registry includes inpatients and outpatient visits); France (SNDS – inpatients and outpatient visits); United Kingdom (CPRD – GP database).</p> <p>Database/Codes: Multiple European country electronic databases – see Case Sources / medical codes for GBS</p> <p>Case Definition: Medical codes</p> <p>Validation: not validated</p>
MIDDLE EAST	
<p>Tonekaboni 2021[123]</p>	<p>Study type: AFP (acute flaccid paralysis) surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: Iranian AFP cases diagnosed by AFP committee as GBS.</p> <p>Database/Codes: AFP surveillance database / not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: not described</p> <p>Validation: Case classification by AFP committee composed of infection, epidemiologist and neurologist experts.</p>
<p>Esteghamati 2008[124]</p>	<p>Study type: AFP (acute flaccid paralysis) surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: Cases of acute flaccid paralysis reported to Iranian national AFP surveillance system.</p> <p>Database/Codes: AFP surveillance database</p> <p>Case Definition: not provided</p> <p>Validation: Case review and verification as to diagnosis by national committee</p>
<p>Momen 2017[125]</p>	<p>Study type: AFP (acute flaccid paralysis) surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: GBS cases identified by Iranian Poliomyelitis surveillance program from Jan 2006 to Dec 2015.</p> <p>Database/Codes: AFP surveillance database / not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: roughly symmetrical motor weakness over a period ranging from days to 4 weeks, and decrease or absence of DTRs in association with appropriate clinical evaluation.</p> <p>Validation: Clinical examination and medical records</p>
<p>Hosseininezhad 2022[126]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Northern Iran, Gullan province.</p>

	<p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge database and Death certificates / ICD-9 code 357.0 (GBS)</p> <p>Case Definition: GBS diagnosis made by a neurologist OR case met criterio of Asbury and Cornblath or had ICD-10 code of G61.1 and GBS the significant and first diagnosis.</p> <p>Validation: Medical chart review</p>
<p>Barzegar 2007[127]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases captured by the Iranian national AFP surveillance program and then confirmed to be GBS by child neurologist examination.</p> <p>Database/Codes: AFP surveillance database</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 – see Table 2.3</p> <p>Validation: Child neurologist</p>
<p>Arami 2006[128]</p>	<p>Study type: Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Prospective enrolment of hospitalised cases in Iran.</p> <p>Database/Codes: not used</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1978 – see Table 2.3</p> <p>Validation: Clinical evaluation of each case</p> <p>Note: <i>all identified cases had electrophysiologic testing; classified into four groups: AIDP, AMAN, AMSAN and mixed type (where test results were described as unexcitable or markedly reduced compound muscle action potentials in ≥ 2 nerves associated with presence of at least two electrophysiological findings suggesting demyelination.) Of 76 enrolled, 46 (60.5%) had demyelination, 19 (25%) had axonal degeneration and 11 (14.5%) had mixed pattern.</i></p>
<p>Jasem 2013[129]</p>	<p>Study type: AFP (acute flaccid paralysis) surveillance study</p> <p>Case Sources: GBS cases found via Iraq’s AFP surveillance program.</p> <p>Database/Codes: AFP surveillance database / not stated</p> <p>Case Definition: not provided</p> <p>Validation: unnot described</p> <p>Note: <i>Of 4974 AFP cases, 2611 (52.5%) were GBS.</i></p>
<p>Ismail 1998[130]</p>	<p>Study type: Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>Case Sources: Hospitalised cases in Kuwait.</p> <p>Database/Codes: Hospital discharge database / coded as GBS; code not provided</p> <p>Case Definition: NINCDS 1990 – see Table 2.3</p>

Validation: medical record review

Table 2.3 GBS Case Definitions used in incidence studies in Table 2.1 and cited in Table 2.2

Case Definition Source	Definition
<p>NINCDS 1978[132]</p>	<p>Progressive motor weakness of the upper and/or lower limbs AND loss or marked reduction of muscle stretch reflexes.</p> <p>Required to support the diagnosis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progressive motor weakness of more than one limb (can range from minimal leg weakness, with or without mild ataxia, to total paralysis of all four limbs and the trunk plus bulbar and facial paralysis and external ophthalmoplegia) • Areflexia – usually universal but may be primarily distal (lower legs) with definite hyporeflexia of biceps and knee jerks <p>Strongly supportive of the diagnosis, ranked in order of importance (but not absolutely required)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motor weakness develops rapidly but ceases to progress by four weeks into the illness. About 50% reach nadir by 2 weeks after onset, 80% by three weeks and >90% by four weeks. • Relative symmetry – not absolute, but usually if one limb is affected, the opposite is as well • Mild sensory symptoms or signs • Cranial nerve involvement: facial weakness, often bilateral, seen in about 50% of cases. May also be involvement of tongue and chewing muscles. • Recovery usually begins 2-4 weeks after progression stops. • Autonomic dysfunction (e.g., tachycardia, other arrhythmias, postural hypotension, hypertension, vasomotor symptoms) • Absence of fever at the onset of neuritic symptoms <p>CSF features strongly supportive of the diagnosis (but not required)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elevated CSF protein after first week of symptoms. • ≤ 10 mononuclear leukocytes/mm³ <p>Electrodiagnostic features strongly supportive of the diagnosis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • About 80% of cases will have evidence of nerve conduction slowing or block at some point during the illness – often delayed until several weeks into the illness. Up to 20% may have normal conduction studies. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ but normal CSF or mononuclear leukocytes ranging from 11-50/mm³ didn't preclude acceptance of a case. <p>Features that cast doubt on the diagnosis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • marked persistent asymmetry of weakness; • persistent bladder or bowel dysfunction, or presence of dysfunction at the onset of illness • definite diagnosis of toxic neuropathy, porphyria, diphtheria, polio or botulism; • >50 mononuclear leukocytes/mm³ or presence of polymorphonuclear leukocytes in CSF;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a sharp sensory level <p>Features that rule out the diagnosis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current history of hexacarbon abuse (volatile solvents; n-hexane, methyl n-butyl ketone; includes huffing of paint lacquer vapors or addictive glue sniffing) • Abnormal porphyrin metabolisms (indicates acute intermittent porphyria) • History of recent diphtheritic infection • Features clinically consistent with lead neuropathy (upper limb weakness with prominent wrist drop; may be asymmetrical) and evidence of lead intoxication • Purely sensory syndrome • Definite diagnosis of a condition such as poliomyelitis, botulisms, paralysis or toxic neuropathy
<p>NINCDS 1981[133]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reiterates verbatim the 1978 criteria as reproduced above (NINCDS 1978) • Provided additional guidance on variant presentatioin as follows: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Sensory loss and areflexia without motor weakness: must have all of the following: rapid onset; widespread, symmetrical distribution of sensory loss/areflexia; recovery complete or nearly so; CSF protein elevated with few or no WBC; characteristic electrodiagnostic results with demyelinating process. Polyneuritis cranialis (symmetrical cranial nerve dysfunction only): must have all of the following: cranial nerves I and II uninvolved; typical course of illness and recovery; elevated CSF protein; typical electrodiagnostic pattern of demyelination. Pure Pandysautonomia: note lack of evidence to support a link to GBS (while acknowledging that some measure of autonomic dysfunction present in many GBS cases)
<p>NINCDS 1990[134]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reiterates verbatim the 1978 criteria as reproduced above (NINCDS 1978) • Provides additional comments that are noted to be opinions of the authors as opposed to being a consensus of NINCDS which proposed 1978 criteria. Includes the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progressive motor weakness and areflexia required for the diagnosis
<p>Ropper 1992[135]</p>	<p>Pure motor GBS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progressive, relatively symmetric weakness in all arms • Evidence of a preceding viral illness should have subsided by the time neuropathic symptoms appear No paresthesias or sensory loss • Usual CSF has ≤ 10 mononuclear cells/mm³ but can see 11-50 in some cases • Normal or minimally abnormal electrophysiologic studies may be seen in 5-14% of patients especially early in illness <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provide criteria for the prevalence of specific electrophysiologic findings (see article)

<p>Pure sensory GBS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paresthesias in the feet and hands • No weakness or respiratory failure • Areflexia or hyporeflexia in all limbs by 1 week • Distally diminished sensation involving mainly vibration & joint position • Proximal progression of numbness and sensory loss on the limbs over several days to 1 month • Improvement in paresthesias and sensory loss by 2-4 months from onset • Lab <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Elevated CSF protein within 3 weeks of onset ○ Severe sensory nerve conduction abnormalities ○ Minimal motor conduction and late response abnormalities
<p>Fisher's syndrome</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bilateral, relatively symmetric weakness of several extraocular muscles & ptosis • Limb and gait ataxia with cerebellar tremor • Areflexia in all limbs by 1 week • Progression of aforementioned 3 features over several days to 3 weeks • Minimal or no limb, facial, or oropharyngeal weakness, or paresthesias • Normal alertness: no cerebellar dysarthria except as a result of facial or oropharyngeal weakness; no Babinski signs • Lab <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Variable, usually slight, elevation of CSF protein concentration ○ Abnormal motor nerve conduction and late responses in the legs
<p>Pharyngeal-Cervical-Brachial (PCB) variant</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progressive weakness in the neck, shoulders, proximal arms, oropharyngeal muscles and diaphragm over 1-3 weeks • Areflexia or hyporeflexia in the arms by 1 week of illness • Normal (or virtually normal) leg power and tendon reflexes • Minimal or no paresthesias or sensory loss • Lab <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Variable, usually slight, elevation of CSF protein concentration ○ Abnormal motor nerve conduction and late responses in the arms: no decrement or increment in compound muscle action potential with repetitive stimulation
<p>Paraparetic variant</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progressive leg weakness over 1-3 weeks • Areflexia or hyporeflexia in the legs by 1 week of illness • Normal (or virtually normal) power and reflexes in the arms and cranial nerve innervated muscles • Minimal or no paresthesias or sensory loss • Lab <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Variable, usually slight, elevation of CSF protein concentration ○ Abnormal motor nerve conduction and late responses in the legs <p>Pure pandysautonomia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progressive sympathetic and parasympathetic dysfunction over 1-3 weeks • No limb weakness, ophthalmoplegia, or ataxia • Areflexia or hyporeflexia by 1 week • Improvement of some autonomic dysfunction by 204 months • Lab <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Elevated CSF protein concentration ○ Normal (or virtually normal) motor nerve conduction studies, and abnormal sensory nerve conduction studies
<p>Wakerly 2014[136]</p>	<p>All GBS spectrum disorders: mostly symmetric pattern of limb and/or motor cranial-nerve weakness; monophasic disease course with 12 hour to 28 day interval from onset to nadir of weakness followed by a clinical plateau; Alternate diagnosis should be excluded. Supported by antecedent infectious symptoms; presence of distal paraesthesia at or before onset of weakness. CSF albuminocytological dissociation</p> <p>Classic GBS: weakness and areflexia/hyporeflexia in all four limbs; usually starts in legs and ascends but may start in arms; may involve cranial-nerve or respiratory muscles; may have normal or exaggerated reflexes in 10% of cases</p> <p>Miller Fisher Syndrome: ophthalmoplegia, ataxia, areflexia/hyporeflexia and absence of limb weakness. Supported by presence of anti-GQ1b IgG antibodies.</p> <p>Pharyngeal-cervical-brachial weakness: no leg weakness; do have oropharyngeal, neck and arm weakness along with arm areflexia/hyporeflexia. Supported by presence of electrophysiological evidence of neuropathy and presence of anti-GT1a or anti-GQ1b IgG antibodies.</p> <p>Paraparetic GBS: leg weakness with areflexia/hyporeflexia; absence of arm weakness. Supported by electrophysiological evidence of neuropathy.</p> <p>Bilateral facial weakness with paraesthesias: facial weakness and limb areflexia/hyporeflexia in the absence of ophthalmoplegia, ataxia and limb weakness. Supported by electrophysiologic evidence of neuropathy.</p>

	<p>Bickerstaff brainstem encephalitis (BBE): hypersomnolence, ophthalmoplegia and ataxia in the absence of limb weakness. Supported by presence of anti-GQ1b IgG antibodies.</p>
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APPENDIX 3

GBS Risk Factors

3.1 GBS Risk Factors

TABLE 3.1. GBS RISK FACTORS

Category	Risk factors
Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase with increasing age (see incidence section)
Sex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence and incidence of GBS is higher in males, compared to females (Female to male ratio is 09:1) [137]
Genetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In a meta-analysis, TNF-α 308 G/A polymorphism was significantly associated with the risk of GBS in the overall population (GG+GA vs. AA: OR= 0.32, 95%CI= 0.16-0.62; GG vs. AA: OR= 0.36, 95%CI= 0.19-0.68). However, results should be interpreted with caution due to the limited number of studies available. ([138]) • GBS risk reflects polygenic immune susceptibility, with variable associations across populations involving HLA class II alleles, cytokine genes (TNF-α, IL-17), Fcγ receptors, CD1 genes, and innate immune pathways; no single locus is universal. [139] • GBS is marked by immune gene dysregulation rather than fixed genetic defects, with Th1/Th17-skewed cytokine and transcriptomic signatures (e.g. \uparrow TNF-α, IL-17/IL-22, MMP-9; \downarrow regulatory signals) that correlate with subtype and severity and partially normalize after IVIG or plasma exchange. [139]
Pregnancy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preeclampsia was associated with two times the risk of GBS (HR 2.01, 95% CI 1.29 to 3.12). The incidence of GBS in women with preeclampsia was 2.62 per 100 000 person-years. [9] • There is a significant increase in GBS relapse two weeks post-partum due to return of cellular immunity and an increase in delayed type hypersensitivity. [140] • Risk of GBS increases in third trimester and first 2 weeks after delivery. Demyelinating variety of GBS was common in the study population. [141]
Pre-, Peri-, Post-natal condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preeclampsia was associated with two times the risk of GBS (HR 2.01, 95% CI 1.29 to 3.12) [9]
Social/Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No evidence found
Occupation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No evidence found
Season	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A systematic review showed that there was an increased incidence of GBS in the winter on average across published studies, which were most marked in Western countries. However, there were significant geographical differences with a reduced winter incidence in the Indian subcontinent and Latin America, possibly associated with regional differences in the seasonality of prodromal illnesses. [142] • More than half of the cases occurred in summer and winter, in a retrospective observational study conducted in Peru.[143]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In a large cohort in the US, incidence rate was 15% higher in winter and spring compared with summer. [16]
Geo-location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prevalence of GBS type varies geographically: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AIDP: up to 90% of cases in North America and Europe versus 22-46% of cases in China, Japan, Bangladesh, Mexico[1, 4] AMAN/AMSAN: 30-65% of cases in China, Japan, Bangladesh, Mexico; about 5% of cases in North America and Europe[4] MF variant: more prevalent in eastern Asia; overall about 5% of all GBS cases but up to 20% of cases in Taiwan, 25% of cases in Japan [1, 4]
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No evidence found
Diet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No evidence found
Behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nitrous oxide (N2O) abuse may lead to GBS.[144, 145] Incidence of GBS after recreational N2O use in 20–25-year-olds was 2.47 [0.64; 4.30] per 100,000 persons.[146]
Comorbidity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Malignancy, especially Hodgkin’s and other lymphomas [1] Even though Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) has been associated with the development of GBS,[147, 148] it is rare. [149] Fulminant GBS may be a severe neuropsychiatric manifestation of systemic lupus erythematosus.[150] Immune-mediated disorders were associated with six times the risk of GBS (HR 6.57, 95% CI 3.58 to 12.04) and rheumatological disorders with seven times the risk (HR 7.23, 95% CI 3.21 to 16.28) [9] Few studies have considered diabetes as a risk factor for GBS. In a recent Danish nationwide population-wide study, diabetes was found amongst the commonest co-morbidities diagnosed within the previous 5 months prior to GBS (O.R. 1.5, after adjustment for infection and surgery). Several other studies have found diabetes as a risk factor of severe prognosis in GBS. [151]
Injury	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prior surgery has been reported as a trigger for GBS in reviews [152, 153] case series [154, 155] and case reports [156-159] Published risk estimates for GBS post-surgery include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Levison et al[160] utilized the Danish National Patient Hospital Registry to show an increased risk of GBS within 5 months of a surgical procedure: Odds Ratio 2.2 (95% Confidence Interval 1.8-2.7); The risk was highest within 1 month of surgery (OR 3.7; 95% CI 2.6-5.2). The analysis controlled for the impact of coexisting morbidity as well as prior infection. Rudant et al[161] estimated the risk of GBS following surgery in a large French population-based study, controlling for antecedent infection during the post-op period while in hospital. Overall, there was an increased risk after surgery (OR 1.5; 95% CI 1.3-1.9); They quantified the increased risk associated with bone surgery (OR 2.8; 95% CI 1.7-4.6) and gastrointestinal organ surgery (OR 2.4; 95% CI 1.3-4.2).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sipila et al [82] estimated the incidence and triggers of adult onset GBS in Southwest Finland from 2004 through 2013. The risk of GBS after surgery was 1.25 cases/100,000 surgeries. They compared the rate of GBS during the 6 weeks after surgery and compared it to the background incidence of GBS in the population. The relative risk following surgery was 6.28 (95% CI 4.15-9.47). ○ Gensicke et al [162] did a retrospective study of GBS in Basel University hospitals (one pediatric). 6 of 63 cases occurred within 6 weeks after surgery. Of these 4 had no other risk factors for GBS. The relative risk for GBS within 6 weeks of surgery relative to the general population was 13.1 (95% CI 5.68-30.3). They calculated an attributable risk of 4.1 GBS cases per 100,000 surgeries. ● Huang et al[163] did a systematic review for GBS cases following trauma. The study was purely descriptive with 136 cases found in 94 publications. 121 followed injury and/or surgery; 13 followed intracranial hemorrhage and 2 after heatstroke. The study did not distinguish the impact of injury versus surgery as a prior risk factor.
<p>Infection</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Antecedent diarrheal or respiratory illness reported in 2/3 of cases BC CD, Esposito 2016, Willison 2016, Sejvar 2011, Yuki 2012 [2-4] ● Arboviruses: GBS can occur with arbovirus infections [164] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Chikungunya: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Neuro-Chikungunya is a severe form of chikungunya fever, with GBS as a frequent diagnosis. [165] Increase in GBS cases have been reported during chikungunya fever outbreak.[166] ○ In a meta-analysis, GBS was the most frequently analyzed type of neurological manifestation, with 70.5 % of studies describing it in association with CHIKV positivity. However, due to the absence of control cases in the studies, it was not possible to estimate any potential association between GBS and CHIKV.[167] ○ Dengue: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Although rare, neurological complications of Dengue due to autoimmune reaction include GBS. [168-170] ○ In endemic areas, dengue infection should be tested as a possible etiological agent in cases of GBS.[171] ○ Zika: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Zika virus infection (ZIKV) has been linked to neurological complications like GBS.[172](Mohite 2020)[173] Several studies have been conducted looking at the association between ZIKV and GBS. ○ Several studies have found a higher incidence of GBS during the ZIKV outbreaks, compared to the before period[174], association with ZIKV (41.9 cases per 10,000 ZIKV) [175] suspected (OR: 3.0, 95% CI: 1.1–8.6) [41]or probable Zika virus disease (OR: 4.6, CI: 1.1–19.0)[41]. Studies have reported series of patients who reported GBS after ZIKV. [176, 177] In Latin America and the Caribbean, GBS increased 2.6 (95% CI 2.3–2.9) times during 2015–2016 ZIKV epidemic. [178] A mathematical inference framework estimated that 2.0 (95% credible interval 0.5–4.5) reported GBS cases may occur per 10,000 ZIKV.[179]

- However, one meta-analysis found insufficient evidence that ZIKV causes GBS (OR 1.57, 95% CI: 0.86–2.86)[180] whereas others showed significant association when controls were enrolled from hospital (OR: 55.8, 95% CI: 17.2-181.7) and no significant association when controls were enrolled at random from the same community or household (OR: 2.0, 95% CI: 0.8-5.4)[181]
- **Campylobacter jejuni:** A globally prevalent gastrointestinal pathogen[182], has the strongest association with GBS. The pathogenesis is based on molecular mimicry between the *C. jejuni* cell wall lipo-oligosaccharide and peripheral nerve gangliosides. The risk of GBS varies with the *C. jejuni* strain. In China ST-2993 has been strongly linked with GBS and large outbreaks with this strain occurred in Peru in 2019 and 2020. [183] Several studies have estimated the incidence of campylobacter-associated GBS:
 - US case-control studies estimate cumulative incidence of 33-95 GBS cases/100,000 *Campylobacter sp.* Infections[184-187]
 - European cohort studies have found a slightly lower incidence of 19-33 GBS cases/100,000 *Campylobacter sp* infections[188-191]
 - Scallan Walter et al [192] used US administrative health data to do a cohort study linking a health care encounter for *campylobacter sp.* infection (ICD-9-CM code 008.43) with a subsequent principal diagnosis of GBS (ICD-9-CM code of 357.0) that onset within 8 weeks following the *campylobacter sp.* infection. They found 21.5 probable GBS cases per 100,000 infections (95% CI 3.7-86.6). They estimated that at a minimum *campylobacter sp.* infections account for 5% (95% CI <1 – 21%) of GBS cases in the US.
 - Halpin et al [193] took advantage of a prospective CDC surveillance for GBS following 2009-2010 pandemic influenza vaccine to do a secondary analysis linking campylobacter infection to subsequent (within 42 days) GBS cases (confirmed as meeting Level 1, 2 or 3 of the Brighton CD).They estimated a range of 32.8-49.2 cases of GBS / 100,000 *Campylobacter sp.* infections which accounted for 8-12% of GBS cases in US.
 - Sharma et al [194] prospectively enrolled 50 GBS cases from a tertiary care hospital in India and matched them (age and sex) to 40 healthy controls. Cases and controls that were seropositive for both IgG and IgM to Campylobacter were considered to have confirmed recent infections. Recent infection was confirmed in a significantly higher proportion of cases (15/50; 30%) than controls (3/40; 8%); p<0.005.
- **COVID=19:** Even though study found no relationship between GBS and COVID-19 infections,[195], other studies report a relationship:
 - In a multi-national cohort study, meta-analysis showed that patients with COVID-19 had a standardized incidence ratio of 6.79 (95%CI: 5.03 – 9.17) compared to pre-pandemic period. [196]
 - A meta-analysis showed that, COVID-19 appears to be associated with an increased likelihood of GBSs and with demyelinating GBS variants in particular (OR 3.27, 95% CI 1.32%–8.09%; I² = 0%).[197]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The relative frequency of GBS among emergency departments patients, in Spain, was higher in COVID than non-COVID patients (OR=6.30, 95%CI:3.18–12.5), as was the standardized incidence (OR = 13.5, 95% CI:9.87–18.4).[198] ● Cytomegalovirus: CMV infection is considered the second most common infection preceding GBS.[14] The incidence of CMV-GBS has been estimated to be between 0.6 and 2.2 cases per 1000 cases of primary CMV infection in a cohort study. [199] ● Enterovirus: GBS has been observed in EV71[200] and EV-D68 [201] infections. ● Epstein-Barr virus: EBV infection can lead to GBS, mainly caused by an abnormal immune cross response, resulting in peripheral nerve axonal injury and demyelination. [202] ● Influenza: GBS has been reported in individuals with influenza virus infection[203], including the H1N1 2009 pandemic, [204, 205] and may even be a triggering agent [206] ● Helicobacter pylori: A meta-analysis showed a strong association between GBS and the presence of <i>H pylori</i> antibodies, especially in CSF. Anti-<i>H pylori</i> IgG were significantly more prevalent in GBS patients compared to controls, in both CSF (OR: 42.45 95% CI: 9.66-186.56) and serum (OR: 2.31, 95% CI: 1.30-4.11)[207] ● Hepatitis E: GBS cases have been reported secondary to HEV. [208] There is mixed data on the strength of association between HEV and GBS. From strong association of HEV with neurological disorders (with primarily dominant peripheral nerve involvement, most commonly manifested as GBS)[209, 210], to probable causal relationship [211, 212] to rare GBS in acute HEV patients in a cohort study. [213] ● HIV: Cases of GBS/Miller Fisher have been reported in HIV-positive individuals. [214] ● Japanese Encephalitis: Presentation of GBS caused by Japanese encephalitis virus is uncommon, but clusters of GBS cases were observed in China and India. [215, 216] ● MPOX: Case of a confirmed MPOX infection has been reported in a patient presenting with GBS.[217] ● Oropouche: GBS cases have been described in oropouche virus disease [218] with an increase in GBS incidence during oropouche disease outbreak [219]. Oropouche virus should be recognized as a potential pathogen in cases of fever associated with GBS [220] ● Scrub Typhus: A case of GBS has been reported after Scrub Typhus, after the individual received the mRNA-1273 COVID19 vaccine.[221] ● Toxoplasmosis: GBS or Miller Fisher syndrome have been reported after Toxoplasmosis [222] ● West Nile Virus: GBS can be associated with West Nile virus infection. [223, 224] ● Zoster Virus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ VZV infection may trigger GBS [225, 226] and the prognosis in zoster-associated GBS appears to be poorer than other cases.[227]
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In a population-based study, the adjusted hazard of GBS during the follow-up period was 18.37 times greater (95CI: 10.22–33.01) for patients with herpes zoster than for those without.[228] ○ The risk of GBS following herpes zoster increased during 1-42 days as compared to 100-365 days, with a rate ratio of 6.3 (95% CI, 1.8–21.9) for those 18–64 years and 4.1 (95% CI, 1.9–8.7) for those ≥65 years. [229]
<p>Medication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Transfusion was associated with three times the risk of GBS (HR 3.58, 95% CI 1.83 to 6.98)[9]. ● Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICI), monoclonal antibodies used in cancer therapy, have been reported to cause GBS and other neurologic disorders. The evidence is based primarily on case reports [230-232] and pharmacovigilance system signals [233-236] A follow-up study involving 1185 cancer patients treated with immune checkpoint inhibitors in one of two European university centers identified 4 (0.33% of treated patients) confirmed GBS cases.[237] ● In addition to immune checkpoint inhibitors other drugs, including monoclonal antibodies, immunomodulators, chemotherapeutic agents, antibiotics, anti-epileptics and anticholesterolemic agents have been linked temporally to GBS. The largest pharmacovigilance study to date was done by the US FDA based on reports to the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS) from 2004 to 2024. [234] Reports were ascertained with MedDRA PTs including Guillain-Barre Syndrome, acute inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy, Miller Fisher syndrome, acute motor axonal neuropathy and acute motor-sensory axonal neuropathy. 1869 reports of GBS were identified out of 17,785,793 reported adverse events. A disproportionality analysis identified signals for 19 drugs. The significant Reporting Odds Ratios (ROR) [95% Confidence Interval] were: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Brentuximab vedotin (monoclonal antibody): 32.29 [21.22-49.11] ○ Efalizumab (monoclonal antibody): 25.85 [14.29-46.74] ○ Atezolizumab (immune checkpoint inhibitor – monoclonal antibody): 15.18 [11.69-19.72] ○ Ipilimumab (immune checkpoint inhibitor – monoclonal antibody): ○ Bortezomib (immunomodulator): 10.37 [7.85-13.71] ○ Pembrolizumab (immune checkpoint inhibitor – monoclonal antibody): 9.76 [7.79-12.23] ○ Tacrolimus (immunomodulator): 7.98 [6.56-9.7] ○ Oxaliplatin (chemotherapeutic agent): 7.87 [6.02-10.3] ○ Nivolumab (immune checkpoint inhibitor – monoclonal antibody): 7.84 [6.41-9.57] ○ Levofloxacin (antibiotic): 7.55 [5.76-9.9] ○ Cyclophosphamide (chemotherapeutic agent): 6.52 [4.65-9.14]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cytarabine (chemotherapeutic agent): 5.22 [3.24-8.4] ○ Vedolizumab (monoclonal antibody): 5.2 [3.13-8.63] ○ Simvastatin (anticholesterolemic agent): 5.04 [3.47-7.31] ○ Ciprofloxacin (antibiotic): 4.84 [3.62-6.47] ○ Mycophenolate mofetil (immunomodulator): 3.88 [2.78-5.42] ○ Ustekinumab (monoclonal antibody): 3.82 [2.82-5.15] ○ Hydroxychloroquine (antimalarial): 3.5 [2.43-5.05] ○ Clozapine (anti-epileptic): 3.27 [2.21-4.84] <p>The authors acknowledged several limitations to the analysis: FAERS is a spontaneous reporting system and subject to bias; GBS cases were not validated against a standard case definition; other risk factors for GBS like prior infection or surgery were not known. Thus the observed associations are not conclusive and would need further research to substantiate.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) T-cell therapy has been linked to GBS based on case reports and pharmacovigilance data [238-240]
Toxin /Toxic exposure	No evidence found
<p>Vaccine <i>Note: The information in this row is a summary of what is known. Tables 3.2 to 3.7 contain detailed information on evidence linking various vaccines to GBS.</i></p>	<p>COVID-19 Vaccines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overall, evidence linking COVID-19 vaccines and GBS is mixed and strongly platform-dependent. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Adenovirus-vector COVID-19 vaccines consistently show an increased risk of GBS across SCCS, cohort, and pharmacovigilance studies, particularly after the first dose, with relative incidence or incidence rate ratios typically around 2.4–2.6 within 1–42 days post-vaccination.[241-243] Observed-to-expected analyses similarly demonstrate elevated risk, with pooled O/E estimates of approximately 2.2–3.4 across EU and U.S. datasets, and higher estimates reported for Janssen vaccines (Ad26.COVS.2.S) in some settings.[244-247] ○ mRNA COVID-19 vaccines, generally show no increased risk and, in several large SCCS, cohort, and pharmacovigilance analyses, are associated with reduced risk of GBS, with adjusted RI, OR or O/E ratios commonly below 1.0 (approximately 0.3–0.7).[242-244, 246-249] One SCCS study reported elevated relative incidence following Moderna vaccines (mRNA-1273) (dose 1: 6.83 [2.14–21.85]; dose 2: 7.41 [2.35–23.38]) with wide confidence intervals, representing an outlier against the broader evidence base.[250] ○ Inactivated COVID-19 vaccines, such as CoronaVac, show no increased risk, while mixed or unspecified COVID-19 vaccine groupings show variable signals, including reduced reporting odds compared with other viral vaccines.[243, 251-253]

Influenza Vaccines

- Evidence for an association between seasonal influenza vaccines and GBS is inconsistent. Across cohort, SCCS, and case–control studies, some analyses report small increases in risk (relative risks or incidence ratios around 1.4–2.0), while others show no association or reduced risk following vaccination.[254-257]
- Pandemic influenza vaccines demonstrate a clearer signal. The 2009–2010 H1N1 pandemic vaccines are associated with a modestly increased risk of GBS, with relative risks or relative incidence estimates typically around 1.9–2.4 within 42 days, and higher estimates reported for monovalent H1N1 formulations. Adjuvanted H1N1 vaccines generally do not show increased risk.[258-261]
- The 1976 A/New Jersey (swine influenza) vaccine was associated with a substantially elevated risk of GBS, with a relative risk of 9.2 (95% CI 8.2–10.3) based on large U.S. surveillance data and an attributable risk of approximately 1 case per 100,000 vaccinated.[1, 6, 262]
- Post-licensure observational studies of influenza vaccines show mixed evidence of an association with GBS, with a case–control study reporting modestly increased odds (adjusted OR ~1.8) and pharmacovigilance analyses reporting elevated but highly variable reporting odds ratios (approximately 2 to >40).[263-265]

Recombinant Zoster Vaccine

- Recombinant zoster vaccine is associated with a small but statistically significant increased risk of GBS in older adults. SCCS and cohort analyses indicate an excess risk concentrated within 42 days post-vaccination, with attributable risk estimates on the order of 3.13 cases per million doses (95% CI 0.62–5.64) and 0.93 per 100,000 person-years (95% CI 0.18–1.68) and RR 2.34 (95% CI 1.01–5.41) during the same risk window.[266]

Respiratory Syncytial Virus Vaccines

- RSV vaccines were associated with an increased incidence of GBS, with an IRR of 2.1 (95% CI 1.5–2.9) within 42 days of vaccination. Higher incidence was reported following RSVPreF (IRR 2.4, 95% CI 1.5–4.0), than following RSVPreF3 (IRR 1.5, 95% CI 0.9–2.2).[267]

Rabies Vaccine

- Rabies vaccine cultured in mammalian brain tissues may induce T cells reactive to myelin basic protein. GBS was observed in about 1 in 7500 suckling mouse brain vaccinees and made up about 7% of all hospitalizations following Semple vaccine.[1, 6]

Other

- Risk window for GBS as a vaccine product related reaction[27]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Inactivated or subunit vaccines –Immune-mediated mechanism for GBS likely similar to ADEM, where recommended risk window for individuals is 2-42 days: for epidemiologic studies 5-28 days for primary analysis, and 2-42 days for secondary analysis. ● Live attenuated vaccines – this should be based on the incubation period for the vaccine strain, adding as above, 5-28 days for primary analysis and 2-42 days for secondary analysis following the end of the incubation period.
Other factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lower TSH, higher Free Thyroxine and Free Thyroxine/Free Triiodothyronine are associated with incidence and severity of GBS. [268] ● Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), a simple indicator of immune function, may be an independent GBS risk factor and predictor of severe functional disability, severe weakness, and short-term prognosis. [269] ● Low levels of Vitamin D are frequent in patients with GBS. [270] ● Cases of GBS have been reported after snake bite.[271, 272] <p>Prior GBS episode</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Genetic or immunological host factors may play an important role in recurrent GBS, since these patients can develop similar symptoms after different preceding infections. Recurrences occur more frequently in patients under 30, with milder symptoms and in MFS.[273] ● TSH was an independent risk factor for recurrent GBS.[274]

Table 3.2 Studies reporting on risk of GBS after vaccination with Measles containing vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group (years)	Number of GBS cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
Case Control studies (n=1)								
Chen, 2020[275]	China	2011 - 2015	Mean: 50.98	7	MMR	Odds ratio compared to controls without vaccination (95% CI)	0.97 (0.41-2.25)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-10 Risk period = 4-42 days
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=2)								
Soriolo, 2024[276]	Italy	2007 - 2022	0-12	1	MMRV	Reporting rate per 10,000 doses administered	0.01	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 1-42 days Vaccinated n = 9510
Patja, 2000[277]	Finland	1982 - 1996	-	2	MMR II	Incidence (95% CI) per 100,000 doses	0.07	Case ascertainment= Clinical information Vaccinated n = 1,800,000 Number of doses = 2,990,000
Other Studies (n=4)								
Bino, 2003[278]	Albania	2000	1-14	1	MR	Rate per million doses	1.15	Case ascertainment= WHO guidelines Number of doses = 867,000
Wang, 2022[279]	Multiple countries	2020	-	-	MR	Pooled rate per million persons (95% CI)*	2.52 (0.19-4.85)	Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 7,909,254 * Meta-analysis
Esteghamati, 2008[124]	Iran	2003 - 2004	5-14	25	MR	Annualized incidence rate per 100,000	0.71	Risk period = 42 days
da Silveira, 1997[42]	Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Columbia	1990 - 1994	9 months - 15 years	97	Measles	Incidence rate per 100,000	0.67	Risk period = 72 days from beginning of 1-month vaccination campaign to 42 days after last day of campaign Vaccinated n = 73,000,000

Table 3.3 Studies reporting on risk of GBS after vaccination with Covid-19 containing vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group (years)	Number of GBS cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=6)								
Wan, 2022[280]	China	2021 - 2022	Mean: 70.40	1	CoronaVac	Incidence of GBS per 100,000 doses	0.09 (95% CI: 0.00-0.50)	Case ascertainment = ICD-9-CM Risk period = 21 day
Yamin, 2023[281]	Israel	2021 - 2022	12+	Booster 1=2	BNT162b2	Risk difference for events per 100,000 people (95% CI)	0.2 (0.0-0.5)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Risk period = 28 days Vaccinated n = 1,073,110
				Booster 2=1			-0.3 (-1.3-0.5)	
Walker, 2022[241]	UK	2020 - 2021	18-105	517	ChAdOx1	Conditional incidence rate ratio (95% CI)	Dose 1: 2.46 (1.82-3.32)	Risk period = 4-42 days Number of doses: ChAdOx1= 7,783,441, BNT162b2=5,729,152
				283	BNT162b2		Dose 2: 1.73 (0.75-3.99)	
Morciano, 2024[250]	Italy	2020 - 2021	Median: 56	Dose 1: 19	BNT162b2	Relative incidence compared to the control window (95% CI)	0.85 (0.49-1.48)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9-CM Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n: BNT162b2 = 10,833,284; mRNA-1273 = 1,706,979; ChAdOx1 = 2,863,950 Number of doses: BNT162b2 = 18,899,505; mRNA-1273 = 3,037,506; ChAdOx1 = 4,520,119
				Dose 2: 30			1.30 (0.80-2.10)	
				Dose 1: 7	mRNA-1273		6.83 (2.14-21.85)	
				Dose 2: 5	7.41 (2.35-23.38)			
				Dose 1: 34	ChAdOx1		6.52 (2.88-14.77)	
				Dose 2: 6	3.56 (0.31-40.29)			
Le Vu, 2023[242]	France	2020 - 2022	Median: 57	Dose 1: 46	ChAdOx1	Relative incidence compared to the control window (95% CI)	2.5 (1.8-3.6)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 1-42 days
				Dose 2: 12	0.86 (0.47-1.6)			
				10	Ad26.COV 2.S		2.4 (1.2-5.0)	
				Dose 1: 14	mRNA-1273		1.2 (0.68-2.1)	
				Dose 2: 35			1.3 (0.84-2.0)	
				Dose 3: 35			0.98 (0.64-1.5)	

				Dose 1: 93	BNT162b2		1.1 (0.91-1.4)	
				Dose 2:107			1.0 (0.83-1.3)	
				Dose 3: 78			0.92 (0.70-1.2)	
Nasreen, 2025[243]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2023	-	24	ChAdOx1	Relative incidence compared to the control window (95% CI)*	2.63 (1.52-4.54)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9, 10, and MedDRA Risk period = 1-42 days * BC LOC 1-4 data reported here. LOC 1-2, and LOC 1-3 data also reported
				4	Ad26.COV 2.S		2.66 (0.77-9.24)	
				14	BNT162b2		0.48 (0.27-0.85)	
				8	mRNA-1273		0.69 (0.33-1.47)	
				1	CoronaVac		0.04 (0.00-0.61)	
Cohort studies (n=14)								
Wong, 2022[282]	China	2021	18+	2	BNT162b2	Cumulative incidence after first dose per 100,000 doses	0.15	Case ascertainment = ICD-9-CM Vaccinated n = 1,308,820
Peng, 2023[283]	Hong Kong	2020 - 2022	Mean: 54.25	12	BNT162b2 , CoronaVac	Hazard Ratio (HR) (95% CI)	1.12 (0.58-2.19)	Vaccinated n = 3,168,131 HR: fully vaccinated vs non-vaccinated
Klein, 2021[284]	USA	2020 - 2021	Mean: 49	-	BNT162b2 , mRNA-1273	Events/million person-years	15.1	Risk period = 21 days Vaccinated n = 6.2 million
Koh, 2021[285]	Singapore	2020 - 2021	Median: 59	2	BNT162b2	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.14	Case ascertainment= BC Vaccinated n = 1,398,074
Tamborska, 2022[286]	UK	2021	Median: 59	67	ChAdOx1	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.15	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-10 Number of doses: ChAdOx1=46 million, BNT162b2= 30 million
				3	BNT162b2		0.01	
Garcia-Grimshaw, 2022[251]	Mexico	2020 - 2021	-	32	BNT162b2	Unadjusted incidence among hospitalized	1.92 (1.36-2.71)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 42 days Number of doses:
				3	mRNA-1273		1.29 (0.44-3.81)	

				37	ChAdOx1 nCoV-19	patients per 1,000,000 doses administered	0.96 (0.70-1.32)	BNT162b2= 16,646,623 mRNA-1273= 2,318,057 ChAdOx1 nCoV-19= 38,516,372 Ad5-nCoV= 2,979,697 rAd26-rAd5= 5,812,864 Ad26.CoV2.S= 1,035,859 CoronaVac= 14,532,954
				5	Ad5-nCoV		1.68 (0.72-3.93)	
				6	rAd26-rAd5		1.03 (0.47-2.25)	
				4	Ad26.CoV2.S		3.86 (1.50-9.93)	
				10	CoronaVac		0.69 (0.37-1.27)	
Shasha, 2022[287]	Israel	2020 - 2021	<18-65+	1	BNT162b2	Incidence following first dose 100,000 person-years	0.4	Number of doses = 233,159
Jeong, 2024[56]	South Korea	2009 - 2019	0-80+	162	COVID-19	Adjusted incidence rate per 100,000, 2019* (95% CI)	1.21 (1.12-1.31)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 * Additional data available
Takalani, 2024[288]	South Africa	2021 - 2022	Median: 44	1	Ad26.COV2.S	Observed/expected ratio following second dose (95% CI)	2.02 (0.05-1.25)	Case ascertainment= ICH-GCP seriousness criteria Risk period = 28 days Vaccinated n = 240,888
Garcia-Grimshaw, 2021[289]	Mexico	2020 - 2021	-	7	BNT162b2	Observed incidence per 100,000 doses administered	0.18	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 30 days Vaccinated n = 3,890,250
Faksova, 2024[290]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2023	-	-	ChAdOx1	Observed/expected ratio (95% CI)*	Dose 1: 2.49 (2.15-2.87)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 99,068,901 * Data on dose 3 and 4 available
					BNT162b2		Dose 2: 0.73 (0.54-0.96)	
					mRNA-1273		Dose 1: 0.90 (0.79-1.03)	
							Dose 2: 0.69 (0.60-1.15)	
							Dose 1: 0.95 (0.65-1.34)	
							Dose 2: 0.84 (0.60-1.15)	
Abdel-Qader, 2022[291]	Jordan	2021	> 18	12	BNT162b2, BBIBP-CorV,	Incidence of GBS per 100,000 persons vaccinated	1.8	Risk period = 14 days Vaccinated n = 658,428 Number of doses = 1,032,430

					ChAdOx1 nCoV-19, Sputnik V			
Han, 2023[292]	South Korea	2020 - 2022	Mean: 54.03	22	ChAdOx1	Incidence of GBS/MFS per 100,000 person- years	7.1	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 60 days (Data for 61- 180 days also available)
				15	BNT162b2		3.6	
				3	mRNA- 1273		4.4	
				1	Ad26.COV 2.S		3	
Choi, 2024[293]	South Korea	2021	Mean: 48.3	15	ChAdOx1	Incidence rate ratio compared to mRNA vaccines	0.20 (0.06-0.69)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 42 days
Case Control studies (n=1)								
Bishara, 2023[248]	Israel	2021 - 2022	Mean: 56.3	8	BNT162b2	Multivariate odds ratio compared to matched controls without GBS (95% CI)	0.41 (0.17-0.96)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Risk period = 42 days
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=15)								
Lloyd, 2022[294]	USA	2020 - 2022	12-64	-	mRNA127 3	Rate Ratio comparing incidence of observed events compared to adjusted historical background rates	Optum: 1.4 Healthcore: 0.85 CVS: 1.34	Case ascertainment= ICD-10-CM Number of doses: mRNA1273= 2,566,689 BNT162b2= 5,023,855 Ad26.COV2.S = 244,448
				-	BNT162b2		Optum: 1.21 Healthcore: 1.11 CVS: 1.05	
				-	Ad26.COV 2.S		Optum: 6.53 Healthcore: 8.53 CVS: 2.31	
Singh, 2022[295]	USA	2021	Mean: 50.7	64	BNTb262	Frequency following vaccine (per million doses)	0.5	Case ascertainment= MedDRA Vaccinated n = 141,208 Number of doses = 239,970,000
				67	mRNA- 1273		0.64	

				30	JNJ-78436735		3.65	
Urdaneta, 2023[249]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2022	<2 - ≥ 75	683	mRNA-1273	Observed-to-expected ratios (95% CI)	0.38 (0.35-0.42)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA Risk period = 21 days Number of doses = 772,908,958
Amarasinghe, 2023[296]	Multiple countries	2021 - 2022	-	172	AZD1222	Reporting rate per 1 million doses administered	4.1	-
Kim, 2024[253]	South Korea	2020 - 2023	12 -17	94	COVID-19	Adjusted ROR (95% CI) vs all other vaccines	0.64 (0.44-0.92)	Vaccinated n = 80,018
Kim, 2023[297]	South Korea	2020 - 2021	≥ 18	T2DM: 13	COVID-19	Calculated rate per 100,000 individuals	190.3	Vaccinated n Type 2 Diabetic = 6,829 Non-diabetic = 20,487
				Non-diabetic:19			92.7	
Frontera, 2022[244]	USA	2021	Median: 50	115	BNT162b2	Observed/expected ratio (95% CI)	0.74 (0.61-0.88)	Vaccinated n: BNT162b2= 90,063,644 mRNA-1273= 72,705,161 AD26.COV2.S= 11,465,768 Number of doses: BNT162b2= 166,981,930 mRNA-1273= 128,084,622 AD26.COV2.S= 11,606,202
				87	mRNA-1273		0.69 (0.55-0.85)	
				61	AD26.COV2.S		3.06 (2.34-3.93)	
Atzenhoffer, 2022[246]	Multiple countries	2021	Median: 57	EU=337	mRNA	Observed-to-expected ratio reported to VigiBase	0.35 (0.31-0.40)	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days
				USA=869			0.71 (0.65-0.77)	
				EU=434	Adenovirus vector		2.31 (1.95-2.74)	
				USA=170			3.40 (2.48-4.66)	
Guo, 2022[298]	USA	2021	18-64	340	BNT162b2	Proportional reporting ratio, as reported to VAERS	0.31	Case ascertainment= MedDRA Number of doses: BNT162b2= 296,870,831 mRNA-1273= 194,260,394 Ad26.COV2.S= 17,640,334
				243	mRNA-1273		0.21	
				233	Ad26.COV2.S		1.29	

Nosedá, 2021[252]	Multiple countries	2021	<10 - ≥75	632	COVID-19	Reporting odds ratio, compared to receiving other viral vaccines (95% CI)	0.15 (0.13-0.16)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA Vaccinated n = 808,906
Takuva, 2022[245]	South Africa	2021	Median: 42	4	Ad26.COV 2.S	Observed/expected ratio following first dose (95% CI)	5.09 (1.39-13.02)	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 28 days Vaccinated n = 477,234
Ferrara, 2022[299]	Italy	2021	-	1	Vaxzevria	Calculated rate per 100,000 individuals	0.34	Risk period = 12 days Number of doses = 295,900
Woo, 2023[300]	USA	2021 - 2022	Median: 46	309	Ad26.COV 2.S	Reporting rate of GBS following Ad.26.COV2.S vaccination	18.16	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = Vaccinated n = 67,995 Number of doses = 17,018,042
Nikitina, 2023[301]	USA	2020 - 2022	0-17	29s	Pfizer & Moderna	Calculated rate per 100,000 individuals	0.05	Number of doses = Over 57 million
Kim, 2022[302]	Multiple countries	2020 – 2021	-	233	BNT162b2 , mRNA-1273	Adjusted reporting odds ratio in VigiBase compared to all other reports (95% CI)	0.20 (0.03-1.46)	-
Other Studies (n=3)								
Wong, 2023[303]	USA	2020 - 2022	≥ 65	53	mRNA-1273	RR observed vs expected	0.86	Risk period = 42 days Number of doses mRNA-1273 = 15,761,718 BNT162b2=15,896,042 Ad26 COV2.S = 576,698
				69	BNT162b2		1.14	
				<11	Ad26 COV2.S		3.85	
Meo, 2024[247]	Multiple countries	-	-	2076	BNT162b2 , mRNA-1273~	Pooled Observed/Expected ratio (95% CI)	0.37 (0.23-0.50)	Number of doses = ~1,237,638,401 ^193,535,249 * Meta-analysis
				1630	ChAdOx1n CoV-19/ ChAdOx1-		2.17 (1.50-2.85)	

					S, Ad.26.CO V2. S^			
Wallace, 2023[304]	USA	2020 - 2021	18-49*	-	Ad26.COV 2.S	Cases per million doses	Female = 5	Risk period = 42 days * Additional age groups available
							Male = 6	

Table 3.4 Studies reporting on risk of GBS after vaccination with Influenza containing vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group (years)	Number of GBS cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=16)								
Shi, 2024[305]	USA	2022 - 2023	-	134	Seasonal quadrivalent	Incidence rate ratio in the seasonality-adjusted and PPV-based imputation analysis (95% CI)	0.90 (0.56-1.42)	Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses = 12.7 million
				79	High-dose		0.89 (0.49-1.64)	
				38	Adjuvanted		0.79 (0.33-1.94)	
Lee, 2011[306]	USA	2009 - 2010	6 months - ≥65 years	15	H1N1 Monovalent	Log-likelihood ratio* (critical value of LLR)	1.5612 (3.6838)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses: Pandemic H1N1= 1,345,663; Influenza - Seasonal trivalent= 267,715 * Automated
				1	H1N1 Live attenuated		0.0271 (3.7235)	
				23	TIV		0.1407 (2.86121)	
Hughes, 2006[120]	UK	1992 - 2000	0-100	3	Influenza	Adjusted Relative Risk (95% CI)	0.99 (0.32-3.12)	Case ascertainment = Diagnostic codes Risk period = 42 days

Stowe, 2008[307]	UK	1990 - 2005	<8 - 88+	12	Seasonal influenza	Relative Incidence (95% CI)	0.76 (0.41-1.40)	Case ascertainment = Clinical symptoms Risk period = 0-90 days
Andrews, 2011[308]	UK	2009 - 2010	0-70+	9	Pandemic H1N1	Relative incidence estimate (95% CI)	1.05 (0.37-2.24)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-10 Risk period = 42-days
Tokars, 2012[309]	USA	2009 - 2010	0.5-≥65	-	Pandemic H1N1	Attributable risk per million doses using the variable-window relative risk	1.5 (0.3-3.4)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 1-42 days; for fixed control window: 43-84 days; for variable control window
					Seasonal influenza		1.9 (0.7-3.9)	
Grave, 2020[310]	France	2010 - 2014	Mean: 73.0	140	Influenza	Adjusted incidence rate ratio compared to the control period (95% CI; p Value)	1.10 (0.89-1.37; p=0.38)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 42 days
Lee, 2020[311]	South Korea	2014 - 2016	≥65	4-7 days: 3	TIV	Overall incidence rate ratio compared to the control window (95% CI)	0.83 (0.26-2.58)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 42 days. 90 days
				8-14 days: 6			0.94 (0.42-2.12)	
				15-42 days: 21			0.86 (0.56-1.34)	
				43-90 days: 39			0.89 (0.64-1.25)	
Juurink, 2006[254]	Canada	1993 - 2004	≥18	51	Influenza	Relative incidence compared to the 20-43 week control window (95% CI)	1.47 (1.07-2.00)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9, ICD-10 Risk period = 2-7 weeks
Arya, 2019[312]	USA	2015 - 2017	65+	-	Seasonal influenza	Attributable risk per million vaccinations using chart-confirmed+imputed analysis (95% CI)	2015-16: 0.85 (-0.75-2.38)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 1-42 days
					High-dose influenza		2016-17: 0.43 (-1.24-2.06)	
							2015-16: 2.15 (-0.08-4.10)	
							2016-17: 0.71 (-1.5-2.8)	
							2015-16: -0.74 (-2.98-1.6)	

					Standard influenza		2016-17: -0.12 (-2.75-2.55)	
Perez-Villar, 2019[313]	USA	2017 - 2018	Median: 74	-	Influenza	Attributable risk (per million vaccinations) using claims identified data (95% CI)	8-21 days: 0.22 (-0.56-0.97) 1-42 days: 0.08 (-1.55-1.7)	Case ascertainment= ICD9, ICD10 Risk period = 8-21 (primary); 1-42 days (secondary) Vaccinated n = 14,169,847
Lloyd, 2025[314]	USA	2023 - 2024	-	93	Any influenza	Adjusted incidence risk ratio in Medicare FFS population compared to the 43–90 day control interval	1.10 (0.74-1.63)	Risk period = 1-42 days
				46	High-dose influenza		1.22 (0.69-2.16)	
				40	Adjuvanted influenza		0.99 (0.55-1.77)	
Romio, 2014[315]	Denmark	2009 - 2010	≤4 - ≥60	-	A(H1N1) pandemic 2009	Relative incidence (95% CI)	4.4 (0.5 to 35.6)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 1-28 days
	Finland						1.0 (0.2-4.6)	
	France						1.3 (0.1-12.6)	
	Netherlands						2.5 (1.0-6.4)	
	Norway						2.2 (0.8-6.1)	
	Sweden						2.7 (0.9-7.8)	
	UK						4.2 (0.4-50.2)	
Prestel, 2014[316]	Germany	2009 - 2010	4-82	19	A(H1N1)	Relative incidence of GBS/Fisher Syndrome (95% CI) compared to the 43–150 day control interval	Monthly adjustment: .19 (0.28-5.01) Seasonal adjustment: 2.85 (1.03-7.90)	Risk period = 1-42 days
Yen, 2022[317]	Taiwan	2003 - 2017	Mean: 75.0	374	Seasonal influenza	Incidence Rate Ratio (95% CI) compared to the 43–150 day control interval	0.92 (0.72-1.17)	Case ascertainment= ICD9, ICD10 Risk period = 1-42 days Vaccinated n = 13,482,122

Ghaderi, 2016[318]	Norway	2009 - 2012	-	8	Adjuvanted influenza A(H1N1) pandemic 2009	Incidence rate ratio (95% CI)	1.31 (0.65-2.66)	Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 1,896,455
Cohort studies (n=16)								
McCarthy, 2013[319]	USA	2005 - 2011	-	6	H1N1	Incidence rate ratio (95% CI) - Self-Controlled Risk Interval (SCRI)	2.00 (0.50-8.00)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses: H1N1 vaccine= 133, 872, TIV vaccine= 189,980 (2009- 2010 season), 185,144 (2010 - 2011 season)
				2009-2010 =11	TIV		1.57 (0.61-4.05)	
				2010-2011 =14			1.00 (0.45-2.23)	
Layton, 2020[320]	USA	2010 - 2016	Mean: 74.7	<11	TIV high-dose	Crude incidence rate	0.01	Number of doses: 38,256
Kawai, 2014[256]	USA	2012 - 2013	>6 months	14	IIV	Relative risk* (95%CI)	0.5 (0.3-0.9)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Number of doses = 2,832,064 *Compared to 1-42 days post-vaccination (control interval)
Nazareth, 2013[321]	UK	2009	Mean: 54.7	1	H1N1 Pandemrix	Standardised incidence ratio (95% CI)	18.11 (0.46-100.89)	Case ascertainment= BC Vaccinated n = 9,143
Moro, 2013[322]	Italy	2009 - 2010	-	-	Focetria	OR (95% CI) vs unvaccinated subjects	1.0 (0.1-7.1)	Vaccinated n = 103,642
Bardage, 2011[323]	Sweden	1998 - 2010	All ages	-	H1N1 Pandemrix	Hazard ratio of GBS* versus those unvaccinated (95%CI)	1.07 (0.66-1.74)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Number of doses = 1,024,019 * Adjusted for age, sex, socioeconomic status, and healthcare consumption
Choe, 2011[324]	South Korea	2003 - 2010	Median: 52	9	Seasonal TIV	Estimated reporting rate per 100,000 doses	0-0.025	Case ascertainment= BC, Korea Advisory Committee on Vaccine Injury Compensation definition

Williams, 2011[325]	USA	2009 - 2010	6 months - 83 years	75	Pandemic H1N1	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.06	Case ascertainment= BC, Clinical Immunization Safety Assessment (CISA) modified (from WHO) causality assessment criteria. Risk period = 8 weeks
Moro, 2012[326]	USA	2010	Median: 71	GBS:4 Miller Fisher: 1	Seasonal TIV high dose	Crude reporting rate per million doses distributed	1.4	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days
Wise, 2012[327]	USA	2009 - 2010	0 - ≥65	67	Pandemic H1N1	Crude incidence of confirmed and probable cases per 100,000 person-years	1.85	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 42 days
				131	Influenza		1.73	
De Wals, 2012[258]	Canada	2009 - 2010	Median: 49	42	Pandemic H1N1	Relative risk using the self-controlled case-series method (95% CI)	1.95 (1.05-3.63)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 1-8 weeks Number of doses = 4.4 million Additional data available
				36			1.67 (0.86-3.23)	
Yih, 2012[328]	USA	2009 - 2010	-	5	H1N1 MIV	IRR from SCRI analysis (95% CI)	SCRI analysis: 2.50 (0.42-15.0)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 70 days Number of doses = 2,880,797
							Case-centered analysis: 1.15 (0.07-18.6)	
Hansen, 2020[329]	USA	2015 - 2016	≥18	0	RIV3 (FluBlok)	Odds ratio compared to IIV3 vaccine (95% CI)	Emergency department or inpatient facility: 0.000 (0.000-16.066)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9, ICD-10 Risk period = 0-41 days Vaccinated n = 21,976
							Outpatient facility: 0.000 (0.000-112.600)	
Langmuir, 1984[330]	USA	1976 - 1977	≥18	504	A/New Jersey/76 (swine influenza)	Relative risk compared to unvaccinated individuals	7.75	Case ascertainment = CDC case definition Risk period = 1-6 weeks Number of doses = 43,327,000
						Estimated rate compared to baseline incidence rates of	5.67	

						unvaccinated individuals (per million vaccinees)		
Hurwitz, 1981[331]	USA	1978 - 1979	≥18	12	IIV3	Incidence (per million person-months)	0.52	Case ascertainment= Neurologist diagnosis based on National Institute of Neurologic and Communicative Disorders and Stroke (NINCDS) Risk period = 1-8 weeks Vaccinated n = ~ 12.56 million
						Relative risk compared to unvaccinated individuals (95% CI)	1.4 (0.7-2.7)	
Roscelli, 1991[332]	USA	1980 - 1988	-	23	Influenza	Incidence per million persons (95% CI)	3.3 (2.0-4.6)	Case ascertainment= Physician diagnosis Risk period = 1 month Vaccinated n = 5,616,000
Case Control studies (n=4)								
Dieleman, 2011[333]	Netherlands	2009 - 2010	≤18- ≥60	104	Pandemic influenza A (H1N1)	Adjusted odds ratio (95% CI) according to timing of vaccination (≤6 weeks or >6 weeks)	≤6 weeks 0.6 (0.1 - 4.4)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = ≤6 weeks or >6 weeks
	Sweden						>6 weeks 0.2 (0.02 - 1.6)	
	UK						≤6 weeks 1.8 (0.3 - 12)	
							>6 weeks 1.3 (0.2 - 8.5)	
Grimaldi-Bensouda, 2011[334]	France	2007 - 2010	Mean: 48.6		All influenza	Adjusted odds ratio (95% CI)*	1.22 (0.45-3.32)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 6 weeks * Data for additional risk periods available
					Seasonal flu	1.30 (0.41-4.12)		
					Influenza A/H1N1	0.92 (0.11-7.55)		
Chen, 2020[275]	China	2011 - 2015	Mean: 50.98	43	Influenza	Odds ratio compared to controls without vaccination (95% CI)	1.03 (0.73-1.45)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-10 Risk period = 4-42 days
	Denmark		0-99	Total: 20	Influenza		1.85 (1.06-3.21)	

Levison, 2022[263]		2002 - 2016		M: 13		CCI - adjusted OR (95% CI)	1.98 (0.98-3.99)	Case ascertainment= National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS) Risk period = 1 month
				F: 7			1.68 (0.68-4.15)	
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=42)								
Vellozzi, 2010[335]	USA	2009 - 2010	<25	99	H1N1	Reporting rates per million vaccinations	0.42	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = 82.4 million
Banzhoff, 2011[336]	Multiple countries	2009 - 2010	Median: 44	22	Inactivat ed H1N1	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses	0.2	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 6 weeks
Moro, 2015[337]	USA	2013 - 2015	18.5	4	Inactivat ed / Flucelvax	Reporting rate of GBS per million doses distributed	0.7	Case ascertainment= BC LOC 1-3, MedDRA Number of doses = ~ 5.6 million
Moro, 2020[338]	USA	2011 - 2019	≥65	61	IIV-HD	Calculated incidence rate, per 100,000 doses	0.054	Case ascertainment= MedDRA Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = 113.1 million
Nakayam, 2007[339]	Japan	1994 - 2004	-	9	Influenza	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.24	Case ascertainment= Ministry of Health and private manufacturer confirmation Number of doses = 38.02 million
Huang, 2012[340]	Taiwan	2009 - 2010	-	19	Pandemi c H1N1	Estimated to expected ratio, 95% CI	0.78 (0.67-1.13)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD9 Number of doses = 5,688,517
Haber, 2015[341]	USA	2013 - 2014	2-17	2	LAIV4	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.012	Case ascertainment= BC or physician diagnosis Number of doses = 12.7 million
Ropero- Álvarez, 2015[342]	Multiple countries	2009 - 2010	-	105	H1N1 pandemi c	Rate per million doses (95% CI)	0.73 (0.59-0.86)	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 144,621,593
Mayet, 2011[343]	France	2009 - 2010	18-56	1	A(H1N1) Pandemr ix	Calculated rate per 100,000	20.35	Vaccinated n = 49,138

GattÃ¡is, 2018[344]	Brazil	2013 - 2017	-	7	TIV	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.004	Number of doses = 158,735,729
Haber, 2016[345]	USA	2013 - 2015	-	12	IIV4	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.017	Number of doses = 70 million
Haber, 2015[346]	USA	2005 - 2012	-	14	LAIV3	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.028	Number of doses = 50 million
Giang, 2024[347]	Canada	2021 - 2022	-	1	SIV	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.006	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 15,605,176
Williams, 2011[325]	USA	2009 - 2010	Median: 38	43	TIV	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.04	Case ascertainment= Modified WHO criteria Number of doses = 105,211,620
Banzhoff, 2011[336]	Multiple countries	2009 - 2010	Median: 44	22	Focetria	Reporting rate among persons vaccinated during the mass vaccination programs (per 100,000 doses)	0.2	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 6 Weeks Number of doses = 12,000,000
Burwen, 2012[348]	USA	2009 - 2010	All ages	78	Seasonal influenza	Relative risk, current vs historical (5 previous influenza seasons), US Medicare population	1.16	Case ascertainment= ICD-9-CM Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses: Influenza= 14,015,101, Pandemic H1N1= 3,283,576
				18	Pandemic H1N1		1.14	
Souayah, 2012[349]	USA	2009	Mean: 46.5	62	Pandemic H1N1	Estimated annual reporting rate of GBS or MFS, per 10 million vaccinated subjects	6.2	Risk period = 6 weeks Number of doses: Pandemic H1N1= 99,366,920 Influenza= 53,708,996
			-	57	Influenza	Rate of occurrence reported to VAERS, per 10 million vaccinations	6.6	

Liang, 2011[350]	China	2009 - 2010	≤ 9 - ≥ 60	8	Influenza A (H1N1)	Incidence rate per 1 million doses	0.01	Case ascertainment= Guideline for Vaccination against Pandemic (H1N1) Influenza for China Risk period = 3 months Number of doses = 89,600,000
Vellozzi, 2010[335]	USA	2009 - 2010	Median: 26	99	Pandemic Influenza	Reporting rate per million vaccinations	<25 years: 0.42	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = 82,400,000
							≥25 years: 1.75	
Souayah, 2011[351]	USA	2006 - 2009	Mean: 16.7	166	Influenza	Annual reporting rate per 10 million treated patients	9.6	Number of doses = approximately 173 million doses
Souayahm, 2009[352]	USA	1990 - 2005	Mean: 47	-	Influenza	Incidence per million vaccinations	0.75	Risk period = 6 weeks
Choe, 2011[353]	South Korea	2009 - 2010	0 - ≥ 65	22	Influenza A (H1N1)	Rate of GBS per 100,000 vaccinations	0.13	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 17,570,000
Vellozzi, 2009[354]	USA	1990 - 2005	≥18	522	Influenza - Seasonal trivalent	Reporting rate per million vaccinations	0.7	Case ascertainment= Coding Symbols for Thesaurus of Adverse Reaction Terms Number of doses = 747,070,979
Fujimori, 2021[264]	USA	2018 - 2019	Mean: 55.7	64	Influenza	Adjusted reporting odds ratio (95% CI), compared to all other vaccines.	3.44 (2.40-4.95)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA
				14	HD-IIV3, SD-IIV3, aIIV3		1.82 (0.99-3.36)	
				47	cIIV4, IIV4, LAIV4, RIV4		5.25 (3.47-7.94)	
				31	HD-IIV3, SD-IIV3, aIIV3, IIV4		1.99 (1.28-3.10)	

				27	ccIIV4		15.00 (9.27-24.20)	
				58	ccIIV4, HD-IIV3, SD-IIV3, aIIV3, IIV4		3.32 (2.29-4.81)	
MMWR, 2010[260]	USA	2009 - 2010	≤24 - ≥25	27	Pandemi c Influen za	Age-adjusted rate ratio per 100,000 person-years	1.77 (1.12-2.56)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 42 days
Moro, 2020[338]	USA	2011 - 2019	Median: 71	69	IIV3-HD	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.68	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = 113.1 million
Lee, 2020[265]	USA	2005 - 2017	-	56	Influenza	Adjusted reporting odds ratio, compared to other vaccines (95% CI)	VAERS: 2.30 (1.74-3.05)	Case ascertainment= MedDRA Risk period = 45 days
	South Korea			17			KAERS: 3.09 (0.83-11.45)	
Bardenheie r, 2016[355]	USA	2009 – 2010	Median: 33	9 6	H1N1 MIV	Incidence rate per million	Civilians: 1.04 Military service: 4.01	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = civilian: 19,163,035, military: 1,757,801
Moro, 2015[337]	USA	2013 - 2015	≥ 18	4	IIV-3	Crude reporting rate per million doses administered	0.7	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 5,600,000
Kim, 2022[302]	Multiple countries	2020 - 2021	-	233	Influenza	Adjusted reporting odds ratio in VigiBase compared to all other reports (95% CI)	48.14 (41.13-56.35)	-
Schoenberg er, 1979[262]	USA	1976 - 1977	11-85	363	A/New Jersey influenza	Relative risks (95% CI)	9.2 (8.2-10.3)	Case ascertainment= Physician's diagnosis and objective evidence of muscle involvement

				209	Monovalent		8.9 (CI not provided)	Risk period = Six-week period
				131	Bivalent		8.1 (CI not provided)	
Greene, 2012[261]	USA	2009 - 2010	-	13	H1N1 MIV	Relative risk, Vaccine Safety Datalink Project (95% CI)	4.4 (1.3-14.2)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses: MIV: 1,480,135 TIV: 1,724,570 * Self-controlled risk interval analysis
				16	H1N1 TIV		1.3 (0.5-3.8)	
Perez-Vilar 2021[356]	USA	2018 - 2019	68-81	Early season: 52	Influenza	Attributable risk (per million vaccinations) claims based	0.82 (-0.74-2.32)	Case ascertainment= BC ICD-9, ICD-10 Risk period = 1-42 days * Self-controlled risk interval analysis
				End of season: 63			0.69 (-0.77-2.11)	
Greene, 2009[357]	USA	2005 - 2008	≥6 months	23	Pandemic Influenza	Relative risk following first dose, 2007-2008	1.37	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = 2,214,335
Chang, 2019[358]	Taiwan	2007 - 2015	Median: 65.19	182	Seasonal trivalent	Odds ratio of vaccination history within 42 days prior hospitalization (95% CI)	1.46 (0.56-3.78)	Risk period = 42 days
Sandhu, 2017[359]	USA	2010 - 2014	Median: 74	-	Influenza	Relative risk among American Medicare population	2010/2011: 1.3	Case ascertainment=ICD-9 Risk period = 0-42
							2011/2012: 0.97	
							2012/2013: 1.07	
							2013/2014: 1	
Haber, 2014[360]	USA	2005 - 2013	18-45	14	LAIV3	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.1	Risk period = 1-73 days Number of doses = 14,221,122
Ropero-Alvarez, 2015[342]	Multiple	2009 - 2010	9 months-79.2 years	105	A[H1N1] pandemic 2009	Rate per million does (95% CI)	0.73 (0.59-0.86)	Case ascertainment = BC Number of doses = 144,600,000

Haber, 2004[361]	USA	1990 - 2003	≥18	501	Influenza	Reporting rate, 2002-2003	0.04	Case ascertainment = Active follow-up, ICD-9
Haber, 2015[341]	USA	2013 - 2014	2-49	2	LAIV4	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.016	Case ascertainment = BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42-day Number of doses = 12,700,000
Lehmann, 2023[257]	Germany	2020 - 2021	≤ 19 - ≥ 80	18	Influenza	Observed vs expected standardised morbidity ratio (95% CI)	0.60 (0.35-0.94)	Case ascertainment = BC Risk period = 3-42 days Number of doses = <15500000
Lasky, 1998[255]	USA	1992 - 1994	18 - 90	19	Influenza	Adjusted Relative Risk (95% CI)	1.7 (1.0-2.8) p=0.04	Case ascertainment = BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 6 weeks Vaccinated n = 273
Other Studies (n=7)								
Burwen, 2010[362]	USA	2000 - 2002	0 - ≥65	122	Influenza - Seasonal trivalent	Incidence rate ratio per 100,000 person-years (95% CI)	1.04 (0.80-1.36)	Case ascertainment = ICD-9-CM Risk period = 0-6 weeks * Controlled observational study
Wang, 2022[279]	Multiple	2020	-	-	Influenza	Pooled rate per million persons (95% CI)*	2.77 (2.47-3.07)	Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 2,006,470,200 * Meta-analysis
Kim, 2015[61]	South Korea	2008 - 2010	-	-	Pandemic Influenza	Relative risk of compared to the reference period without vaccination using a distributed lag model (95% CI)	1.46 (1.26-1.68)	Case ascertainment = BC * Ecologic design
Kaplan, 1982[363]	USA	1979 - 1981	-	1979-80: 7	Influenza	Relative risk compared with other time periods (95% CI)	0.6 (0.45-1.32)	Risk period = up to 8 week * National surveillance
				1980-81: 12			1.4 (0.8-1.76)	
Vellozzi, 2014[364]	USA	2009 - 2010	< 25 - ≥ 65	-	pH1N1	Adjusted incidence Density Ratio,	0.83 (0.63-1.08)	Case ascertainment = BC, ICD-9

						compared to unvaccinated (95% CI)		* Population-based active surveillance
Verity, 2014[365]	UK	2009 - 2011	≤ 16	96	Pandemrix	Observed vs. Expected cases (within 6 months)	3 observed vs 4.4 expected	Case ascertainment= BC * Case coverage design
				1	Celvapan		1 observed vs 0.8 expected	
				2	2010-2011 seasonal flu		2 observed vs 0.6 expected	
Dodd, 2013[259]	Multiple	2009 - 2010	≥6 months	333	H1N1	Relative incidence compared to the non-risk period (95% CI)	Pooled: 2.42 (1.58-3.72) Meta-analytic: 2.09 (1.28-3.42)	Case ascertainment= BC Risk period = 1-42 days

Table 3.5 Studies reporting on risk of GBS after vaccination with HPV containing vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group (years)	Number of GBS cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=1)								
Andrews, 2017[366]	UK	2007 - 2016	11-19	86	HPV4	Relative incidence (95% CI)	1.61 (0.39-6.54)	Risk period = primary: 91 days
				15	HPV2		0.84 (0.3-2.34)	
Cohort studies (n=6)								
Cameron, 2016[367]	UK	2004 - 2014	12-18	M = 2 F = 1	HPV	2012 Incidence ratio (Observed/Expected X 100), 95% CI	M = 118.6 (13.3-428.2) F = 88.9 (1.2-494.5)	Case ascertainment= ICD- 10
Gee, 2011[368]	USA	2009 - 2010	9-26	1	HPV4	Relative risk using historical comparison group	2.1	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses = 183,616

Martin-Merino, 2021[369]	Spain	2002 - 2016	9-18	3	HPV	Incidence rate per million person-years (95% CI)	1.77 (0.25-12.54)	Case ascertainment= ICPC, ICD-9 Risk period = 90 days Vaccinated n = 480,634
Sundaram, 2022[370]	USA	2015 - 2021	9-26	6	HPV9	Ratio vs. comparator vaccines (95% CI)	0.4 (0.1-0.9)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9, ICD-10 Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = 1,835,789
Miranda, 2017[371]	France	2008 - 2013	Mean: 15.0	20	HPV	Incidence rate per 100,000 person years	1.36	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = Several risk intervals
				17	HPV4		1.28	
				2	HPV2		2.89	
Skufca, 2018[372]	Finland	2013 - 2016	11-15	-	HPV2	Overall adjusted hazard ratios (95%CI)	5.31 (0.62-45.39)	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Risk period = 0–180 days, 181–365 days, and >365 days post-vaccination Vaccinated n = 240,605
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=11)								
Phillips, 2020[373]	Australia	2007 - 2017	12-26	5	HPV4	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses	0.05	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Number of doses = ~ 9.4 million
Slade, 2009[374]	USA	2006 - 2008	-	12	HPV4	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses distributed	0.3	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Number of doses = 23,051,336
Dalla Valle, 2024[375]	Italy	-	≥ 9	1*	HPV4	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses	0.15	Risk period = 1-42 days * BC LOC4
Hu, 2021[376]	China	2018 - 2020	-	3	HPV4	Reporting odds ratio (ROR)-1.96SE	0.48	Case ascertainment= ICD- 10 preferred terms
Mauro, 2019[377]	Brazil	2014 - 2016	9-29	2	HPV4	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses	0.1	Case ascertainment=BC
Angelo, 2014[378]	Multiple countries	2007 - 2011	-	14	HPV2	Reporting rate per 100 000 doses	0.048	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days
	UK			-		Rate (95%CI)	0.23 (0.03 - 0.82)	
Souayah, 2011[351]	USA	2006 - 2009	Mean: 16.7	69	Gardasil	Annual reporting rate per 10 million treated patients	80.23	Number of doses = approximately 26 million doses

Slade, 2009[374]	USA	2006 - 2008	13-30	12	HPV4	Reporting ratio 100,000 person-years	0.3	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 6 weeks
Arana, 2018[379]	USA	2009 - 2016	-	14	HPV4	Calculated rate per 100,000	0.023	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 60,461,220
Gee, 2017[380]	USA	2006 - 2015	9-26	Total: 7	HPV4	Incidence rate of prior to medical review, per million (95% CI)	2.52 (1.01-5.20)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9 Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 1,708,075 Number of doses = 2,773,185
				Female: 4			2.10 (0.057-5.39)	
				Male: 3			3.44 (0.71-10.04)	
Mauro, 2019[377]	Brazil	2014 - 2016	Mean: 11.8	2	HPV4	Reporting rate, per 100,000 doses administered	0.1	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 3,390,376
Other Studies (n=2)								
Wang, 2022[279]	Multiple countries	2020	-	-	HPV	Pooled rate per million persons (95% CI)	2.44 (0.97-3.91)	Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 34,900,559 * Meta-analysis
Deceuninck, 2018[381]	Canada	1999 - 2014	7- 17	100	HPV4	Adjusted relative risk (95% CI)	0.81 (0.29-2.26)	Risk period = 8 weeks * Ecological

Table 3.6 Studies reporting on risk of GBS after vaccination with Pneumococcal containing vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group (years)	Number of GBS cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=1)								
Yoon, 2024[382]	South Korea	2022 - 2023	≥65	-	PPSV23	IRR (95% CI) (adjusted by age)	0.27 (0.06-1.17)	Case ascertainment = ICD-10 Risk period = 28 days
Cohort studies (n=1)								
Tseng, 2018[383]	USA	2011 - 2015	≥65	4	PCV13	Unadjusted relative incidence (95% C) comparing to PPSV23	0.37 (0.11-1.22)	Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses: PCV13= 313,136 PPSV23= 232,591
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=3)								

Oliveira, 2025[384]	USA	2021 - 2023	Median: 65	11	PCV20	Reporting rate per million doses distributed	0.5	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Number of doses = 20,579,720
Haber, 2016[385]	USA	2012 - 2015	≥19	11	Prevnar 13	Reporting rate per million doses	0.7	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = ~ 16 million
Stowe, 2008[307]	UK	1990 - 2005	<8 - 88+	1	Pneumo coccal	Relative Incidence (95% CI)	0.61 (0.08-4.42)	Case ascertainment = Review of patient profiles for clinical symptoms and free-text comments Risk period = 0-90 days

Table 3.7 Studies reporting on risk of GBS after vaccination with Other vaccines, by study type

Author, year	Location	Study Years	Age Group (years)	Number of GBS cases	Specific Vaccine	Risk Estimate	Risk estimate value	Relevant Additional Study Details
SCCS (n=2)								
Goud, 2021[266]	USA	2017 - 2020	Mean: 74.8	24	RZV	PPV-adjusted attributable risk (95% CI)	Per million doses: 3.13 (0.62-5.64)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9, ICD-10 Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 2,113,758
							Per 100,000 person years: 0.93 (0.18-1.68)	
Fry, 2025[267]	USA	2023 - 2025	Median: 74	102	RSV	Incidence rate ratio compared to control	2.1 (1.5-2.9)	Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses = 4,746,518
				51	RSVPreF3		1.5 (0.9-2.2)	

				51	RSVPreF	period of 43-90 days (95% CI)	2.4 (1.5-4.0)	
Cohort studies (n=5)								
Yih, 2009[386]	USA	2005 - 2008	10-64	4	DTaP	Relative risk*	1.6	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Risk period = 1 to 42 days * Compared to background incidence during 2000–2004
Souayah, 2012[387]	USA	1990 - 2009	-	189	Combine d HAV HBV	Annual reporting rate of GBS-MSF reported to VAERS (per 100,000 vaccinations), 2005*	0.29	Case ascertainment= ICD-9 Risk period = 2-6 weeks * Data from other years also available
Goud, 2021[266]	USA	2017 - 2020	Mean: 74.8	15	RZV	Rate ratio compared to ZVL vaccine adjusted for age and sex (95% CI)	2.34 (1.01-5.41)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-9, ICD-10 Risk period = 42 days Vaccinated n = 849,397
Nelson, 2022[388]	USA	2018 - 2019	≥50	6	RZV	RR, compared with historical ZVL recipients (95% CI)	1.56 (0.18-18.62)	Case ascertainment= ICD codes validated by medical record review Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses = 647,833
Safranek, 1991[389]	USA	1976 - 1977	≥18	Michigan: 24	A/New Jersey/8/76 (swine flu)	Attributable risk	8.6	Case ascertainment = ICD-8 and an Expert Neurology Group Risk period = 6 weeks Number of doses = 2,235,994
				Minnesota : 21			9.69	
Case Control studies (n=3)								
Lai, 2015[390]	USA	2006 - 2014	Median: 65	25	Herpes Zoster	Odds ratio (95% CI); p-value for cases vs controls	0.73 (0.46-1.2); 0.18	-
Chen, 2020[275]	China	2011 - 2015	Mean: 50.98	58	HBV	Odds ratio compared to controls without vaccination (95% CI)	0.96 (0.70-1.23)	Case ascertainment= BC, ICD-10 Risk period = 4-42 days
				25	HAV		0.94 (0.60-1.46)	
				31	Varicella-zoster		0.80 (0.57-1.15)	

				31	Rabies		0.87 (0.58-1.30)	
				7	DTaP		0.93 (0.43-2.12)	
				8	Japanese encephalitis		1.09 (0.46-2.41)	
				15	Meningococcal ACWY		0.91 (0.53-1.58)	
De Wals, 2008[391]	Canada	-	-	1	Meningococcal C	O/E ratio after 1 st dose (95% CI)	0.36 (0.02-2.07)	Case ascertainment= BC, icd-9 Risk period = 8 weeks Number of doses = 1,428,463
Pharmacovigilance Studies (n=14)								
Moro, 2016[392]	USA	1990 - 2015	Median: 32	4	Imovax Rabies	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.1	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Number of doses = 3.8 million
Kuno-Sakai, 2004[393]	Japan	1981 - 2003	-	1	DTP	Rate per 10 million	0.5	Case ascertainment= Clinician-developed diagnostic criteria Number of doses: DTP= 25,100,000 DTaP= 40,300,000
				1	DTaP		0.2	
Pan, 2022[394]	China	2015 - 2020	-	5	DTP-IPV/Hib	Reporting odds ratio	1.16	Case ascertainment= ICD-10 Number of doses = 2,860,884
Wu, 2017[395]	China	2008 - 2013	-	1	JE-L (live-attenuated)	Reporting rates (per million doses)	0.007	Number of doses = 139.5 million
Chang, 2013[396]	USA	2005 - 2007	Median: 22	4	Tdap	Rate per 100,000 doses	0.05	Case ascertainment= BC
Souayah, 2011[351]	USA	2006 - 2009	Mean: 16.7	52	Menactra	Annual reporting rate per 10 million treated patients	23	Number of doses = approximately 22.6 million doses
Souayahm, 2009[352]	USA	1990 - 2005	Mean: 47	-	Hepatitis B	Incidence per million vaccinations	2.4	Risk period = 6 weeks

Myers, 2020[397]	USA	2005 - 2016	Median: 14	120	MenACWY-D	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.17	Case ascertainment= BC Number of doses = 70,312,683
McNeil, 2019[398]	USA	2011 - 2018	Median: 19	12	Adenovirus type 4 and type 7	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.92	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = Over 1.3 million
Tavares Da Silva, 2020[399]	Multiple countries	2017 - 2019	Median: 65	17	RZV	Reporting rate per 100,000 doses	0.18	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Risk period = 42 days Number of doses = ~ 9.3 million
Moro, 2016[392]	USA	1990 - 2015	-	4	Human diploid cell	Calculated rate per 100,000 doses	0.11	Case ascertainment= BC, MedDRA Number of doses = 3,800,000
Top, 2015[400]	Canada	1996 - 2012	<15	246	Multiple vaccines	Annual rate (95% CI)	2 (1.4-3)	Case ascertainment= ICD-9, ICD-10 Risk period = onset ≤30 days after immunization
Sejvar, 2005[401]	USA	2002 - 2004	-	3	Smallpox	Incidence per 100,000	0.5	Case ascertainment= COSTART Vaccinated n = 665,000
Daley, 2014[402]	USA	2009 - 2012	4-6	1	DTaP-IPV	Relative risk, Vaccine Safety Datalink	2.98	Case ascertainment= ICD-9-CM subject to manual review Risk period = 1-42 days Number of doses = 201,116
RCT (n=1)								
Bi, 2020[403]	Finland	2007 - 2014	12-15	1	HBV	Incidence 100,000 person-years (95% CI)	1.3 (0.00-7.4)	Case ascertainment= ICD Risk period = 18 months Vaccinated n = 17,338
Other Studies (n=1)								
Hughes, 2006[120]	UK	1992 - 2000	0-100	7	Influenza HAV, HBV, tetanus, meningo	Adjusted Relative Risk (95% CI)	1.03 (0.48-2.18)	Case ascertainment = Diagnostic codes Risk period = 42 days

					coccal, polio, diphtheri a			
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APPENDIX 4

GBS Case Definition Key Caveats for Diagnosis, Data Analysis and Presentation

4.1. GBS Case Definition[1] Key Caveats for Diagnosis, Data Analysis and Presentation

- **Key elements of Case Definition (CD)**
 - Both GBS and MF have 3 levels of diagnostic certainty and the lowest, level 3, is limited to clinical findings.
 - Critical for GBS to meet CD level 3 is demonstration of absent or decreased deep tendon reflexes in the same limbs that are weak. Without this it cannot meet any level of certainty.
 - Miller Fisher is an infrequent GBS subtype that includes bilateral ophthalmoparesis and ataxia, usually without limb weakness. GBS/MF overlap syndromes may occur, where there is weakness and features of MF. (See Appendix 5, Figures 1A and 1B - Pictorial Algorithms). In such cases the level of certainty should be based on the GBS criteria, but it can also be described as GBS/MF overlap syndrome.
 - For both GBS and MF there must be sufficient follow-up to demonstrate a monophasic illness pattern (see Appendix 5, Figures 1A and 1B - Pictorial algorithms) and no alternative diagnosis for weakness. That said, lack of testing for alternative diagnoses does not impact on the ability to meet the case definition.
 - CIDP must be distinguished from GBS; the clinical picture may be identical but CIDP tends to onset over 8 or more weeks and weakness tends to remit and relapse[1]
- **Recommendations for real time assessment**
 - Ensure that the degree and distribution of limb weakness is assessed and that deep tendon reflexes are assessed in all weak limbs.
 - If possible, seek assessment by a neurologist and ask that the following assessments be recorded: manual muscle testing using the Medical Research Council scale; deep tendon reflexes; sensory and cranial nerve examination; presence or absence of ataxia. Measures of functionality or disability would also be helpful. These are provided in the published case definition appendices and reproduced here in Appendix 5, Table 5.2.
 - Full assessments should ideally be done at:
 - Initial presentation to medical care
 - At clinical nadir (see below)
 - At all subsequent points where there is significant change in neurologic status until a final outcome endpoint is reached (recovery, death, end of follow-up). If not possible, assessments should be done weekly for 4 weeks, monthly for 5 months and then once every 3 months.
 - A date/time for the clinical nadir (defined as the worst state of clinical symptoms) should be determined. Normally for GBS there is a steady progression in weakness to a nadir point followed by a plateau, fatal outcome or gradual improvement. Therapies such as immunoglobulins or steroids may cause fluctuations in levels of weakness – all of which should be carefully documented. These are usually within the first 9 weeks.
 - Level 1 of certainty requires CSF WBC and protein results showing cyto-albuminologic disassociation (WBC <50, elevated protein) and characteristic electrophysiological test results (EMG, nerve conduction studies) as outlined in Appendix 5, Figures 1A and 1B (Pictorial Algorithms). Of note electrophysiological tests can be normal if obtained in the first 7 days after symptom onset. If normal, testing should be repeated, if possible.

- Level 2 of certainty can be reached with either CSF or electrophysiologic testing rather than both.
- Nerve conduction studies may be normal if done within 7 days of onset of weakness. If normal at that time, they should be repeated after 1 to 2 weeks.
- Level 3 relies solely on clinical findings, of which the most important are the requirement, for GBS (not Miller Fisher variant) that the deep tendon reflexes be absent or decreased in the same limbs that are weak.
- Confirmed alternate etiologies that exclude a diagnosis of GBS, or Miller Fisher Syndrome are listed in Table 5.3 in Appendix 5. Investigation for these is not required to meet the case definition but if found do rule out GBS or Miller Fisher syndrome.
- If real time assessment is not possible, the SPEAC data abstraction and interpretation form (Appendix 5) can be used in conjunction with medical records to gather the information needed to assess the level of diagnostic certainty.
- Testing for autoantibodies is not required for the case definition. May be relevant to type of GBS with anti-ganglioside antibodies absent in AIDP, but present in AMAN/AMSAN (GM1, GD1a) and Miller Fisher (GQ1b, GT1a). [4]

Data Collection Guidelines

- Gather detailed clinical descriptions of symptoms/signs and time course including severity of weakness at the clinical nadir, additional neurologic signs of GBS (e.g., fasciculations, atrophy, myoclonus).
- Document other concurrent signs, symptoms and diseases.
- Document the dates and results of all:
 - electrophysiologic studies (electromyography [EMG] and nerve conduction velocity studies [NCS].
 - additional neurophysiologic studies including electroencephalography [EEG], neuroimaging studies (computed tomography [CT] or magnetic resonance imaging [MRI].
 - CSF examinations including WBC (cells/uL), RBC (cells/uL), differential WBC count if available, protein (mg/dL), glucose (mg/dL) and if done a concomitant serum glucose. The upper limits of normal for the laboratory performing the CSF analysis should be documented.
 - Tests done to identify and/or rule out alternative etiologies for weakness.
- Document nature and dates of all therapy given for GBS/MF.
- Document the neurologic/functional outcome and disposition at last observation.

Data Analysis Guidelines

- In the setting of pre-licensure trials, it is unlikely that more than one or a few cases will be reported. The guidelines in the published case definition provide suggestions for data analysis and presentation of scenarios where several cases are assessed (e.g., self-controlled case series study). These are not reproduced here but can be easily found in the published guidelines section 3.2.[1]

APPENDIX 5

GBS Data Abstraction and Interpretation Form With Algorithms for Assessing Level of Certainty and Glossary of Terms

5.1. GBS Data Abstraction and Interpretation Form with Algorithms for Assessing Level of Diagnostic Certainty.

The form is organized in a series of Steps presented as tables.

- **Step 1** guides the collection of data needed to meet the case definition criteria for GBS. Depending on the specific criterion, data are collected using two formats:
 - i. as mutually exclusive answers of YES, NO or UNKNOWN to a series of questions
 - ii as a checklist of specific things that were noted to be present (i.e. YES) like signs or symptoms, or lab test results.

Relatively simple criteria used in the case definition may be defined directly in step 1. Others may require formulae to define – as done in Step 2.

- **Step 2** uses some or all of the data entered in Step 1 to assign values (YES, NO or UNKNOWN) to each case definition criterion.
- **Step 3** is a small tabular summary of the assigned value (YES, NO or UNKNOWN) for each criterion in the case definition.
- **Step 4** provides a tabular algorithm to assign the Level of certainty that meets the case definition (Level 1, 2 or 3) or that does not meet the case definition (Levels 4 and 5).
- A Pictorial algorithm is presented that presents, in a single page, all the relevant criteria needed to meet the case definition and a flow diagram that shows the path to each level of diagnostic certainty depending on the criterion values.
- A Glossary of Terms is also included. Any terms defined in the glossary are **yellow highlighted** in the Step 1 data form.

The abstraction form can be used in several settings:

- As a case report form for data abstraction from a hospital/other institutional chart as part of epidemiologic studies of background incidence or to test for causal association between vaccine (s) and GBS
- Guide data collection for case validation (all or a subset) in studies where electronic health data were used for case ascertainment based on selected medical codes (ICD9/10, SNOMEDCT, MedDRA)
- Serve as a supplement to a prospective clinical trial case report form where one or more cases of GBS may be observed during the course of the trial. In such settings it may also serve as a guide for the type of data to be collected and investigations to be done at the time a possible case is identified.
- Supplement national pharmacovigilance AEFI report forms in case of the occurrence of a safety signal related to GBS
- Help to organize the data available in an Adverse Event Following Immunization Report form relative to what is needed to assign a level of certainty. Equally important the form will make it clear what data are missing and help to guide case follow-up when feasible.

The same data form will also be available online as part of an Automated Brighton Classification (ABC) Tool.

TABLE 5.1. GBS/Miller Fisher key case definition criteria, likely and actual sources of information

Criterion	Criterion category	Likely sources of information	Actual source of Information
A	Limb weakness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outpatient clinic / emergency room record(s) • Neurology / Infectious Disease / other consultation notes • Hospital admitting history & physical exam; discharge summary • ICU admission notes • Follow-up clinic records 	
B	Deep tendon reflexes		
C	Temporal illness pattern		
D	Ophthalmoparesis		
E	Ataxia		
F	Altered level of consciousness		
G	Corticospinal tract signs		
H	Electrophysiologic testing	EMG, nerve conduction study reports	
J	Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) testing	Laboratory reports – CSF analysis	
X	Alternative cause for weakness	Differential diagnosis, investigations & results (see Appendix 1)	

Step 1. Complete the case data entry form choosing the most appropriate answer as defined below:

- ‘YES’ means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was present.
- ‘NO’ means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was not present.
- ‘UNKNOWN’ means there was uncertainty in interpreting whether the criterion was present or absent, OR nothing was documented about the criterion.
- Questions regarding criteria marked with an asterisk* must be answered.

Terms with a glossary definition.

Criterion	Question	Possible Answers		
CRITERION A – Weakness of Limbs (Arms or Legs)				
A0.1*	Was there weakness of arms or legs? If YES answer A (1 through 4) below	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
A	1. Right leg weakness present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Left leg weakness present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	3. Right arm weakness present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	4. Left arm weakness present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
CRITERION B – Decreased or absent Deep tendon reflexes (DTRs)				
B0.1*	Were any deep tendon reflexes decreased or absent? If YES answer B (1 through 4) below:	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
B	1. Right leg reflexes decreased or absent	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Left leg reflexes decreased or absent	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	3. Right arm reflexes decreased or absent	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	4. Left arm reflexes decreased or absent	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
CRITERION C – Monophasic illness pattern				
C*	1. Was the pattern of illness monophasic? (Worsening from onset to a point of maximal degree of illness followed by: no further change OR improvement OR death)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Was the Interval from onset of weakness to point of maximal weakness ≥ 12 hours and ≤ 28 days?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
CRITERION D - Bilateral Ophthalmoparesis				
D	1. Was there weakness of the muscles that move the Right eye?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Was there weakness of the muscles that move the Left eye?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN

CRITERION E - Ataxia				
E1	Was ataxia present?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
CRITERION F – Altered level of consciousness				
F1	Was the level of consciousness normal or unchanged from normal baseline?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
CRITERION G – Corticospinal tract signs				
G	1. Babinski sign present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Hyperreflexia present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	3. Spasticity present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	4. Clonus present	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
CRITERION H – Electrophysiologic testing				
H0.1*	Was electrophysiologic testing done. If YES specify specific test(s) done in H0.2, if known, and answer both H0.3 and H0.4:	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
H0.2	1. Electromyogram (EMG)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Nerve Conduction Study (NCS)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
H0.3	Electrophysiologic testing showed: Choose the one best answer. If multiple electrophysiologic tests performed, choose the most abnormal test (tests done early in the course of illness may be normal) ___ 1. Primary demyelinating pattern ___ 2. Primary axonal pattern ___ 3. Inexcitable ___ 4. Equivocal ___ 5. Sensory nerve involvement only ___ 6. Normal ___ 7. None of the above			
H0.4	Electrophysiologic testing was consistent with which of the following GBS subtypes? Choose the one best answer. If multiple electrophysiologic tests performed, choose one that reported the GBS subtype. (tests done early in the course of illness may be normal) ___ 1. AIDP (Acute inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy) ___ 2. AMAN (Acute motor axonal neuropathy)			

	__3. AMSAN (Acute motor and sensory axonal neuropathy)			
	__4. None of the above			
CRITERION J – Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) Protein and White Blood Cell (WBC) Count				
J0.1*	Was CSF fluid obtained for analysis? If YES answer J (1 and 2) below.	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
J	1. Were there <50 WBC/uL of CSF?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Was the CSF protein elevated?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN

V. (Optional) Clinical features of GBS variant types (NOTE: data in this section do not contribute to the case definition of GBS, however, the data may be helpful if the case does not meet a level of certainty despite there being characteristic electrophysiologic or CSF results. In such cases, it is advised to seek expert neurologic advice as to whether or not the case could be a GBS variant).				
V	1. Was there weakness of pharyngeal muscles? (difficulty swallowing)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	2. Was there weakness of neck muscles?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	3. Was there bilateral facial weakness?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	4. Was there an acute or subacute sensory neuropathy?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	5. Was there paraesthesia?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	6. Was there hyperreflexia?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
	7. Was there weakness that was asymmetrical? (i.e., not present on both Right and Left sides of the affected area)	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN
CRITERION X – Identified alternative diagnosis for weakness				
X1*	Was there an alternative cause for weakness?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN

Step 2. Based on clinical data entered in Step 1, assign a value to CD criteria A1, B1, B2, C1, D1, G1, H1, H2, J1 and J2 using the rules in Criterion Options columns

CRITERION					CRITERION VALUE: compare data entered in step 1 table to formulae in the YES, NO and UNKNOWN columns to determine FINAL VALUE for each criterion		
CLINICAL CATEGORY	Name	FINAL VALUE (Circle / Highlight)			Criterion = YES (Y) IF:	Criterion = NO (N) IF:	Criterion = UNKNOWN (U) IF:
Bilateral Limb Weakness	A1	Y	N	U	All of A (1, 2, 3 & 4) = YES, OR A (1&2) = YES, OR A (3&4) = YES	A0.1 = NO OR ≥3 of A (1, 2, 3 & 4) = NO, OR [<2 of (A1&A2) AND <2 of (A3&A4)] = YES	A0.1 = Unknown OR ≥3 of A(1, 2, 3 & 4) = NO or Unknown*
Deep Tendon Reflexes decreased or absent in limbs that are weak	B1	Y	N	U	A(1&2) AND B(1&2) = YES, OR A(3&4) AND B(3&4) = YES, OR A(1,2,3&4) AND B(1,2,3&4) = YES	B0.1 = NO OR A(1&2) = YES AND B(1&2) = NO, OR A(3&4) = YES AND (B3&4) = NO	B0.1 = Unknown OR A(1&2) = YES AND B(1&2) = NO or Unknown*, OR A(3&4) = YES AND (B3&4) = NO or Unknown*
Deep Tendon Reflexes decreased or absent	B2	Y	N	U	B (1 & 2) OR B (3 & 4) OR all of B (1, 2, 3 & 4) = YES	B0.1 = NO OR ≥3 of B(1, 2, 3 & 4) = NO	B0.1 = Unknown OR ≥3 of B(1, 2, 3 & 4) = NO or Unknown*
Monophasic Illness Pattern	C1	Y	N	U	C (1 & 2) = YES	C (1 & 2) = NO	C (1 & 2) = NO or Unknown*
Bilateral Ophthalmoparesis	D1	Y	N	U	D (1 & 2) = YES	D (1 & 2) = NO	D (1 & 2) = YES or Unknown**
Absence of Corticospinal Tract Signs	G1	Y	N	U	All of G (1, 2, 3 & 4) = NO or Unknown	Any of G (1, 2, 3 or 4) = YES	Not Applicable
Electrophysiologic findings consistent with GBS	H1	Y	N	U	H0.3 = (1, 2, 3 or 4) OR H0.4 = (1, 2 or 3)	H0.3 = (5, 6 or 7) AND H0.4 = (4)	H0.1 = NO or Unknown
Electrophysiologic findings consistent with Miller Fisher	H2	Y	N	U	H0.3 = (5 or 6)	H0.3 = (1, 2, 3 or 4) OR H0.4 = (1, 2 or 3)	H0.1 = NO or Unknown
Cytoalbuminologic dissociation	J1	Y	N	U	J (1 & 2) = YES	≥1 of J (1 & 2) = NO	J0.1 = NO or Unknown, OR ≥1 of J (1 & 2) = Unknown
CSF WBC <50	J2	Y	N	U	J (1) = YES	J (1) = NO	J0.1 = NO or Unknown, OR J (1) = Unknown

* NOTE: If there is a combination of YES, NO or unknown that doesn't meet the rule for YES or NO, then the criterion = UNKNOWN (e.g. if A(1) = YES and A(2) = NO and A(3 & 4) = UNKNOWN, then Criterion A1 = UNKNOWN).

** NOTE: D1 = Unknown for all the following combinations: D(1+2) = Unknown; D(1=YES and 2 = Unknown); D (1=Unknown and 2 = YES)

Step 3. Record the final value for Criteria E1, F1 and X1 from the step 1 table and for criteria A1, B1, B2, C1, D1, G1, H1, H2 and J1 from the Step 2 table. Y = YES, N = NO, U = UNKNOWN

Criterion	A1	B1	B2	C1	D1	E1	F1	G1	H1	H2	J1	J2	X1
Final Value													

Step 4-A Use the final values of all criteria recorded in the Step 3 Table above to determine the level of certainty based on the formulae below for GBS. Start with Level 1 (criteria **A1, B1, C1, H1, J1, X1**). If Level 1 not met, then move to Level 2 (criteria **A1, B1, C1, H1, J1, X1**) and, if not met, try Level 3(**A1, B1, C1, H1, J1, J2, X1**). If none of Levels 1, 2 or 3 met, try Level 5 (criteria **A1, B1, C1, X1**). If Levels 1, 2, 3 & 5 not met, assign Level 4.

Level of Certainty	GBS	
Level 1	(A1 AND B1 AND C1 AND H1 and J1 = YES) AND (X1 = NO or Unknown)	
Level 2 : can be met by 2.1 or 2.2	2.1	(A1 AND B1 AND C1 = YES) AND (H1 = YES) AND (J1 = NO or Unknown) AND (X1 = NO or Unknown)
	2.2	(A1 AND B1 AND C1 = YES) AND (J1 OR J2 = YES) AND (H1 = NO or Unknown) AND (X1 = NO or Unknown)
Level 3	(A1 AND B1 AND C1 = YES) AND (X1 = NO or UNKNOWN)	
Level 4	Reported GBS but fails to meet any level of certainty	
Level 5	(A1 OR B1 OR C1 = NO) OR (X1 = YES)	

Step 4-B Use the final values of all criteria recorded in the Step 3 Table above to determine the level of certainty based on the formulae below for Miller-Fisher Syndrome. Start with Level 1 (criteria **A1, B2, C1, D1, E1, F1, G1, H2, J1, X1**). If Level 1 not met, then move to Level 2 (criteria **A1, B2, C1, D1, E1, F1, G1, H2, J1, J2, X1**), and, if not met try Level 3(**A1, B2, C1, D1, E1, F1, H2, J1, J2, X1**). If none of Levels 1, 2 or 3 met, try Level 5 (criteria **B2, C1, D1, E1, F1, G1, X1**). If Levels 1, 2, 3 and 5 not met, then assign Level 4.

Level of Certainty	B. Miller Fisher Syndrome	
Level 1	(A1 = NO)* AND (B2 AND C1 AND D1 AND E1 AND F1 AND G1 AND H2 AND J1 = YES) AND (X1 = NO or Unknown)	
Level 2 : can be met by 2.1 or 2.2	2.1	(A1 = NO)* AND (B2 AND C1 AND D1 AND E1 AND F1 AND G1 AND H2 = YES) AND (J1 AND X1 = NO or Unknown)
	2.2	(A1 = NO)* AND (B2 AND C1 AND D1 AND E1 AND F1 AND G1 AND [J1 OR J2] = YES) AND (H2 AND X1 = NO or Unknown)
Level 3	(A1 = NO)* AND (B2 AND C1 AND D1 AND E1 AND F1 = YES) AND (H2 AND J1 AND J2 AND X1 = NO or Unknown)	
Level 4	Reported Miller Fisher Syndrome but fails to meet any level of certainty	
Level 5	(B2 OR C1 OR D1 OR E1 OR F1 OR G1 = NO) OR (X1 = YES)	

* IF **A1** = YES, may be a GBS – Miller Fisher Overlap Syndrome. In such a case, determine LOC for both GBS and Miller Fisher and classify as an Overlap syndrome.

Figure 1A. Pictorial algorithm for determining GBS level of diagnostic certainty

Figure 1B. Pictorial algorithm for determining MILLER FISHER SYNDROME level of diagnostic certainty

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Term	Definition
AIDP	Acute inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy (classic form of GBS)
AMAN	acute motor axonal neuropathy (a less common form of GBS)
AMSAN	acute motor and sensory axonal neuropathy (a less common form of GBS)
Ataxia	loss of coordination in voluntary movements; can present in many ways including: lack of coordination, slurred speech, gait abnormalities, inability to balance, trouble eating and swallowing, loss of fine motor skills, tremors;
Babinski sign	when sole of foot is stroked the toes fan out and upwards (instead of curling inwards which is normal); also referred to 'upgoing toe' or 'extensor response'
Bulbar palsy	dysfunction of one or more lower motor neuron centers in the brain stem. May involve cranial nerves IX to X11 (see table on cranial nerves) with loss or decreased ability to swallow, loss of sense of taste, weakness or loss of ability to move head side to side or up and down, heart rate abnormalities
Clinical nadir	the point at which clinical symptoms are felt to be at the clinical worst. This needs to be defined and identified by the health practitioner on a case by case basis.
Clonus	Rhythmic, oscillating, stretch reflex. Cause is not completely known but thought to be related to lesions in upper motor neurons, often seen in conjunction with hyperreflexia.
Corticospinal tract signs	evidence of upper motor neuron damage (as opposed to lower motor neuron damage seen in GBS). Paralysis with spasticity, increased muscle tone, hyperreflexia and presence of primitive reflexes (defined in glossary)
CSF (Cerebrospinal fluid)	a normally clear and colourless fluid that surrounds the brain and spinal cord.
Deep Tendon Reflexes (DTRs)	Involuntary muscle contractions in response to a sudden stretch of a muscle's tendon. These indicate a healthy nervous system in terms of the signals from the brain to muscles to guide movement. They are automatic responses that don't involve conscious thought. Doctors use rubber tools, called reflex hammers, to test whether DTRs are normal or abnormal. In GBS and Miller Fisher Syndrome they are reduced or absent.
Electrophysiologic testing	Includes needle electromyography (EMG) and nerve conduction study (NCS); Either or both may be used to characterize the specific subtype of GBS or Miller Fisher Syndrome. See specific definitions for EMG and NCS below.
EMG (Electromyogram)	used to measure the electrical activity of muscles when at rest and when being used
Encephalopathy	state of being in which consciousness or mental status is altered

Flaccid weakness/paralysis	muscular weakness/total loss of function accompanied by decreased muscle tone.
GBS Overlap syndrome	Syndrome with features of both GBS and Miller Fisher. This overlap may be seen in 15% of MFS patients.

<p>Variant GBS <i>Based on Leonhard SE, Mandarakas MR, Gondim FAA et al. Diagnosis and management of Guillain-Barre syndrome in ten steps. Nature Reviews_Neurology 2019; 15:671-683. The figure is from the same article</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Brighton Case definition addresses the classic version of GBS with rapidly progressive symmetrical weakness, absent or reduced tendon reflexes. It is the most frequent type, accounting for 30-85% of cases. There may also be sensory signs like paresthesias: these are not necessary to meet the Case Definition. Two other GBS subtypes, recognized by the case definition criteria are: 1. ‘pure motor’ where there are no sensory abnormalities (5-70% of cases); and 2. Paraparetic where weakness is restricted to the legs (5-10% of cases). ● The Brighton CD also defines Miller Fisher Syndrome which is a variant of GBS (5-25% of cases). The classic triad of of ophthalmoplegia, ataxia and areflexia is required to meet any level of diagnostic certainty, but there are variants that don’t have all 3 features ● There are 4 other variants that are not covered in the Brighton case definition: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. Pharyngeal-cervical-brachial variant: weakness of pharyngeal, cervical and brachial muscles without leg weakness; (<5% of cases) II. Bilateral facial palsy with paraesthesias: bilateral facial weakness, paraesthesias, reduced reflexes (<5% of cases) II. Pure sensory variant: acute or subacute sensory neuropathy without other deficits (<1% of cases) V. Bickerstaff brainstem encephalitis which includes the features Miller Fisher Syndrome but also includes impaired consciousness and corticospinal tract signs – both of which exclude Miller (<5% of cases)
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<p>Hyperreflexia</p>	<p>Increased Deep tendon reflex response</p>
<p>Hyporeflexia</p>	<p>diminished deep tendon reflex response</p>
<p>Identified alternative Diagnosis for Weakness</p>	<p>The possible alternative diagnoses are listed by anatomic location:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Brain: Encephalitis; Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM); carcinomatous meningitis; brain stem stroke; thiamine deficiency ('Wernicke's encephalopathy') Spinal cord: Infarction, myelitis, compression by internal or external mass Anterior horn cells of spinal cord: viral infection (e.g., polio, West Nile Virus, Zika Virus); amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; progressive spinal muscular atrophy Spinal nerve roots: chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy (CIDP); cauda equina compression Peripheral nerves: metabolic derangements (e.g., magnesium, phosphates); tick paralysis; heavy metal toxicity (e.g. arsenic, gold, thallium); drug-induced neuropathy (e.g., vincristine, platinum, nitrofurantoin, paclitaxel); porphyria; critical illness neuropathy; vasculitis; diphtheria; Lyme disease; thiamine deficiency Neuromuscular junction: myasthenia gravis; organophosphate poisoning; botulism. Muscle: critical illness myopathy; polymyositis; dermatomyositis; hypokalemia or hyperkalemia; rhabdomyolysis; mitochondrial disease
<p>Monophasic illness pattern</p>	<p>a key criterion for selected BCCD case definitions. For Guillain Barré / Miller Fisher syndromes: from disease onset a steady progression to a symptomatic nadir followed by either a plateau (no worsening, no improvement), fatal outcome or gradual improvement. From the case definition footnote 10: "Fluctuations in level of weakness, before</p>

	reaching nadir, or during the plateau or improvement phases, occur in some cases, usually associated with the use of disease-modifying therapies. Such fluctuations usually occur within the first 9 weeks after onset and are followed by eventual improvement.
Muscle atrophy	a wasting or reduction of muscle mass due to disuse.
Nadir	lowest point, used to refer to the worst state of clinical symptoms related to GBS, Miller Fisher syndrome, encephalitis, myelitis or acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM)
NCS (Nerve Conduction Study)	measure how well and how fast nerves can send electrical signals. May also be referred to as Nerve Conduction Velocity study
Ophthalmoparesis/plegia	weakness/paralysis of one or more extraocular muscles responsible for eye movements (See table 5.8B).
Ptosis	drooping of the eyelid(s)
Spasticity	An increased rigidity of muscles due to brain or spinal cord injury
Symptomatic nadir	point (date) at which clinical symptoms are felt to be at their worst. Should be defined and identified by the health practitioner on a case-by-case basis.
WBC/uL	White blood cell count per microliter. Could be CSF, blood, urine or other body fluid.

TABLE 5.2 Criteria for Assessment of Severity of Weakness at Clinical Nadir and Follow-up for final outcome
Medical Research Council Manual Muscle Testing Scale

Grade	Muscular capability
0	No contractile activity
1	Muscle activity can be palpated when performing action, with gravity eliminated
2	Patient can move limb with gravity eliminated through partial range of motion
3	Patient can't hold against resistance, but is able to move limb against gravity through range of motion
4	Patient can hold the position against moderate resistance, has full range of motion
5	Patient can hold the position against maximal resistance and through complete range of motion

TABLE 5.3. Alternative diagnoses[1-4] for weakness by level in the nervous system from brain to muscle.

Nervous System Level	Investigated?	Alternative explanation for weakness	Present		
Intracranial		Encephalitis, ADEM	Yes	No	Unknown
		Carcinomatous meningitis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Brain stem stroke or encephalitis (Bickerstaff's)	Yes	No	Unknown
		Wernicke's encephalopathy (thiamine deficiency)	Yes	No	Unknown
Spinal Cord		Infarct	Yes	No	Unknown
		Myelitis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Compression	Yes	No	Unknown
Anterior horn cells of spinal cord		Viral infection: Polio / VAPP, West Nile Virus, Zika Virus	Yes	No	Unknown
		Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Progressive spinal muscular atrophy	Yes	No	Unknown
Spinal nerve roots		Chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy (CIDP)	Yes	No	Unknown
		Cauda equina compression	Yes	No	Unknown
Peripheral nerves		Metabolic derangements (magnesium, phosphates etc.)	Yes	No	Unknown
		Tick paralysis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Heavy metal toxicity (arsenic, gold or thallium)	Yes	No	Unknown
		Drug-induced neuropathy (vincristine, platinum, nitrofurantoin, paclitaxel)	Yes	No	Unknown
			Yes	No	Unknown

		Porphyria	Yes	No	Unknown
		Critical illness neuropathy	Yes	No	Unknown
		Vasculitis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Diphtheria, Lyme disease	Yes	No	Unknown
		Thiamine deficiency	Yes	No	Unknown
Neuromuscular junction		Myasthenia gravis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Organophosphate poisoning	Yes	No	Unknown
		Botulism	Yes	No	Unknown
Muscle		Critical illness myopathy	Yes	No	Unknown
		Polymyositis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Dermatomyositis	Yes	No	Unknown
		Hypo / hyperkalemia	Yes	No	Unknown
		Rhabdomyolysis	Yes	No	Unknown
	Mitochondrial disease	Yes	No	Unknown	

Table 5.4 Cranial nerves associated with eye movements

Cranial nerve	Innervated muscle(s)	Effect of dysfunction
III – Oculomotor	Superior, inferior and medial rectus muscles and inferior oblique muscle Pupillary constriction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eyeball displaced laterally and inferiorly – so gaze is down and out; inability to look up or towards the nose (adduction). • diplopia - double vision • ptosis - drooping of the eyelid • loss of pupillary light reflex
IV Trochlear	Superior oblique	Decreased or loss of ability to look up
VI – Abducens	Lateral rectus	Decreased ability to look away from the nose (abduction). May have double vision; eye tends to turn inward towards nose

APPENDIX 6

Methodology: Brief Summary

6.1. GBS ICD-9/10-CM and MedDRA Codes [404-408]

An initial set of codes were retrieved through the CodeMapper tool. Subsequently they were reviewed and classified into narrow or broad codes

CodeMapper[404] builds upon information from the Metathesaurus of the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS). The Metathesaurus is a compendium of many medical vocabularies, which have been integrated by assigning equivalent codes and terms from different source vocabularies to the same concepts. Each concept in the UMLS is identified by a CUI. A CUI is a Concept Unique Identifier for a Metathesaurus concept to which strings with the same meaning are linked. The Metathesaurus contains more than one million concepts connected to codes from 201 vocabularies. Each concept is assigned to one or more of 127 semantic types, which define broad conceptual categories like Disease or syndrome, Finding, or Substance.[405] CodeMapper was built on the version 2016AA of the UMLS. The automatic concept identification of CodeMapper is based on lexical information from the Metathesaurus. The lexical information of a concept consists of terms that can be used in free text to refer to that concept. We compiled a dictionary for the concepts in the semantic groups Anatomy, Chemicals & Drugs, Disorders, Genes & Molecular Sequences, Living Beings, Phenomena, Physiology, and Procedures of non-suppressible, English terms from several vocabularies including ICD-9 CM, ICD-10 CM, and MedDRA.[406, 407] A text-indexing engine Peregrine uses this dictionary to identify medical concepts in the case definition.[408] Of note, while SPEAC focused on ICD-9/10-CM and MedDRA codes, the CodeMapper concepts shown in the table can be used to search for codes in other systems including SNOMED-CT, MeSH, ICD-9 and Read-CTv3.

CodeMapper has three screens.

1. The first displays the free text entered by the user – in this case the Brighton case definition. Medical concepts are automatically identified in the text and highlighted inline.
2. The second displays the mapping as a table with one row for each medical concept, and one column for each targeted vocabulary. Each cell contains the names of the codes that are used to represent the medical concept of the row in the targeted vocabulary of the column. The codes are displayed when the names are hovered over with the mouse. Several user operations are available for revising the mapping. The user can remove concepts from the mapping, search and add concepts, or retrieve more general and more specific concepts. The retrieved concepts are shown in a list and can be selected by the user for inclusion in the mapping. The user can also add or remove vocabularies that should be targeted by the mapping. After every operation, the codes are automatically updated and displayed in the table.
3. The third shows a list of all operations that have been made, for later traceability of the mapping process. When the user saves the mapping, he has to provide a summary of the modifications, which is incorporated into the mapping history. The user can download the mapping as a spreadsheet file to incorporate the codes into extraction queries. The spreadsheet file comprises the original free-text case definition, the concepts of the mapping, the codes for the targeted vocabulary, and the full history of the mapping process.

CodeMapping was conducted by MS. The output of the CodeMapper concepts was reviewed by a medical expert (BL) familiar with the GBS Brighton case definitions for all Tier 1 AESI. The concepts identified for GBS were considered relevant for background incidence rate determination as well as to study hypotheses related to GBS as a vaccine-product related reaction.

For a more detailed description of methodology see SO2-D2.3 Tier 1 AESI: ICD-9/10-CM and MedDRA Codes which is available in the [CEPI Developers' Toolbox](#) and at the [Brighton Collaboration website](#).

6.2. GBS Background Incidence

What follows is the methodology used for V1.0 of the Companion Guide. It is kept here because most of the references found in that search have been kept for this guide. Details of the search done for the updated background incidence are provided in the Methods section on page 8.

systematic literature search to estimate the incidence of acute GBS in the population was conducted using the following search strategy:

("Guillain-Barre Syndrome"[Mesh:noexp] OR "Guillain Barre"[ti] OR "Guillain-Barre"[ti] OR "Guillain-Barré"[ti] OR "GBS"[ti] OR "Miller Fisher Syndrome"[Mesh:noexp] OR "Miller Fisher"[ti] OR "Miller-Fisher"[ti] OR "Fisher Syndrome"[ti]) AND ("Incidence"[Mesh:noexp] OR "incidence"[tiab]) AND English[lang] AND ("2000/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT]) AND ("Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type] NOT ("animals"[Mesh:noexp] NOT "humans"[Mesh:noexp]) NOT ("Coronavirus"[Mesh:noexp] OR "coronavirus"[ti] OR "nCoV"[ti] OR "COVID"[ti] OR "SARS-CoV-2"[ti]) NOT ("therapy"[ti] OR "therapies"[ti] OR "therapeutic"[ti] OR "treatment"[ti] OR "treatments"[ti] OR "drug"[ti] OR "drugs"[ti] OR "trial"[ti] OR "trials"[ti] OR "prevention"[ti] OR "prevent"[ti] OR "prevents"[ti] OR "surgery"[ti] OR "procedure"[ti] OR "procedures"[ti]).

Articles had to meet the following criteria:

1. Original research/meta-analysis
2. Population-based study (selecting the entire population or using probability-based sampling methods)
3. Reported an incidence estimate (or raw numbers that allowed the calculation of an estimate).

If multiple articles reported data from the same study population, the most comprehensive data were used. When studies reported on different data collection years or subgroups (sex, age), efforts to include all nonoverlapping data were made. Age, sex, study location, sources of ascertainment, and definitions/diagnostic criteria for GBS were extracted. GBS incidence estimates, raw numbers, and confidence intervals (CIs) (when provided) were recorded along with any stratified results by age, sex, or year of data collection.

Articles were screened by a single medical reviewer (BL). Screened in articles were then reviewed independently by two reviewers and relevant data abstracted for inclusion in the background rate table (MRV).

The [spreadsheet with all extracted background incidence data](#) is available in the on the Brighton Collaboration website.

6.3. GBS Risk Factors

What follows is the methodology used for V1.0 of the Companion Guide. It is kept here because most of the references found in that search have been kept for this guide. Details of the search done for the updated background incidence are provided in the Methods section on page 8.

A risk factor is “an exposure, behavior, or attribute that, if present and active, clearly alters the occurrence of a particular disease compared with an otherwise similar group of people who lack the risk factor”. According to James Last dictionary of epidemiology version 4, a risk factor is an aspect of personal behavior or lifestyle, an environmental exposure, or an inborn or inherited characteristic, that, on the basis of epidemiologic evidence, is known to be associated with health-related condition(s) considered important to prevent. The term risk factor is rather loosely used, with any of the following meanings:

1. An attribute or exposure that is associated with an increased probability of a specified outcome, such as the occurrence of a disease. Not necessarily a causal factor. A RISK MARKER.
2. An attribute or exposure that increases the probability of occurrence of disease or another specified outcome. A DETERMINANT.
3. A determinant that can be modified by intervention, thereby reducing the probability of occurrence of disease or other specified outcomes. To avoid confusion, it may be referred to as a modifiable risk factor.

Risk factors can include infection, medication, diet, surgical or medical procedure, environmental location, stress, toxins, trauma and vaccine. Attribute includes genetic makeup, age, gender, ethnicity, social status, occupation. Behavior includes smoking, drinking, other substance abuse, sexual practices, level of physical activity. A standard tabular format, as shown in the appendices was used to summarize the key known risk factors for each AESI. Risk factors are only included if there is evidence for an association with the AESI.

The published Brighton Case Definition[1] for GBS was reviewed for evidence related to associated risk factors. In addition, review articles published after the Brighton case definition were retrieved and reviewed in depth regarding known risk factors for GBS.[404-406] Additional articles were identified in the citations of the first four.[6, 7, 20, 22, 26, 27, 407, 408]

6.4. GBS Case Definition[1] key caveats for diagnosis, data analysis and presentation

The published Brighton case definition for Guillain Barré and Miller Fisher syndromes was reviewed, and key aspects identified with particular relevance to real time assessment of GBS in the context of a clinical trial where it occurs as an AEFI. In addition, the guideline section of the published GBS case definition was reviewed, and key recommendations identified for data collection, analysis and presentation.

For a more detailed description of methodology see [SO1-D2.7 Guidance for CEPI Developers](#) which is available in the CEPI Developers' Toolbox.

6.5. Data Abstraction & Interpretation Form with Algorithms for Level of Certainty Determination

The Brighton Collaboration case definition for GBS[1] was thoroughly and repeatedly reviewed by one individual (BL) to identify all clinical, laboratory and other criteria (e.g., temporal course of disease) used to define each and every case definition level of certainty.

A data abstraction form was developed to capture information relevant to the GBS case definition criteria. The form uses a standard format developed to ensure harmonized approaches between paper forms (as here in the Companion Guide) and digital forms used online. The questions in the form are designed to enable one of three possible answers:

- 'YES' means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was present.
- 'NO' means there was written or verbal evidence that the criterion was absent or not present.
- 'UNKNOWN' means there was uncertainty in interpreting whether the criterion was present or absent OR nothing was documented about the criterion

Step 1 involves completing the data abstraction form. Most of the criteria used to determine Level of diagnostic Certainty (LOC) are determined by the evidence provided in Step 1. However, for some criteria further manipulation of the data

entered in Step 1 is needed to define one or more specific criteria. This is done in Step 2. A small summary table of all the final criterion values from the first two steps is done as Step 3. Step 4 involves a tabular algorithm that uses the values of the Case Definition Criteria (YES, NO or UNKNOWN) to determine the highest achievable LOC with Level 1 being the highest, most specific level (Definite Case). A one-page pictorial algorithm is created to show the stepwise pathway to each defined LOC based on the criterion values. This algorithm is designed for use as a stand-alone tool for LOC calculation since in addition to the pathway it also provides defines the data needed for each criterion.

A glossary of terms relevant to the case definition criteria was developed based initially on the published case definition. Where possible, the term definition was taken directly from the published case definition (often from the footnotes provided within each published case definition). If there was no definition in the Brighton publication, then an on-line search was done to obtain definitions based on available medical dictionaries or other on-line resources. The glossary is provided for use by data-abstractors without a medical background.

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